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The Human Right to a Healthy Environment

in Kenya through the voices of the people:

an assessment of its realisation and

consolidation processes in Kisumu County

Written by: *Sharon Fera*

Supervisor: *Prof. Enzo Colombo*

Co-supervisor: *Prof.ssa Chiara Ragni*

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Introduction

Environmental degradation has become in the last century increasingly pervasive, destabilising ecosystems and exacerbating inequalities worldwide, in connection with a fast and intensive economic development and anthropogenic industrial activities. The magnitude of this crisis and the conceptual shift in the role of humanity from being a part of nature to being a geological agent itself, brought scientists to individuate in the first 2000's a new geological epoch in the life of our planet, marking the passage from the Holocene to the Anthropocene¹ (Vidas *et al.*, 2014). This new tight bond between man and nature, where both have mutual effects on the other, has been felt not only in scientific field, but also social, political and legal. It brings along a sense of danger and of urgency that, starting from the '70s, lead local activists and social movements to claim for this new need of protection, and institutional frameworks to translate the new environmental dimension of human life into some form of right, attempting to create regulation and safeguarding. Treaties and soft law started to proliferate worldwide, but always with embryonal, uncertain, and emblematic shape; still today, the nature and the definition of this bond do not appear immediately clear in a cohesive way globally, neither in common sense perception nor in legal terms.

The first chapter of this research presents a profound reconstruction of the progressive development of environmental human rights in social discourse and in legislative frameworks, through a careful literature review, aimed at outlining a precise academic and historical profile of the right to be investigated. Having a clear and reliable understanding of the matter under study is essential not only for the researcher but also for the reader to -respectively- develop and acquire critically, a comprehensive and aware analysis of an emerging right. “Environmental rights”, “environmental human rights”, “human right to a healthy environment”: the chapter goes along the evolution of different labels and approaches, highlighting their improvements and their shortcomings. As a

¹ The Anthropocene is a concept developed to indicate that human imprint on the Earth system may have already reached a geological magnitude, focusing on the role of humans in the destabilization of the planet. It offers a broad framework for bridging the *perceived* divide between *nature* and *humans* (*ibidem*).

conclusion of the review, it will be found that legal definition and recognition of the right does not, in this case, imply its *realisation*. The latter requires further empirical study.

The effects of climate change, pollution, and ecological collapse are intensifying at global level, but most frequently the most severe impacts are suffered especially where institutional capacity, economic resources and environmental resilience are the weakest. Among others, this is the case of Kenyan territories, especially continental rural ones. Having the possibility volunteer there engaging in a project for environmental resilience, I decided to combine the opportunity with on the ground research on the topic, to inquire exactly the level of realisation of the studied right in a focus region of the planet, and to eventually examine qualitatively the process that lead to that point.

Before jumping in the core of the research, the second chapter will present the methodology by which the investigation was conducted, describing accurately all the three phases of prefiguration, data collection and data analysis, on the basis of the rigorous guidelines elaborated by the scholar in qualitative methods for social research, Mario Cardano. In-depth interviews have been the favoured technique, in line with the aim of conducting a qualitative study of the local reality. A relevant aspect to be highlighted is that the present research was led with a solid ethnographic approach which aims, through a role of participative observation of the researcher towards the object, to give value to the *voices* of the people, bringing to the foregrounds their personal stories and feelings in relation to the topic under analysis. The choice of this method stems from the conviction that, since we are dealing with a *human* right, human experience must be central.

The third chapter represents the first set of core investigation under this thesis: it inquires whether and to what extent the human right to a healthy environment, legally recognised both internationally and nationally (Kenyan Constitution, 2010), is *realised* in Kisumu County. In view of this, it will examine whether the environment enjoys a status of healthiness, resulting in expected negative results, and the factors behind this condition, which will result to align with the Anthropocene concept elaboration. Assessed that the environment is not healthy, and that the major reason is of anthropogenic nature, a full section will be dedicated to report the consequences of such unhealthy environment on the people living in it, reserving considerable space to their personal words, stories,

and emotions. Those were often terrible, highlighting the urgent need to do more to build a HRHE, which however, according to them is averagely “being built”.

The fourth chapter wants to study *how* this right that is “being built”, carrying a qualitative in-depth analysis of the processes of its consolidation in the territory under investigation. It will explore, in two dedicated sections, how actors “from above”, intended as international, national and local institutions, and actors “from below”, intended as organised forms of civil society –prominently NGOs– and individuals, participate to the process, the quality and effectiveness of strategies they implement, their difficulties and shortcomings, as well as their interaction and mutual influences. The approach in this chapter will be tendentially descriptive, collecting practices from the experience of the people, of the NGOs and CBOs staff on the ground, volunteers, and also professionals working in the institutions, both at local and international level, whom I was able to get contact with and interview thanks to my internship at the Italian Mission at the UN and other International Organisation in Geneva while writing this thesis.

The fifth and last chapter will draw the implications and conclusions of the whole research, adopting a critical approach in the interpretation of results. The goal to identify which mechanisms and practices *effectively* contribute to build right, and which –maybe despite good intention or significant investment– fail to create meaningful sustainable change. It will explore the reasons behind these respective results, and try to individuate patterns and common ground elements that shape the trajectory of consolidating the human right to a healthy environment in Kisumu. The overall purpose is to compare and contrast the literature around this nascent right to an empirical case, adding value with possible evolutions and real-life verifications of theories and developments in the field. A more concrete ambition is to study the applications of such theories combined with the resulting findings and conclusions, to provide a basis for the actors to improve their commitment with more targeted and strategic action.

CHAPTER I

Environmental Rights: a new Human Right?

The goal of the present chapter is to provide the reader with a complete overview around environmental human rights' background -definitions, conceptualisations, state of the art, problematics-, in order to be able to better follow the empirical analysis of their possible consolidation in Kenya carried on in the core of this study.

To this aim, the first sub-chapter will explore historically their origins and development, from both a narrative-sociological and political-legal point of view. It will find that, for an effective protection of both the environment and the affected human beings, the legal instruments in place and the judicial strategies used in the last decades are not sufficient, and that the recognition and application of an autonomous "human right to a healthy environment" is necessary. Then, it will study the state-of-the art of such right in international and regional contexts and find out -by tragic episodes from the news- that even where developed, humans and the environment are not always effectively protected: a human right *realisation* does not coincide with its correspondence in human rights *law*.

The second sub-chapter will hence investigate, with the help of the existing literature, the consolidation of a human right in general and the processes by which they are realised afterwards. It will elaborate on the insufficiency of legal approaches to accomplish human rights, especially when they have a degree of collective connotation: contributes from "the above" -laws- and "from below" -civil society- are both necessary. The social aspect of human rights will be investigated in the framework of their ontology by means of the constructivist theory, and in relation to their practice, identifying which actors do participate, together with the legal instruments, to it. This will lay the ground for the empirical analysis at the core of the whole research, by providing a theoretical background and indicating the elements to be studied.

1.1 The development of environmental human rights

1.1.1 *An historical overview*

Environmental human rights do not originate as they are, being them not precisely and completely defined even nowadays: they can be described as the state-of-the-art product of an evolution of concepts enriched with new elements step-by-step over time.

The first element of this complex product is environmental awareness, which stands at the basis of any further elaboration: from the rise of environmental movements to the building of environmental rights and environmental law, and lastly to the eventual connection to human rights, or even to become an alone-standing human right itself.

Some evidence of environmental concern can be found in several periods of history in sparse areas of the world; one example is the Londoners' complaint about the smoke - thirteenth century-, then resulted in the ban of burning sea-coal by King Edward I. However, the singularity and locality of the measure, as well as the total disregard for the environment in the provision (centred on the people only), do not allow a reference to this episode for identifying the origin of environmental rights (Akyüz, 2021, p.219). Although limited by the absence of numerous scientific documents, studies of pre-colonial African environmental history agree on the attribution of "the decline of Great Zimbabwe in the fifteenth century to environmental factors such as overgrazing, deforestation and drought" (Kwashirai, 2012, p.103). However, no voice was raised relatively to these environmental issues, which hence did not develop into any subsequent form. Primordial environmental movements manifested in the US in the late 1800s: hunters and naturalist promoted preservation of the territorial natural resources and claimed for an improvement of their management, while urban reformers among which engineers and doctors demanded for enhancing living conditions in the newly growing American cities, by the means of ensured water supply and better sanitation systems (Coglianese, 2001, p.89). However, as the Londoners' case, the environmental alertness remains local, and the relative provisions remain rather connected to the single complaint than to a collective awareness and sensitivity.

Scholars agree in placing the origin of environmental rights in the second half of the 20th century, when environmental concerns became global for the first time, and - accordingly for the first time- an international voice claiming environmental protection

raised. In fact, in the 1950s, along with the global industrial development, change in the patterns of production and consumption, rapid population growth, the world could no longer ignore the level severe of degradation of nature, of which the effects impact started to be witnessed on people's lives. One key moment in this timeline that caught global attention and created general alert was, again in London, the "Great Smog" -or "Big Smoke"- of 1952: an air-pollution event that provoked 4000 deaths (Akyüz, 2021). The 1950s are also the core of the decolonisation era of African and Asian states, which unveiled the qualitative shift in landscapes and human populations' health -with respect to a previous anthropogenic and resilient approach-, provoked by the unfair exploitation of resources by the settlers: (Maddox, 1999). During this decade, people from all over the world were able to witness the effect of environmental degrade on both the land itself and people, and this "led to the concept that a safe environment is necessary for the safeguarding of human well-being *on a global scale*" (Akyüz, 2021, p.220).

In the 1960s, the new concern started to be explored and expressed also by the studies and publications of major experts and journals (e.g. Carson, Club of Rome); this fuelled the newly emerging awareness of a safe environment importance and with it the environmental movement claiming for environmental protection, not only at individual level but now at in a collective and organised way too: it is from the late '60s that the first NGOs advocating around green issues start come to existence (e.g.: Greenpeace movement was founded in 1969). The social pressure solicited a formal response, and that is how in the early 1970s "environmental thinking reached the political, social and academic agendas" (Akyüz, 2021, p.220): for the first time, environmental history is a discipline in university; academic journals in this field appeared; environmental ethics became a new branch of ethics; the first global conference on the issue of environment was held, the UN Stockholm Conference. These two decades are the moment in which the birth of the "environmental rights" rhetoric can be placed in time.

1.1.2 The development of environmental human rights in the legal framework

The 1972 UN Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment, in particular, marks a much greater step forward in the history of environmental protection, by not only recognising it formally for the first time in an international legal framework, but doing this linking it to human rights. It defines environmental quality as a pre-condition to the

enjoyment of fundamental human rights and enshrines environmental protection as a responsibility:

“Man has the fundamental right to freedom, equality and adequate conditions of life, in an environment of a quality that permits a life of dignity and well-being, and he bears a solemn responsibility to protect and improve the environment for present and future generations” (UN, 1972, Principle 2).

The Stockholm Conference also adopted concrete measures to start realizing the principles in the Declaration by establishing a Plan of Action and creating the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), the first UN programme focused solely on environmental issues (UN, n.d.). The Stockholm Declaration was widely criticised for being insufficient to effectively enforce environmental protection, as it is a non-binding document, but still represents a milestone in the history of environmental law for being primordial step for its consolidation in the context of human rights law by recognising the newly emerged interrelationship between the two dimensions.

The same critique will be directed towards the subsequent Declaration of the UN on the matter, resulted from the Rio Conference (1992), where however, a step-forward in the conceptualisation of environmental human rights was achieved: environmental preservation was no longer conceived only as a pre-condition to human rights, but as an alone-standing principle for the sake of the environment itself (Francioni, 2010). Furthermore, it starts to develop on the practical implementation of the principle, building the relationship in the field of procedural rights, which will be one of the main initial approaches adopted with respect to the matter: right to “public participation, ...access to information, ...opportunity to participate in decision-making processes, ...access to justice and administrative proceedings” (UN, 1992, Principle 10).

This strategy will become legally binding at international level for the first time in 2001, when the Aarhus Convention came into force: the “first multilateral treaty to specifically denote a human right to government information about environmental policy and decisions related to the environment” (Akyüz, 2021, p.221). The Convention was ratified by 47 parties (where one party is the whole EU), and additionally established a Compliance Committee, in charge of checking on eventual violations of the obligations.

During the following two decades, many instruments were produced at the UN level: in 2000, the eight Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) were established, ancestors of the 2015 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) protagonists of the Agenda 2030 and foreseeing seven -out of seventeen- principles connected to the environment². In 2002, the World Summit on Sustainable Development in Johannesburg gave birth to a new Action Plan, and, ten years later, the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development established the United Nations Environment Assembly, the world's high-level decision-making body on the environment, in charge of setting priorities for global environmental policies and develop international environmental law (UN, n.d.). At the same time, the Human Rights Council appointed an independent expert tasked with the study of the "human rights obligations relating to the enjoyment of a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment" (UN Human Rights Council, 2012), who in 2018 produced the *Framework Principles on Human Rights and the Environment* on the human rights obligations of States relating to environmental protection, yet not binding again (Knox & Tronolone, 2023).

Another important branch to be considered is environmental law -simultaneously developed in the international framework over the same decades.

Climate change is the protagonist of most of the instruments, starting from the creation of the *Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change* (IPCC) of 1988, the UN body in charge of assessing the science related to climate change, to the elaboration of land-mark multilateral treaties, as the *United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change* (UNFCCC), adopted in 1992 by 197 parties (gaining hence near universal membership) and establishing the Conference of the Parties (COP) -meeting on a yearly base to discuss on how to implement the Convention. It is also the parent of the subsequent 1997 Kyoto Protocol and 2015 Paris Agreement, respectively determining greenhouse gas emission reduction targets and global warming to be below 2°C (Brooklyn Law School, 2015).

All of these norms, while playing a fundamental role in environmental protection, are nevertheless limited in effectiveness by the fact that their bindingness can be prejudiced by the non-provision or the withdrawal of consensus by a State to be legally bound by it (Knox & Tronolone, 2023); in addition, they all do not relate (directly) to human rights.

² Goal 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation), Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), Goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), Goal 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), Goal 13 (Climate Action), Goal 14 (Life Below Water), and Goal 15, (Life on Land). (UN, n.d.)

1.1.3 *The evolution of environmental human rights in the judicial framework*

In the history of their development, international legal instruments have never included an autonomous globally recognised *substantial* human right to live in a healthy environment to which refer for administrative and judicial proceedings; as a result, human rights bodies had to develop an environmental jurisprudence in an indirect way: first, as seen, by employing procedural human rights to protect environmental rights; second, by “greening human rights” (Knox & Tronolone, 2023), that is the expression commonly used in the literature to mean the practice of judges, over time and across countries, to recast and re-interpret existing human rights law in a way to include environmental harm as a ground preventing the enjoyment of that particular human right (Shelton, 2006). This approach, noteworthy, follows the theoretical argument on which it is based that sees environmental preservation as a *condicio sine qua non* for numerous human rights³, also in reflection of the principle enshrined in the 1972 Stockholm Declaration.

Despite the absence of a general framework convention, evolving case-law enables the development of a certain degree of protection of the environment and of the human rights that might be affected by environmental factors. For this reason, judicial decisions and opinions are not neglectable for the sake of outlining an overview of the actual development of environmental human rights and their protection. The following lines will select some of the most relevant cases to draw a comprehensive picture of the history of environmental jurisprudence in the context of human rights (Council of Europe, 2012).

The first relevant connection between the two dimensions appears in 1985 in a statement of the Inter-American Court of Human Rights (IACtHR), in response to a petition brought on behalf of the Yanomami Indians of Brazil: “the realization of the right to life, and to physical security and integrity is necessarily related to and in some ways dependent upon one's physical environment” (Shelton, 2006, p.147), implying State parties to be required to fulfil also positive obligations -as procedural rights- in its regard.

However, the first proper environmental case involving the violation of a human right is dated 1994 and was dealt with by the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR)

³ Especially: the substantive right to life, the right to health, the right to a family and private life, the right to culture, the right to a fair trial and to have access to a court, the right to an effective remedy, the right to receive and impart information and ideas, the right to the peaceful enjoyment of one's possessions (Shelton, 2006; Council of Europe, 2012).

[*López Ostra v. Spain*]: the Court held that, even if not directly affecting the individual's health, pollution can harm the right to respect for private and family life protected by Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), and required the state to take the appropriate measures to protect against such interference (Knox, 2020). The *Guerra v. Italy* (1998) case has a similar relevance insofar -despite the claim of pollution damage was not accepted- the Court reaffirms the emphasis on the state's positive obligations towards the environment, in terms of procedural rights, as collecting and disseminating information (Shelton, 2006).

Similarly, the Court emphasised that also the right to life (Article 2 of the ECHR) does not entail negative obligations only, in the *Öneriyildiz v. Turkey* (2004) -the first environmental case before the European Court involving loss of life (thirty-nine people died following a methane explosion at the municipal waste dump). The final judgement held that to protect the right to life from environmental harm, states shall take all the appropriate measures, underlining -among the prevention measures- the public's right to information, hence using again the procedural human rights approach to environmental issues besides the "greening" one (Francioni, 2010).

At international level, it was the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) General Comment No. 14 on *The Right to the Highest Attainable Standard of Health* (2000) to first mention the connection to environmental protection of the positive obligations of states with respect to the right to life and the right to health: "state obligations to protect the right to life can require positive measures designed to reduce infant mortality and protect against malnutrition and epidemics, implicating environmental protection" (CESC, 2000, para. 36); "the right to health embraces a wide range of socio-economic factors [...] and extends to the underlying determinants of health, such as [...] a healthy environment" (*ibidem*, para. 4).

Another example of "greened" human rights is those held by indigenous people. Two relevant cases come from African and American case-law⁴, significant for the emphasis of the decisions to protect collective claims of indigenous communities to land rights (Knox, 2020; ESCR, 2010).

⁴ respectively, the *Centre for Minority Rights Development and Minority Rights Group International on behalf of Endorois Welfare Council v. Kenya* (2003) and the *Saramaka People v. Suriname* (2007) case before the Inter-American Court (IACtHR).

1.1.4 The need for a substantial human right to a healthy environment

This brief excursus on the history of the development of environmental human rights in the international framework shows how blurred their definition actually is.

After having been claimed concretely for the first time in the '50- '60s, a response from legislative bodies arrives with the Stockholm Treaty, which recognises the existence of a connection between environment and human rights, as one a pre-condition of the other. The subsequent legal instrument, the Rio Declaration, uses instead an eco-centric approach where the environment needs to be protected for its own sake, and where human rights qualify as a means through which to enforce such protection: it elaborates on the use of procedural human rights in environmental matters⁵ in order to enhance preservation (Akyüz, 2021). Though, this approach lacks a complaint mechanism that could be exercised by those affected by an environmental issue, or against states who do not guarantee a sufficient level of environmental protection.

The latter problem is solved in international and regional jurisprudence by employing the strategy of “greening human rights”, that is re-interpreting existing human rights law in an environmental situational context. However, attaching environmental protection to human rights can be a double-edged sword: if on the one hand it allows to operate in a legal system where complaint mechanisms are foreseen, yet it also limits the legal enforcement of environmental human rights to an anthropocentric view only, excluding all the situations which do not directly affect man, as nature protection and ecological balance (Shelton, 2006).

This problematic approach is perfectly disclosed by a legal document from the European system, the *Guide on Environment to the European Convention on Human Rights* -a factsheet reporting up to date case-law and relevant judicial decisions, in order to foster an evolutive interpretation of the ECHR. It draws on paper on the applicability of environmental threats as a ground for the violation of the human rights protected by the Convention, by providing a list of situations which might fall under this argumentation, but also prescribes that to assess a violation, a “direct impact” shall be found (Council of Europe, 2012). This “direct impact”, indeed, is not always easy to

⁵ An example is the right to information on environmental issues or public participation to decision-making process regarding them.

prove: it could be thought, for example, to a situation of long-time soil exploitation and consequent diminishment in productivity, hence participating to hindering the right to food; or again, a situation of environmental degradation due to climate change effects worsening accessibility to food or water in a region maybe already in difficulty. As the researcher Elena Cima underlines, “there are several theoretical difficulties, deriving from the complex, global and intergenerational nature of climate change, that significantly complicate its relationship with human rights law” (2022, p.39). As a result, in general, the impact might not be “direct”, in the sense that it is not a singular event (as a methane explosion at a waste dump [see *Öneryildiz v. Turkey*, 2004]) and might not be the *only* factor contributing to the violation of a human right; it is, however, evident that the impact of the environmental conditions is much greater than the extent to which it is considered by current environmental jurisprudence, which hence *needs* implementation. Another example, taken from a real case-law in the European jurisprudence, is the *Kyrtatos v. Greece* case (2003), where the Court did not find any violation of Article 8 from the destruction of a wetland following a drainage caused by illegal activities, claiming that the applicants -living in the vicinity of the site- could not prove their right to private life to be affected (Francioni, 2010). This paradoxical decision shows how difficult is to enforce the preservation of the environment when the juridical strategy to protect and condemn illicit activities damaging nature is to find a direct interference with the life of an individual. This anthropologic “purely individualistic conception of human rights” (*ibidem*, p.50) can be addressed as the main obstacle to an effective protection of both people and nature in connection to environmental issues: it is clear that linking environmental factors to existing human rights law, not only might not be enough to address *all* human right violations in consequence of an environmental issue, but also, it does not consider at all protection of the environment for its own sake.

At the same time, a purely eco-centric approach would not be able to address human rights violations, as in the case of the Kyoto Protocol or the Paris Agreement. The parallel and apparently complementary progress of human rights jurisprudence (anthropocentric) and environmental law (ecocentric) has indeed proved insufficient for a valuable crystallization of environmental human rights and their legally enforceable protection. In fact, the anthropocentric approach often focuses on the *consequences* of a problem (as threats to life or health, inadequate standards of living or even insufficient fulfilment of basic needs as water, food or housing, etc.), rather than addressing all of them in once by

operating on their common root cause, that is living in an unhealthy environment. On the other hand, the ecocentric approach successfully focuses on some of these root causes, but only on a long-term view (e.g.: reducing emissions to reach the zero goal), without addressing the problems that they are causing in the meantime on both humankind and nature itself.

A merge of the two perspectives might be the best solution, as “[t]he more we learn about human dependence on biological diversity, the smaller the gap between anthro- and eco-centric approaches to environmental protection appears. [...] One way to close it is by enshrining rights *of*, as well as *to*, the environment” -or, even better, “to interpret the right of humans to live in a healthy environment to include the right of the environment [itself] to be healthy” (Knox, 2020, p.92). In this way, both parts would be addressed at the same time, the environment and humans, the causes and the consequences.

To move towards this direction, the theoretical conception of human rights itself shall change: it must widen and extend itself beyond the individualistic sphere. In fact, on a procedural level, it precludes the admissibility of public interest proceedings to defend the environment, and on a substantive right, it hinders the development of a substantial right to a decent environment, and risks to be not only reductionist but even counter-productive, by relegating environmental values to a the very limited sphere of the individual interest. This reasoning should be solved evolving towards a more comprehensive conception of human rights to include their collective dimension⁶, adapting to the enhanced threat posed by environmental crisis on society, and indeed, to the entire humanity and planet (Francioni, 2010). For instance, a communitarian approach of the jurisprudence would have safeguarded the rights of the applicants of the *Kyrtatos v. Greece* case, as well as a communitarian approach of private individuals to the environment would possibly encourage more respect and attention to potential harm.

While it is necessary to work for change and towards increasingly sustainable development, unfortunately some damage has already taken place and is manifesting its negative effects *now*. To make a concrete example, in many areas of the world climate

⁶ Human rights scholarship itself has hampered for long time such a development of human rights, cautioning against their conceptual extension to the collective level, fearing it could weaken individual protections and expose individuals to community tyranny (Francioni, 2010).

change is producing droughts or disasters as floods: this puts at risk (and too often realizes the threat) the life of people in those regions, their houses, their food and water security, and they cannot wait for the effects of gas emissions control to reverse climate change to improve their conditions, as this will take decades or more: what is (also) needed is measures to *adapt* to climate change. This is the revolutionary aspect that the consolidation of a right able to address these both parts simultaneously would deliver; it has been advocated in the last decades literature by even the most prominent scholars as an autonomous substantial “right to a healthy environment”. It is from the words of the very Human Rights Committee Special Rapporteur on Human Rights and the Environment that states are called upon to support the United Nations in recognising by their resolutions “*the right to a safe, clean, healthy and sustainable environment*”. The reason for its impellent need is that the implicit bidirectional (environment and humanity) concept exposed above underlying this wording of environmental human rights, produces a high number of advantageous effects (Boyd, 2022, para. 89, e, i).

First, it provides a “common language” to environmental advocates and to victims of human right violations, which would also be linked to “a well-established social justice framework and enforcement infrastructure” (Rodríguez-Garavito, 2018, p.165). The formal recognition of this right at international level would in fact be able to raise awareness in the common sense, create and energize movements and in turn support advocacy for global agreements (*ibidem*, p.159; Knox, 2020, p.90). This would be path towards an effective enjoyment of healthy conditions by both of the two targets of this right, as social, political and legal protections all foster each other. The creation of international provisions could likely boost the inclusion in domestic legal systems of the principle, providing stricter standards to be complied with, a relative enforcement mechanism and a stronger basis judicial complaint. The two scholars make use of the words of the Special Rapporteur D. Boyd to express the positive effects that an introduction of constitutional environmental rights would produce: “higher environmental standards in legislation, jurisprudence and policy; greater governmental accountability with regards to environmental policy; prevention of retrogressive laws and policies; greater citizen participation in environmental decision making; and possibly improved environmental performance” (Rodríguez-Garavito, 2018, p.165); in his empirical study, the expert also finds out that “countries with environmental provisions in their constitutions have better environmental records across several measures,

including ratification of environmental treaties and reduction of air pollution” (Knox, 2020, p.91). Furthermore, the right would imply, straight forwardly with the requirement of compliance with positive obligations, also the adoption of a *due diligence* approach to it (Cima, 2022). States would hence be held more accountable and, maybe, claimants for environmental violations would be encouraged to raise their voice. A formal recognition would also put environmental protection at the same level as the other existing human rights and provide equally valuable arguments vis-à-vis other legally protected goals -as economic development- in case of frictions (Knox, 2020; Rodríguez-Garavito, 2018).

If an effective protection is realized, the advantages are actually multiplied in terms of beneficiaries on multiple levels: type of holder, number, space and time.

Nature itself would, in fact, become also a holder of the right to be healthy, as mentioned above, besides human beings (Cima, 2022). For the sake of human-holders, it is noteworthy to consider that the environment is a common good, and that hence from the claim of one many could actually benefit from that (Rodríguez-Garavito, 2018) - consider for example the win of a case solving pollution in a specific area: not only who raised the issue would benefit from its resolution but also the other inhabitants, animals and nature in the zone. Then, the advantages can extend beyond borders, expanding the scope of this human right to an extraterritorial extension, due to the transboundary nature of many types of environmental harm (Knox, 2020). Some difficulties in jurisdiction would continue to arise, however, in the case of *global* harm -as climate change-, different from *transboundary*, due to the multiplicity of the victims and perpetrators, hence struggling to identify the subjects of the matter. Nevertheless, the recognition of the right’s extraterritorial scope of application appears to be slowly consolidating in jurisprudence alongside the right itself, through decisions and advisory opinions of courts and tribunals throughout the world⁷ (Cima, 2022).

Last, the holders of the right to a healthy environment would extend also to future generations. What has emerged clearly in the latter decades, is that the relationship between the environment and mankind is producing effects also -if not mostly- on the long-term: the exploitation of resources of today can cause a harm in the following years,

⁷ See for example, the Advisory Opinion on the *Palestine Wall Case*, International Court of Justice (2004); Advisory Opinion on the *Atapattu Case*, Inter-American Court of Human Rights (2017). (Cima, 2022)

as it happened with the economic boom of the '50s (see *Section 1.1.1*), or more broadly with the '900s industrial progress and its contribution to climate change and pollution. Sustainable development has become a priority in the world social and political agendas, being it by definition “meeting present needs without compromising the chances of future generations to meet their needs” (Sustainable Development Summit, 2023), hence laying the ground for the crystallization of the intergenerational equity principle in the application of the newly emerging human right to a healthy environment (Knox, 2020).

Steps towards the consolidation in a legal framework of this needed and advocated human right to a healthy environment, have been moved lately in the international panorama: it of great relevance the Human Rights Committee *General comment No. 36 on Article 6 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* [right to life], which not only recognises the threat to life of present and future generations by “environmental degradation, climate change and unsustainable development” (Human Rights Committee, 2019, para. 62) but also includes in the “necessary measures to respond to death threats, [...] the creation and maintenance of a safe and enabling environment for defending human rights” (*ibidem*, para. 53).

Nevertheless, the right to a healthy environment as a *human right* appeared in an official and authoritative piece of international (soft) law only in 2022, in a UN General Assembly resolution [A/RES/76/300], on the footsteps of a precedent resolution of the Human Rights Council [A/HRC/RES/48/13] (October 2021), where it was framed as a “right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment”, generally understood to include the substantial rights of “the right to clean air; a safe and stable climate; access to safe water and adequate sanitation; healthy and sustainably produced food; non-toxic environments in which to live, work, study and play; and healthy biodiversity and ecosystems”, and the procedural rights of “access to information; the right to participate in decision-making; and access to justice and effective remedies including the secure exercise of these rights free from reprisals and retaliation” (UN et al., 2023). This decision, which was adopted with unprecedented support (161 votes in favour, 8 abstentions, and no votes against), represents a landmark development in the history of human rights, as it shows that States can and are willing to work together to collectively and effectively address environmental issues. According to the UN Secretary-General, António Guterres, this resolution, despite being non-binding, will have a great impact in

enhancing environmental justice by accelerating implementation of the obligations and commitments in the field, and will empower people, especially those in the most vulnerable situations (UN News, 2022).

1.1.5 Recognising a right to a healthy environment is yet not enough

While at international level the right to a healthy environment was recognised as a human right only after a long-time struggle between social and political forces⁸ and only in a non-binding -hence “potentially ineffective”- document (Knox & Tronolone, 2023), at regional level and national level it has already been present for decades in human rights instruments which furthermore are legally enforceable.

Among the regional systems, the first and still most developed instrument was produced by the Organisation of African Unity in 1981 -less than a decade after the Stockholm Declaration and more than forty years before the UNGA resolution-: the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights became at that time the first human rights treaty to include an environmental right, providing in Article 24 that all peoples have the right to “a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development.” (Knox, 2020). In 1988, the right of all people to “a general satisfactory environment favourable to their development” was included in the American Convention on Human Rights by the adoption of the Additional Protocol of San Salvador and later in the new millennium also the Arab League and the Association of Southeast Asian Nations recognised the human right to live in a healthy environment, respectively in the 2004 Arab Charter on Human Rights and the 2012 ASEAN Human Rights Declaration (*ibidem*). In contrast, no explicit recognition of such right has ever appeared in the European legal framework, neither the European Social Charter explicitly recognises a right to a healthy environment.

Noteworthy instead, at national level, more than a hundred constitutions guarantee a right to a healthy environment, impose a duty on the state to prevent environmental harm, or mention the protection of the environment or natural resources (Shelton, 2006).

The positive effect of including such a right in a binding piece of law was made manifest for the first time exactly in the first regional system to have adopted it: in 2003, the African Commission on Human and Peoples' Rights was called to be the first

⁸ A particular opposition came from the United States and the United Kingdom.

international human rights body to decide a contentious case involving violation of the right to a general satisfactory environment, after the claim of two non-governmental organizations on behalf of the people of Ogoniland, Nigeria (Shelton, 2006)⁹. As many other multinational oil companies, in the 1950s the Shell Petroleum Development Company of Nigeria started carrying out extensive oil exploration and extraction in the Niger Delta, provoking though, over time, widespread environmental degradation, including oil spills, gas flaring, and pollution of water sources. This devastated the ecosystem and the livelihoods of the Ogoni people, who suffered consequent violations of their human rights to health, life, a clean environment, housing, and food. The Nigerian government was accused of these violations, as supporting these oil companies and failing to regulate their activities. The case assumes landmark relevance not only because the Commission assessed the claimed violations, but especially because of the positive obligations that it found to arise under Article 24, requiring the state "to take reasonable and other measures to prevent pollution and ecological degradation, to promote conservation, and to secure an ecologically sustainable development and use of natural resources" (*ibidem*, p.167) and for the concreteness of the recommendations issued to the Nigerian government to clean up the polluted areas, compensate affected communities. The *Ogoniland* case shows the effectiveness of foreseeing a right to a healthy environment for the protection of human rights: it is much easier to find evidence for one claim, than to address every single human right one-by-one: the right to live in a healthy environment already encompasses the right to life, health, housing, food and water.

The effectiveness of including such a right in the national constitution was instead studied and demonstrated by the Special Rapporteur on human rights and environment David Boyd: as reported by the prominent scholar J. Knox (2020), his empirical research shows that countries with environmental provisions in their constitutions have stronger environmental laws; for example, they are more likely to ratify environmental treaties and to perform better in reducing air pollution.

Nevertheless, even a formal recognition of a human right to a healthy environment does not appear to be enough to *effectively* protect the environment and the people. The Amazon Rainforest continues to be deforested, resulting in loss of biodiversity and in

⁹ ACHPR, Communication 155/96: *Social and Economic Rights Action Center (SERAC) and Center for Economic and Social Rights (CESR) v. Nigeria* (2001) (Ogoniland). (Cima, 2022)

threats to Indigenous people's livelihoods (UNCHR, 2022); almost 40% of people across the United States are living in high levels of polluted air (CNN, 2024) and even more severe issues of air pollution in various Chinese cities are provoking respiratory diseases and premature deaths (OHCHR, n.d.); hundreds of millions of other children in many parts of South and Southeast Asia were impeded to go to school due to unprecedented heat levels and absence of adequate means to face it (e.g.: proper air-conditioners) (CNN, 2024); violent floods are hitting countries across Europe provoking displacement and death -219 deaths in Valencia after the 7th November flood, and multiple flooding cases experienced in Italy- (tgcom24, 2024); the Turkana region in Kenya is facing prolonged droughts and resource scarcity enhanced by climate change, that are threatening health, food security, and livelihoods (Human Rights Watch, 2015); more than 24 million people in southern Africa face hunger, malnutrition and water scarcity due to drought and flood; 376 million people around the world have been forcibly displaced by floods, windstorms, earthquakes or droughts since 2008, with a record 32.6 million in 2022 alone (EU Parliament, 2023).

The news unveil an important concept that will be fundamental for the present analysis: environmental human rights *law* does not equal environmental human rights *realization*. Environmental issues continue to be perpetrated all over the world, and increasingly affect human beings, almost indifferently from the norms in place in that area: the violent floods provoked by climate change are experienced with disastrous consequences in both Italy, which is bounded neither by a national nor an international norm, *and* Kenya, which instead has both. The presence of a hard law establishing such a right does not imply an effective protection: for example, only the African Charter is reviewable by an international body, while neither the Arab Charter nor the ASEAN Declaration foresees an oversight mechanism; it also happens that despite court's decisions are legally binding, states do not always comply with them (Knox, 2020).

It appears clear that something else than legal instruments shall participate to the actual consolidation of a new human right. In the following subchapter, we will investigate this -making use of the literature-, to detect all the factors that need to be studied in order to yield an accountable evaluation of a new human right status.

1.2 The consolidation of a new human right

1.2.1 Deficiency of legal recognitions in the ontological discourse on human rights

The belief that the existence of a right is only linked to specific qualifications such as citizenship or to provisions in pieces of legislation has been contested and dismissed in the modern literature on human rights. The prominent and accredited scholar Amartya Sen -philosopher and Nobel prize in economic sciences-, has extensively argued on this, maintaining that “proclamations of human rights, even though stated in the form of recognising the existence of things that are called human rights, are really strong ethical pronouncements as to what *should be done*” (Sen, 2009, p.357). By stating that formal recognition does not imply *existence* of a right but is rather an indication of the intended, or even only desired, direction to be taken, he implies that to the concrete emergence of a human right concur many other factors, both before and after such formalisation. Before, as the right emerges from practical difficulties, needs, and consequent voices advocating for it (as happened in the case of the right to a healthy environment, see *Section 1.1.1*); after, as the legal provisions serve as setter of the path to be followed in order to arrive to the point claimed. This does not nullify or reduce the significance of legal recognitions and conquests; instead, it underlines the prominent role they have in boosting action that can build the *realisation* of a human right: while they do not qualify *per se* the existence of a right, yet legal means are fundamental instruments to it, and as a consequence, this view does not downplay their role but only confirm that progress in the legal framework shall always be worked on to go further. Nevertheless, it unveils how important it is to distinguish human rights law from the actual existence of a human right, and hence to extend research for the evaluation of such existence to other forces as well. The whole reasoning is based on the approach to social justice that he adopts in his rhetoric, where “public scrutiny” (*ibidem*, p.360) is central, meaning that the proof of existence shall be looked for in empirical checks, which law-centred conceptions of rights fail to deliver (Rodríguez-Garavito, 2018). The example of this is exactly what questioned in the previous paragraph: the reason why so many injustices still happen violating the right to a healthy environment although -somewhere even widely- protected under soft and hard law norms, is because those laws are not necessarily a description of a *realized* situation, but most likely only an ethical assertion.

The ontological essence of human rights is hence to be framed as an “articulation of an ethical demand” (Sen, 2012, p. 320), following the reasonings proposed by the prominent scholar of the mid 20th century Herbert Hart seeing human rights as *moral* rights, being -rather than the contrary¹⁰- “parents of law”, insofar they motivate specific legislation (Sen, 2009, p. 363). This appears to be the case also for the right at stake in this study: as shown in the first sections of this chapter, it is from claims arising from below that legal recognition of the right to a healthy environment was encouraged. The effect that these legal instruments have or will have on the *realisation* of this right are then to be evaluated in a separated analysis.

As a bottom line, human rights can be described theoretically as ethical claims, and in the timeline of their development, legal proclamations do not place themselves neither at the beginning nor at the end: they do not represent *per se* the origin of a right, but consolidate with formal recognition a process started long before, putting a new claim on paper; also, they do not imply full realisation of that right, but rather participate to its realisability.

1.2.2 *Realisability and realisation processes of human rights*

Feasibility is a debated question in the ontological discourse around human rights, especially second and even more third generation ones¹¹. If this requirement was to be accepted as a precondition for qualification as a human right, the risk would be to exclude many of the rights classified in those categories from discourse and protection, hence actually hampering their realisation: it appears in fact impossible to be able to *fully* accomplish economic equality among the members of a society, and even more to achieve absolute peace in the whole world. Similarly, it would be puerile and misleading to think to be able to achieve a perfectly healthy environment, and even more impossibility to frame

¹⁰ The contrary, law-centred theories, see institutional creation of a norm protecting a specific human right as the base of its origin and essence. These are sustained by also prominent scholars as Jeremy Bentham, father of utilitarianism, who refuses universalism and transcendental origins of human rights, criticising the law of nature as giving birth to equally imaginary rights, as Sen also agrees, but then arguing in favour of the positive law as parent of a substantial right, here differently from the more modern and accredited theory developed by Amartya Sen.

¹¹ Second generation rights being economic, social and cultural ones, and third generation rights being the so called “solidarity rights”, which include the rights to development, to peace, to a healthy environment, to share in the exploitation of the common heritage of mankind, to communication and humanitarian assistance (Council of Europe, n.d.).

this in every part of the world. Nevertheless, this shall not be an excuse not to work through these objectives. In the words of Sen, from his book *Elements of a Theory of Human Rights*: “the understanding that some rights are not fully realised, and may not even be fully realizable under present circumstances, does not, in itself, entail anything like the conclusion that these are, therefore, not rights at all. Rather, this ethical understanding suggests the need to work toward changing the prevailing circumstances to make the unrealized rights realizable, and ultimately, realized” (2012, p. 348). The roots of this rhetoric of Sen’s are to be found in his idea of justice (as from the title of another of his prominent works), being social justice the main ground of justification of human rights: according to him, the objective shall not be to *eliminate* injustice, but rather to *reduce* it, and not to necessarily reach the full realisation of the claimed right, but rather to *tend* towards it. This very pragmatic approach allows to avoid risk of a deadlock point that a transcendental and utopistic thinking of a just society could bring with it; rather, social justice shall be framed in a comparative way, with roots in the specific and real situations (Sen, 2009). Translated in a concrete instance, it allows to stimulate action to reduce -and prevent additional- environmental damage and its impact on human lives, and take steps in the direction of *adaptation* to climate change instead of completely giving up on the ground of the irreversibility of some loss or of the very long times required to reverse the situation to healthy and safe levels.

This reasoning is especially crucial when considering human rights of third generation, as it is the right to a healthy environment. The generational repartition of human rights, introduced in 1979 by the Czech French jurist Karel Vašák as a simplified record of the historical evolution of human rights¹², points out some specific differences that allow a distinction among rights and talks about their realisability. Although some of these proved over time not to be accurate, if not taken as strictly distinguishing clear-cuts among the groups, they can be useful to pragmatic reasonings and to comprehend the functioning and implementation of the different human rights.

¹² Vasak argues that Human Rights can be classified into three generations: first generation, civil and political rights (18th century); second generation, social-economic-cultural (19th century); third generation, collective or solidarity rights -such as the right to development, to peace, to a healthy environment- (20th century). A fourth generation seems to be developing in human rights discourse in the 21st century, which includes rights linked to the development of biotechnology, genetics and information technology (Mazzeschi, 2021).

The two International Covenants (1966) -the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* (ICCPR) and the *International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights* (ICESCR)- are extremely important for being the first international human rights treaties (hence with binding force) to have been ratified at almost universal level, with a respective number of ratifications of 114 and 112 countries. For this reason, together with the *Universal Declaration of Human Rights* (UDHR, 1948) that has inspired them, they form the International Bill of Human Rights (UN, n.d.). They provide a good distinction of first- and second-generation rights characteristics (even if the distinction is never formally and explicitly made in the legal document), and represent the turning point for their concrete consolidation. The analysis of these two aspects will be relevant for the sake of the present study to highlight by comparison the differences and new difficulties arising in the case of third generation right -which the right to a healthy environment is-, keeping in mind that each subsequent generation shall not be understood as a separate one, pictured in a horizontal division of the categories, but rather as an evolution of the precedent one: building on it, adding new characteristics to it, and interrelating with it, especially in terms of realisation.

To start, the two Covenants show some of the main theoretical differences between first- and second-generation rights: the first regards the type of obligation demanded, that is respectively negative and positive, where the first means a requirement of abstention of the State, and the second supplements (also) its active intervention. The second difference, that is the timing of the effects of such obligations, comes as a consequence of the nature of the rights considered and the type of obligation entailed: in the first case, they will be *immediate*, with the sufficiency of the enforcement of a binding legal instrument; on the contrary, in the case of second generation rights, they will be witnessable only in a longer term, because the measures are “programmatic”, insofar they require not only legislative but also administrative, organizational and technical measures, which imply particular costs and a gradual implementation over time (Mazzeschi, 2021). Third generation rights are more akin this latter category, with the effects going in the same direction but further. As the prominent Professor and Law scholar Monica Pinto underlines in her comment on the ICCPR and ICESCR, “the growing shared understanding that progressivity does not imply the absence of immediate obligations created room for the intervention of courts and tribunals [...] and clarified that some engagements could be immediately satisfied like the principle of non-

discrimination” (2020), while third generation rights are more volatile and present less instances of possible immediate measures, being often reduced to mere “political action programmes” (Mazzeschi, 2021, p. 138), and are vulnerable to the argument that their realisation can be “delayed *sine die*” (Pinto, 2020). The critique shall be solved by opposing Sen’s approach to social justice (see *Section 1.2.1*).

The second relevant aspect is that the two Covenants, together with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (which they reflect almost completely but with a binding effect), played an essential role in the consolidation of the rights they enshrined. They formalised the claims of Western countries for civil and political rights, and of socialist countries for economic, social and cultural ones, and contributed quickly to their practical realisability, thanks to their character of entailing (fully or in part) obligations *of result*¹³ (Mazzeschi, 2021). Recalling the lines on the ontological discourse around human rights, it is possible to notice that also in the case of these sets of rights, the origin cannot be placed in the legal instruments *per se*, but rather in the ethical claims coming “from below” that lead to their establishment; an example is the claim for the right to vote of women, which started already in the late 18th century in France under the voices of Antoine Condorcet e Olympe de Gouges, evolved in England with the Suffragettes movement in the Victorian era, and obtained there a first victory in the early 20th century. The right *per se* already *existed*; just, it started to *realise* after that the institutions recognised it. In particular, after the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, enshrining universal and equal suffrage (Art. 21, para. 3, 1948), thirty new countries recognised such right. Whether the issuance of the UDHR is correlated to these recognitions could be further analysed, but what is evident is that the realisation of such right inevitably comes from its recognition in legal provision of the state. A contrasting example is the right to equality and non-discrimination: as Monica Pinto said, it is immediately legally enforceable as a right, even being of second generation; however, especially in the current decades, LGBTQIA+ communities are still suffering from discrimination and advocating against it even in countries where even the very same constitution foresees such equality¹⁴ (Amnesty International, 2024). The right is legally established and immediately

¹³ Obligations *of result* are those that require a party to achieve a specific outcome or result, regardless of the methods used. Compliance is judged based on whether the desired result is attained, often also if whether achieved within a given deadline (Mazzeschi, 2021).

¹⁴ According to a report of Amnesty International (2024), steps back have been moved for example in Italy in the latter years in the field of discrimination and right of expression of LGBTQIA+ people.

enforceable in theory, but still not (fully) realised as it needs *all* the individuals to actually adopt a non-discriminating behaviour. “From the above”, from the part of the law, it could be said to be realised, but not “from below”, from all the civil people, yet. This because discrimination entails in its nature a collective character, that requires the action of individuals as well, not only of an act of the State, be it negative or positive. Similarly, the environment cannot become healthy by issuance of legislative pieces establishing so, nor by the actions of a single State, or of a group of individuals. A *universal* and *collective* action is needed, and this is the main underlying reason why -in some forms also second-generation rights already- third generation rights, that by definition are collective and solidarity rights, need time to be implemented, and cannot be realised by an action “from above” only.

As a bottom line, two main points can be concluded. The first is that third generation rights are to be realised on the long-time, keeping in mind that both legal regulations and individual behaviour may not have immediate effects, but that measures are more programmatic in their nature, and may even remain mere political action. To this extent, it is important to adopt Sen’s approach and aim to reduce social injustice, rather than giving up when cannot be eliminated instantly. This progressive character of the realisation of third generation human rights also sheds light on a fundamental distinction that has to be done in order to conduct a more adequate and useful study: the ontological consolidation of a right is not the consolidation of its accomplishment. The human right to a healthy environment already exists: it does in social movements and ethical demands, it does in formal legal recognitions, it does scholarly and in the literature. What can instead be assessed is its *practice*, the level of its realisation, which is different thing and requires the analysis of different factors. A step further can then be made, stemming out exactly by the long-term character of these rights: the consolidation of a right’s accomplishment is also not its *momentaneous* realisation, it must be sustainable and durable over time to be marked as achieved (Ponti, 2024). To make the concept clear we will borrow a concrete example from the field of environmental health connected to food security: providing a child some food for one month will not make the objective of no hunger attained, because as soon as the organisation delivering this food will end its action, the right to adequate food will again be violated; the person shall be able to have food in the present, and expect to have in the future, to say to be enjoying the right.

Increasing crop production in a permanent way, reducing soil erosion by working through the factor that the factors that aliment desertification, adopting more efficient and ethic agricultural techniques, would for instance be better solutions. as underlined by the 2016 Human Development Report (UNDP) by designing it as one of the four pillars of policymaking, to assess the real consolidation of a right, its resilience is determining.

The goal is to put the people in the condition to be able to produce and enjoy that right by themselves, so that it can be ensured over time, expected not to expire in dependence to external conditions only (as the help of an NGO might be). This logic reflects the “capability approach” -elaborated by Sen to explain human rights and further developed by the philosopher M. Nussbaum-, where capability is the resulting combination of “abilities” (*id est* internal individual qualities), and external “opportunities” (Sen, 1999; Nussbaum, 2011). To reach a “functioning” (that is a certain status, as in this case, adequately nourished), the person shall be *capable* to realise it. We see, hence, the importance of the people themselves: it is fundamental that communities participate to the development processes, have control on their environment, that the change comes not only from the outside, but also from the inside.

Here we connect to the second focal point of this section: the sustainability requirement and the social character of third generation rights as the one at stake, require both actions “from above” *and* “from below”, that is formal recognitions and legally enforceable constraints, and participated action of the whole civil society. As far as the first set is concerned, we have already fathomed the several legal instruments in place in particular at international level, discovering also that some regional systems and many national constitutions have already included the right to a healthy environment in their legal texts. We have acknowledged how such a right has been finally formally recognised, revolutionarily as a human right, also in a UN General Assembly resolution in 2022 [A/RES/76/300] (see *Section 1.1.4*). It will be opportune to study the possible impact that this action from above has or might in the future have on the implementation of the right. Together with this example, it will be fundamental to understand the relationship between the actors of the above and the actors from below in the studied situation, their engagements, the results that their interactions produce. To this extent, the following sections will elaborate on the social aspect of the construction of a right, first ontologically and then in their practice, to identify the actors composing this “below”.

1.2.3 *Human rights as a social construct: the role of civil society*

Ontologically, a human right is constructed socially in that it comes from the ethical claims of a group of individuals. This process, that we verified to be peculiar to the right to a healthy environment -as well as to the civil, political, economic, and social rights-, is the core of the constructionist theory of human rights. It upholds that human rights are a social construct produced in specific time and space, in opposition to precedent approaches according to which they are natural rights, -in other words, possessed by all human beings (at all times and in all places) simply in virtue of their *humanity*. These theories stem out from the need to detect the universal principle of human ontology that identifies human rights and explains their non-relativised character. Bryan Turner, naturalist, found such universality in the conjunction of the two conditions of human frailty and the precariousness of social institutions coping with the first, which generates a process of collective sympathy. In turn, institutions as human rights are produced as a result of a genuine human empathy (1993). However, the argument is not as solid as it may seem, in that as much as empathy can be a universal human value, also violence and thirst for power -for example- are. Furthermore, such a definition would not be able to cover all the human rights, insofar would only consider those rights related to corporal frailty, whereas many have to do also with freedom of action or with mentality -for instance the freedom of religion (Waters, 1996). The emergence of one right rather than another one, reflects the ethical demands of a specific community: a naturalist theory would not be able to explain, for example, why rights of women developed so differently in the different regions of the world; in some regions, women protest against the custom of wearing the hijab, while in some others, they are *willing* to bear it. Some women claim a right to wear what they want and eventually uncover their hair; some others do not feel a need for the same. The difference is intrinsic in their cultural context, in this case involving religion: those who practice Muslim religion may be willing to follow this practice to affirm their faith, or to find instant sisterhood with other visibly Muslim women (Shah, 2024). This example renders it clear how human rights are not naturally existing and to be delivered over time (Sen, 2009), but rather “an institution that is specific to cultural and historical context [...], and its very universality is itself a human construction” (Waters, 1996, p. 593). Empirical scrutiny of this explanation of human rights origin can be observed in the very history of each set of rights over time: claims

for personal liberties start to arise in European countries where absolute monarchies were at power, namely England (1689) and France (1789)¹⁵; demands for independency raised instead in the United States of America, as they were under the domination of the United Kingdom and felt its oppression, ultimately proclaiming rights to life, freedom and happiness in the *Declaration of Independence* (1776). The claim for civil and political rights culminated in Western countries after the two World Wars, that had seen dictatorships destroying lives and lands: it is exactly for the fear that it could happen again that the production of human rights documents proliferated in these countries starting from the half of the 20th century. It is also not a coincidence but contextual to the economic developments of the region, namely capitalism, that the rights claimed had more of an individual character. The right to own property did not arise -at least not with the same strength- in Eastern countries, where instead social and collective rights were prioritised by the community and political class, contingently to the socialist nature of their institutions and economic system (Mazzeschi, 2021). Coming to the central topic to the present dissertation, it is in connection to the contingent industrial development of the country that social demands for protection of the air quality arose in England (see *Section 1.1.1*); it is in connection to the fact that all the ten countries more at risk of climate disaster are in Africa (International Rescue Committee, 2023) that the human right to a healthy environment arrived to the attention of the political and legislative institutions in the African system before any other regional contexts.

The ontology of human rights is hence of being a social construct, in that they are originated and realised “only by the struggles of real people experiencing real instances of domination” (Stammers, 1999, p. 980), or in general, real problems and issues.

Observing the process by which rights socially emerge, -for example those already mentioned in the previous sections about the environment, the rights of women, or of the LGBTQIA+ community-, it is possible to individuate a sort of pattern involving specific elements: in relation to a situation (no matter whether political, social, or environmental in origin) impacting negatively on human beings of that region and time, awareness of a

¹⁵ After a primitive document in 1215 -the *Magna Charta*-, England was the first to recognise claims for fundamental rights in its *Bill of Rights* in 1689; their “human” connotation was recognised in the *Déclaration des Droits de l'Homme et du Citoyen* in 1789 after the French Revolution, crystalizing demands for freedom and equality.

problem slowly arises and the need for a solution becomes impellent; voices rise to claim for protection until they are enough to be listened to, creating a social movement which aims to political and juridical responses. Women protested firstly as suffragettes, the LGBTQIA+ do it with prides; environmental protection stemmed out from the Londoners in the 19th century, and continues to be demanded through FridaysForFuture in the 21st. This latter is an example of contemporary movement against climate destruction, and precisely against the inaction and incomppliance of states and political institutions to their obligations with respect to pieces of environmental law -as the Paris Agreement (see *Section 1.1.2*)- as well as their polluting activities. It was started by the 15 years-old Swedish student Greta Thunberg in 2018¹⁶, and her protest was immediately joined by millions of students around the world for about two years, skipping school and pacifically striking in front of city halls on agreed Fridays. The noise made was huge, to the point that for a period the news about this movement was on all social media and in press articles, bringing the topic to the attention of a larger public and of the political institutions. Even, Greta Thunberg spoke at the UN climate conference in Katowice, at the WEF in Davos, and at the EU parliament in Brussels, on behalf of all the young people manifesting for a safe environment in which to have a future. According to UN boards, “#FridaysForFuture will hopefully result in true climate action because the world population wants it!” (UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, n.d.). While this is only one example taken from an international general framework -and whereas many regional or even local social manifestations could be observed in the most varied forms-, it perfectly shows how social movements play a central role in that social construction of human rights that we have mentioned before, both in their origin and in their realisation. Stammers (1999) has found in these processes a triadic relationship between human rights, power, and social movements. He emphasises social movements, among other “more formally organised and ideologically coherent associations [...] clearly involved in the social construction of human rights” (*ibidem*, p. 983), for their impact in the long-term historical development. He finds them to be agents of social change, due to their role of challengers to power. However, it is important to consider that he focuses on this element of civil society for the sake of a choice of in-depth study on the specific

¹⁶ She sat in front of the Parliament every school day for three weeks, documenting her protests in social media and becoming quickly viral.

topic, not for a dominant participation to the construction of human rights. Instead, there is huge room for an analysis of who these “other actors” are, and how they contribute to the construction of a human right. Further analysis on this will be conducted in the following lines.

The example of social movements renders it clear how every single person can be fundamental in the realisation of a collective right, as the outcome is made the sum of the actions of its parts: the individual can decide to advocate, to participate to protests; they can limit pollution and waste by adopting ecofriendly behaviour and habits (e.g.: not using too much water, do the differentiated waste, choosing means of transport instead of an oil car, etc.), or the contrary and worsen the quality of the surrounding; they can also provide a positive contribution by ‘supplementary’ actions, beyond adopting sustainable conducts in their every-day life, for example actively recycling, cleaning parks and streets, or planting trees. The scholar M. Ambrosini would call this direct involvement of private individuals “active citizenship” (2021), where acts of citizenship would include not only political militancy but also *mundane* actions.

Another example of active citizenship would be volunteering, in the most varied forms: it can be done individually -for example in the own village-, or by joining a local association, an international organisation volunteering body (e.g.: UN Volunteers programme), or collaborating to a non-governmental organization (NGO)’s project.

NGOs are a very central actor in the field of the practice of human rights, for the multiplicity of the scope-orientation of their strategies, which range from documentation, reporting, advocacy, but also on field-action of relief, prevention, or development, training and education and, where relevant, litigation. They give a continuation to social movements’ role in claiming for a right and in consolidating its existence, but also widen the outreach of the voices: they contribute to raising awareness among the rest of the public opinion, can influence political agendas, even be a helpful instrument for juridical institutions¹⁷. Of great worthiness of notion, is the action that NGOs can deliver on field, autonomously and in a systematic way: examples are the construction of water bore-holes in dry regions, or of schools in poor areas, but also provide training and education to local

¹⁷ Reports and analyses of Amnesty International or of Human Rights Watch are publicly used, for example, by the International Criminal Court (ICC) (n.d.).

communities to eventually enhance their conditions self-sufficiently. The advantages of NGO's activities are many: first, as they are composed by educated experts who are able to draw purposeful and targeted plans, they are able to gather and address the positive spirit of those "active citizens" in organised and systematic action that can be more effective: those who want to contribute to a good cause but don't know how to do it can donate to the NGO and they know how to use them; those who would like to volunteer can join a project where their competences or even just their spirit can be most useful. In other words, NGOs are a catalyst of useful resources able to allocate them for the sake of a more effective action. Secondly, most frequently their actions are more *concrete* (as food or water distribution, construction of orphanages, tree planting, etc.) or play the role to complement measures of the institutions to actually implement them¹⁸. Third, they work and have effect in quicker ways than public institutions: being private entities, they are not slowed down by excessively long bureaucratic procedures, or requirements of transparency and democracy. These lower levels (which however are to be present) are also one of the main objects of criticisms directed towards NGOs (Pérouse de Montclos, 2021). Nonetheless, the benefit of their contribution to the realisation of human rights overall appears to outweigh their costs and flaws: as empirically found out by statistical researchers of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, "[p]rograms implemented by nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) are often more effective than comparable efforts by other actors" (Usmani et al., 2024). In particular, as Knox reports, a research by Gellers (2015) "finds that the adoption of an environmental right has been more likely in countries with more international civil society organizations" (2020).

Last, private for-profit actors -that is multinational or transnational corporations when they act across national borders-, can also contribute to enhance human rights with some corporate initiatives (Forsythe, 2017). Regulations do exist¹⁹, and they have the duty to respects them, especially because the impact on people's enjoyment of human rights that they can have nowadays is huge, due to their extension and power, especially related to working conditions and the exploitation of resources of a land. It is highly

¹⁸ e.g.: in Tanzania -the right to education already formally included in legal documents-, girls' enrolment in school increased after an NGO provided dual sanitation facilities at the village school (Hanchett, 2008).

¹⁹ One example is the compliance to the UN Global Compact (UNGC), establishing universal principles in the areas of human rights, labor, environment, and anti-corruption and seeking to promote a more just and sustainable global economy (UNGC, 2024); similarly, corporations are increasingly required to respect investing standards in the ESG (Environment, Social, Governance) to be encouraged to act responsibly.

explicative the Shell case of 2004, happened in Nigeria: a pipeline owned by Royal Dutch Shell leaked oil into the waterways surrounding the village of Goi, and the spill was left unchecked due to Shell's neglect and slow response. As a consequence, creek and mangrove forests -crucial to the local ecosystem and livelihoods- were polluted, and most severely, oil caught fire in a farmer's house, burning the village and the surrounding areas, causing severe harm to the community and provoking long-lasting damage to the environment (Craig, 2022). It is fundamental that multinational corporations commit to respect the environment and human rights, because the consequences of not doing so are devastating.

Made an overview of the actors participating in civil society to the construction and practice of a new human right, it results clear that *locality* is fundamental when taking into exam the assessment of a certain human right: insofar it depends not only on international rules and behaviours, but also on the local norms and especially on the people acting in that specific region (who might also come from abroad), a right might develop or realise differently in different parts of the world. This element is fundamental for the empirical research that will follow: it remarks how the specific local history, culture, issues, approach to environmental activities and to human rights, legal framework are to be investigated in order to draw a valid study. Also, it underlines how the findings on the level of practice and the kind of process verified will not to be generalised, as they can be peculiar to the region. Despite their non-universality, they can still be useful for a comparative study assessing environmental human rights in other parts of the world, to understand similar processes, or to contrast to different ones.

CHAPTER II

Methodology

The following chapter will outline the methodology used in the present study, responding to requirements of accountability and reliability that any scientific research shall comply with. To this purpose, it is useful to start from the general topic that we want to inquire, as its characteristics actually set the path to follow.

The present dissertation has the primordial objective to assess the degree of realisation of the human right to a healthy environment in Kisumu County in Kenya, with the academic interest to investigate the concrete state-of-art of one of the last consolidated human rights in contemporary times in a concrete local portion of the planet, and the processes that brought to that specific level. From a careful review of the literature, it emerged that -under the label of solidarity and collective right- the role of the people is particularly crucial in this kind of rights, as they are enjoyed by a community rather than the single individual. The communal dimension is also delivered by the right's accomplishment itself: the law is no longer enough to grant their enjoyment, as they not only do not imply negative obligations but positive, but also require an active cooperation by and among the community (besides political, legislative and judicial bodies) in order to actually come into being. Alongside the wording used in the framework of the constructivist theory of human rights, they are “social constructs”: the relevance of the people's role themselves is here determinant, and a study of the personal *enjoyment* of the right and of the personal commitment to realise it is central to the research. This will imply a closer look to the life of the people, peeking into their everyday, wearing their way of thinking and perceiving. For this reason, the research is not only of a sociological type, but also ethnographic, characterised exactly by the ability of the researcher to reconstruct and understand, by personal participation and interaction, the cultural context of the society under analysis and its members' points of view and behaviours –being this technique called *participant observation* [trad.it., (Semi & Bolzoni, 2022)]²⁰.

²⁰ Giovanni Semi has dedicated an entire book, in two editions, to the explication of such a technique, which is cantered into the humanity of the objects under study and the researcher's subjectivity, in her way not only to collect and interpret these “human” data, but also to empathize and interact with people.

In light of what concluded in the first chapter, locality has a great importance in a sociological research, both to the extent of the analysis itself and to the validity of its conclusions. As said above, different actors participate and enjoy differently a human right in different parts of the globe, and because of this the outcomes of one study cannot be generalised to the universality. The research is therefore *qualitative*, and aims to describe a deep understanding of the process in a specific area, making use mainly of textual sources and flexible methods²¹ (Cardano & Gariglio, 2022). The geographical circumscription of the data collection will here be a limited territory of Kenya in Kisumu County, namely the Nyando sub-county, where the reasons behind the choice of this specific area and its description will be provided along the incoming pages.

The chapter will be structured following Cardano's "steps of the plan" of sociological research ([trad.it.] Cardano & Ortalda, 2021). A first section -the *prefiguration*- will describe how all the phases preceding the empirical research on field were conducted, articulating the research question, defining the empirical context, explaining and motivating the method and techniques employed. A second section will display all the data obtained, categorised by technique, telling about their collection process, the eventual difficulties encountered, and the solutions found. The last section, instead, describes all that follows the experience on field: the gathering and subsequent analysis of all the data, that is how they were categorised and by which criteria, and the communication of the results, as well as the way they will be considered in light of the academic literature to assess a final evaluation of the research question.

²¹ The contrast is made with the *quantitative* type of research, which aims to a generalisation by the collection of a massive number of data that can inductively conduct to a common point, to a universal theory. Its peculiar techniques are surveys, especially with -in opposition to qualitative methods- the least possible discursive questions and the highest possible objectivity and externality.

2.1 Prefiguration

2.1.1 Research question

The final research question has itself been the result of a process, stemming out from the combination of my university studies and a volunteering experience in Kenya.

In the framework of my master's degree in cooperation and human rights, development and sustainability have always grabbed a distinct interest in me, and after learning about the social construction component of a human right's consolidation -as deeply exposed in the first chapter-, a curiosity about the current assessment of the seventeen goals of the UN 2030 agenda (SDGs) quickly grew in me; that has been at the root of my primordial thinking for thesis inquiry. Some months later, while on my Erasmus in France at Sciences Po, I acknowledged the decisive role that a (un)healthy environment plays in the enjoyment of all those seventeen goals: no poverty, no hunger, clean water and sanitation, good health and well-being, quality education, reduced inequalities, gender equality, responsible consumption and production, peace²². "Imagine a dry land:" -was explaining Professor L.A. Berg (2023)²³- "it will be difficult for people to have clean water, not only for drinking and hygiene, but also for the fields; they will probably suffer from hunger. Health will be endangered by the physical weakness provoked by insufficient water, food and sanitation and will expose people to illnesses and death risks. Furthermore, the scarcity of food and water will inflate their cost on the market, fostering poverty and increasing the threats on their life, as well as precarious and unsafe work opportunities. Income and gender inequalities will increase, and in these contexts of tension and survival attempts, conflict among classes or factions very likely arises. Clashes within the community or with the state may concretely threaten peace and security". Starting from this hypothetical reasoning, that is only one of the many possible environmental issues that could exist, I realised the scope and impact of the environment on the life of human beings, not to consider the drastic consequences on the environment itself, also advocated by the SDGs (13, 14, 15). I developed the curiosity of investigating these effects on field, verifying them with the people living them on their skin.

²² SDGs n°: 1, 2, 6, 3, 4, 5, 10, 12, 16 (SDG, 2023).

²³ Dr. Louis Alexandre Berg is Associate Professor of Political Science at Georgia State University. His research examines the effects of foreign aid and international security assistance on peace, security, and human rights. He taught in the academic year 2023/24 the course of *Conflict, Security and Development* at Sciences Po Lille (Dumez, 2024).

In the meanwhile, I was attending the courses to be enabled to volunteer in the European Solidarity Corps (ESC) for Humanitarian Aid, and after completing my education, I applied -and was selected- for a project on environmental conservation and promotion of permaculture in Kenya, where droughts and floods have been a serious problem for decades, proposed by the NGO CIVS Kenya²⁴. Embedded in the general ESC “ECHAV” project (Empower vulnerable Communities through Humanitarian Aid Volunteers)²⁵ -which aims to provide practical support to missions of organisations in non-EU countries to contribute to strengthening local capacity and resilience-, the actions of CIVS Kenya are devoted to empowering local populations with the aim of mitigating flooding and droughts risks, and enhancing environmental resilience and water and food security, in a sustainable and lasting way. In order to achieve these objectives they (and the volunteers) work in close collaboration with the local community, in all their activities: “establishment of tree nurseries and planting of trees in homes, schools and community social places to enhance vegetation cover, reduce soil drought and the risk of flooding; [s]upport community members in the farms to enhance methods of cultivation, irrigation, harvesting and increase productivity; [e]ducational sessions on permaculture and environmental sustainability in schools and other social places” (ESC, 2024).

Under suggestion of my supervisor, given the perfect match with my academic interests, I decided to conduct, parallelly to the volunteering activity, empirical research on field to investigate the curiosity I had.

Provided the background in which the research topic arose, the following lines will deliver some key information about Kenya and Kisumu County in particular, to equip the reader with a conscious idea of the empirical context, before jumping into the articulation of the question, and to prove the relevance of the research pursued in that specific area.

²⁴ CIVS Kenya - Centre for International Voluntary Service - is a Community Development Organization operating in the marginalized and poverty-stricken areas of Kenya to contribute toward the socio-economic and cultural empowerment of disadvantaged communities and fight against poverty and social exclusion. CIVS Kenya runs a wide range of volunteering projects including teaching, childcare, environmental protection, agricultural work, healthcare and supporting people with disabilities (ESC, 2024).

²⁵ IBO Italia coordinates the activity with the sending organisations Grenzenlos (Austria), Visioners (Germany), Keric (Slovakia) and Amigos de Europa (Spain), and with the hosting organisation of CIVS Kenya (ESC YouthPass, 2024). I was selected by Keric, with whom I worked closely.

Kenya, together with other African states, has been since the late 20th century one of the most affected countries by environmental issues, experiencing a number of severe natural hazards, the most common being weather related: floods, droughts, landslides, thunderstorms, wildfires, and strong winds (Andre de la Porte, 2005). The Arid and Semi-arid Lands constitute more than 80% of Kenya's landmass, support nearly half of the livestock population of the country and over 30% of the total human population; because they are prone to harsh weather conditions, they render the communities within these regions vulnerable to natural hazards, mainly droughts and floods (*ibidem*). Furthermore, the situation has worsened in the last decades in correlation to climate change: higher temperatures and changing rainfall patterns result in more frequent and intense extreme weather events, in particular droughts and floods. Ecosystems, water resources, food, health, coastal zones, industrial activity, and human settlements, especially the most poor and marginalised communities, are disastrously impacted (National Environment Management Authority, 2021). Western provinces of Kenya are in particular mostly disrupted by floods, especially along the flood plains in the Lake Victoria Basin. In this region, Nyando district -as *Figure 1.* shows- is one of the most affected territory ever, as the homonym river is likely to overflow in the rain seasons, which are too often unpredictable in time and intensity (Andre de la Porte, 2005).

Figure 1. Map of Kenya by propensity to environmental issues (Andre de la Porte, 2005)

The project where I volunteered was based in Kuth Awendo, village where I had most of my activities and community in which I was mostly immersed into during my stay. Some initiatives were instead carried in the neighbouring village -Ahero-, the principal city of the county -Kisumu-, and the county right on the lake's coast -Homa Bay-, all equally affected by floods more than the rest of the country.

Another extremely relevant aspect of Kenya's environmental profile relates to the legislative governance field: in 2010, the new Constitution obtained after a harsh civil uprising revolutionarily included the right to a healthy environment [art.70] (World Bank, 2019). This event renders it interesting to study whether the establishment of the right "from above" brought any concrete change and eventually how it did so.

Provided the context, it is now possible to understand how the main topic of research generated actually many narrower hints for inquiry: the human right to a healthy environment is foreseen formally by the supreme national law, yet even recent reports acknowledge environmental risks and problems impacting on the territorial population.

The first set of research, reflected in the third chapter of this document, will try to study empirically the impact of the environmental hazards described by data and reports, with the valorisation of the *human* experience of these risks and disasters, asking to the community members about their personal stories and their perceptions. The objective is to start from an empirical source, and then integrate it with further research and academic reasoning, on the understanding of the consequences of an unhealthy environment, with the theoretical relevance (Cardano & Ortalda, 2021) of enriching the literature on the connection between the environment and human beings with a lived dimension of humanity and participated sympathy. The main question of this part will be the *actual* level of enjoyment of the right to a healthy environment by the people of the Nyando district and neighbouring territories, also from a relative perspective compared to the past. When did the environment start to impact particularly negatively on people, how, driven by which reasons? How is the situation at present time, improved, worsened? how? why?

It is also wanted to investigate among the people's perception the root causes of the issues, for the practical relevance of fathoming the starting point for the building of possible solutions and a consequent construction of the right to a healthy environment. This will introduce the core research question, *how the right has been and is being built*, and will articulate in a myriad of narrower questions, as who are the actors of this process,

how do they participate to it, how do they interact with each other, what difficulties do they encounter,... Acknowledged the 2010 Constitution adoption including the HRHE²⁶, did things improve after its establishment or was there any other type of a change? There have been other measures launched “from above”, at international/national/county/local level which brought a change? If yes, what; if no, what hampered their efficacy? About the “below”: how do the actors individuated in the first chapter operate? How do they interact with each other, with institutional bodies, and international entities? How is their impact perceived?

The global study, comprehensive of all its decompositions, has the overall objective of assessing the actual level of realisation of human right to a healthy environment in the Kisumu area of Kenya, and the process of construction, the way each actor contributes to it, with an ethnographic approach of research and sympathetic human participation.

Using Cardano’s terms (2021), it has pragmatic relevance for the sake of improving or continuing the path to accomplish the aimed right in the specific area under analysis, by providing some grounds for evaluating the actions pursued so far. Highlighting the mechanism underlying process of construction of the right can be useful for academic studies on emerging human rights and their suggest paths for their crystallisation in other countries. One critique that could be opposed would be that, exactly for the importance of the locality underlined in the first chapter, any conclusion could not be taken as universal, or applicable directly to other situations. That is true, but does not diminish the significance of the research, as it has not the scope of finding a universal truth or rule, but rather to study qualitatively the mechanisms and processes; these, could *then* eventually result useful for a comparative analysis with countries presenting similar characteristics (e.g.: Tanzania, Mozambique) which might hence borrow with a possibility of success the same strategies, or avoid already made mistakes; it could be useful also to contrast outcomes in very different countries (e.g.: European states), or to inspire preventive action in countries where the environmental threat is not yet as severe as it is in Kenya.

Theoretical relevance, which could still find practical applicability, would regard a deeper understanding of the relationship between “the above” and “the below” in the

²⁶ For the sake of avoiding long written repetitions, we will sometimes abbreviate the “human right to a healthy environment” with the acronym HRHE.

construction of a right, in light (or contrast) of the premises found in the literature: with what degree are respectively contributing; how they interact; influence, boost or obstacle each other.

2.1.2 *Empirical context*

Following Cardano's guidelines on methodology, before outlining the design and techniques used to pursue the research, this section will briefly define the objects of study, and their "eloquence" (2021), that is their ability to contribute properly to answer to question presented in the previous lines.

The scope of work ([trad.] *ibidem*, p.61) is the community of Nyando district in the year 2024, and the unit of analysis are its members, strongly affected since decades by environmental hazards and eventually fighting them. The unit of collection includes the individual members, but also their organisations -when present-, and some textual document or data.

In particular, among the people from which I was able to collect some data -in form of formal interview, informal discourse, observation, textual document- there are: members of the community as farmers, teachers, cooks, youths; local volunteers of CIVS Kenya, members of its staff but also -and mostly- of other local organisations; members of international organisations cooperating with CIVS for the ECHAV project.

The eloquence of the empirical context is provided by the diversity of the subjects considered, by gender, age, role, geography: men and women; adults and youths, grandmothers and children; people only affected by environmental issues and people who also work to combat them; members of local organisations and others of international ones. One shortcoming consists in the lack of figures from the institutional framework: the intention was to interview also members of the county government, and the possibility to reach them has been concrete for a while thanks to a contact, but in the end nothing resulted from that connection. Nevertheless, while further investigation on field would be beneficial, the objects gathered still appear to be able to yield interesting results.

2.1.3 Design and techniques

The method was designed to acquire qualitative data, meaning not aiming at the number of information but rather to their communicative power, and the techniques used to collect them diversified according to the information needed or encountered. Employing the literature on methodology elaborated by Cardano, and his classification related to the agency of the researcher and the type of phenomenon under study (2021, p. 56)²⁷, the following lines will outline which techniques were used and why in the relative cases, as well as their general features for a better understating of the data provided in the *Section 2.2*.

Discursive interviews were the main technique foreseen in the design of the method before departing to the field, because their features enable the wanted deep research, in the perceptions of people and understanding of their actions and thoughts. In fact, they allow to take as much time as needed to investigate directly with the interviewed, and lay the ground for creating a human connection that can make the researcher go more easily deeper into personal stories, emotions, opinions, of the person. The degree of freedom intrinsically entailed consents to explore their responses in multiple directions while in the conversation, navigating in the flow of the information as it is received. Quoting the French sociologist J.C. Kauffman, as Semi does in his book *The participant Observation* [trad.it], “[t]o find the right question, there is no other solution than to listen attentively to what is being said and reflect on it while the informant speaks” (2022, p. 77). However, I also referred strongly to Cardano’s approach, according to whom the research with this technique is rather “guided” than completely free (2022). For this reason, I prepared a draft of the questions I would have asked, for different sectors according to the position of the interviewed, but implemented them while on field, and formulated also new inquiries according to the flow of the communication for each single case. Below, some examples of the samples prepared, to be more widely articulated in the interview.

²⁷ According to the level of agency of the researcher, she can collect “naturalistic data” or “provoked data”, meaning respectively that they were in any case there to be observed, or that if the researcher hadn’t intervened she wouldn’t have obtained the information, e.g. asking a question. The second criterium instead identifies the type of phenomenon under study -that can be: the individual, the social interaction, and the products of the social action or interaction-, and the relative technique that is more appropriate to employ (*ibidem*, pp.54-55).

TO INDIVIDUALS

- *A few words about you and what you do for a living.*
- *I read that your constitution foresees the RHE; do you feel you actually enjoy it?*
- *Which ones do you think are the main environmental issues of Kenya, or at least this area?*
- *Have you seen any changes over the years?*
- *How was, or is, the life of the people affected?*
- *Is there any positive response by the national/local gov?*
- *Did you see any change after the Constitution was adopted in 2010?*
- *Who is doing something useful? Eventually how?*
- *How important do you perceive local organisations and volunteers?*

ABOUT ORGANISATIONS

- *What does your project consist of?*
- *What are the results that you have reached?*
- *Who had the idea of the project? Who designs what to do?*
- *How do you engage with the community? / How do you engage with the government?*
- *How do you check activities and monitor that results are maintained after collaborations?*
- *Are you funded by anyone? How do you finance your activities?*

Here instead, some examples of the questions integrated on field:

- *The volunteers told us about the problem with droughts and floods, saying they're strictly connected to deforestation: when did this process happen and what is the cause?*
- *Where do you get the seeds?*
- *I saw the journal/tv shared your work, how many people does it reach?*
- *Which do you think it is the problem with the governmental policy inefficiency?*
- *What do you feel you would need to be able to say you actually enjoy the right to a HE?*

Some questions were thought to be introductory and to make the person feel comfortable, some to give an historical context of the environmental issues and compare the perceptions of their severity over time and by person, then to the evaluation of the actual enjoyment of the HRHE, and then to the perceptions and construction of the action to build it by institutions and civil society.

No interview was programmed before departure: every opportunity developed on field entailing initiative of mine and help by local people from the project. I was open to in person conversation, but also remote ones if no time or possibility to meet was there. A fundamental instrument I used during and immediately after interviews are *field notes* [trad.it. “note di campo”], where I annotated the most important information or particular quotations I heard or remembered schematically and by topic. This practice is strongly suggested by Giovanni Semi -renewed Italian ethnographer-, according to whom the experience lived on field needs to be put on paper as soon as possible, in order to prevent our brain from -even unconsciously- reflecting on the information acquired and elaborating it subjectively, spoiling it with the researcher’s interpretation. To do so, I brought with me a clean notebook and a pencil, and had the “notes” app on my phone ready to use.

A second technique employed is the *participant observation*, because thanks to the volunteering project it was foreseen to live and work with the community, giving me the possibility to continue my research also out of formal context by interacting with local people on a daily basis and in common everyday activities. The immersion in the culture of the population studied allows, besides a sociological analysis, also an ethnographic research, providing the human and cultural context to the issues investigated and to the responses obtained. Field notes will be the main instrument to write down the observations and the results of those informal interactions.

While participant observations is *per se* defined by a degree of perturbation of the datum observed by the researcher, *naturalistic observation* (Cardano & Gariglio, 2022) is instead a technique where no intervention is ever contemplated. The researcher is completely external to the situation witnessed, and it is not known about her specific attention to the object. According to Semi, ethnographic notes shall be first of all descriptive, and as a consequence, not only be written with this kind of language, but also be integrated with graphic and visual material (2022). For this reason, the phone was used not only to take notes of what observed, but also to take photos of it.

A last technique is the analysis of real or digital documents, be them *solicited* or *natural*, according to the level of agency of the researcher (Cardano & Ortalda, 2021).

The method outlined does not involve costs or particular limits of accessibility to the people to be interviewed, hence presents full realisability; furthermore, it is thought to enter in deep connection with people and ask lived stories and perceptions, there is no need for deception, nor does it encourage to get sensitive information without consent: it is based on consensual interviews and observation of situations under the light of the sun. Its realisability and ethical admissibility qualify the method with *pragmatic adequacy*. Since it appears able to provide acceptable answers to the general inquiry it also *epistemic adequacy* (Cardano & Ortalda, 2021).

2.2 Data collection

2.2.1 Interviews

Table 1. Table of all the subjects interviewed in the period September 2024 - March 2025.

Name	Age	Gender	Role/Profession	Context
Mr. Ogando & Mr. Bitter	40-50	Males	Farmers, colleagues	24 th Sep 2024, Nyando
Samuel & Elisabeth	30-40	Male & Female	Farmers, husband & wife	25 th Sep 2024, Katolo
Nancie	25-30	Female	Staff CIVS	28 th Sep 2024, Badilisha
Brian	26	Male	Staff CBO	30 th Sep 2024, Kuth Awendo
Mr. Dilman	32	Male	Staff CIVS, coordinator of the volunteers group	1 st Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo
Mr. David	30-40	Male	Teacher	2 nd Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo
Nam	25-30	Male	Staff CIVS, CBO	3 rd Oct 2024, Ahero
Mr. Paul	40-50	Male	Agribusiness expert	3 rd Oct 2024, Ahero
Ms. Valery, Ms. Karen, Ms. Iphrys, Ms. Christina	30-50	Females	Teachers at Kuth Awendo Resource Centre school	3 rd Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo
Mr. Moses	35-40	Male	Farmer, permaculture expert, Red Cross.	4 th Oct 2024, Ahero
Mr. Isaac	45-50	Male	Staff The Green World	3 rd Jan 2025, online
Aurora	30-35	Female	Staff IBO Italia	10 th Jan 2025, online
Ms. Quinter	40-45	Female	Kisumu County government staff	12 th Feb 2025, online
Mr. James	45-50	Male	Permanent Mission of the Republic of Kenya to the UN and other IOs in Geneva, minister	10 th Mar, Geneva
Mr. Reuben	30-35	Male	Climate finance expert	26 th March, Geneva

The present subchapter will display all the data collected, divided by the technique used to obtain them, and will tell the story around each reception of the information: why this method, why that person, eloquence, accessibility, difficulties encountered, etc.

The first set of data, listed in *Table 1.*, was acquired by discursive interviews, which were all programmed on field. I started by asking to interview the experts on permaculture and farmers that we were meant to meet according to the schedule of our volunteering programme to get trained on the matter and to practically do fieldwork at their farms. So, after work, often while my colleagues were enjoying time after the meal or snack kindly offered by the hosts to greet us for the help (sincere gratitude and warm hospitality are intrinsic in the Kenyan culture, sometimes even in a disproportionate measure), I was able to sit somewhere apart and speak to my informers. It is the case of Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter, Samuel and Elisabeth, and teacher David.

Figure 2. Interview with Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter at their farm in Nyando, 24th September 2024

Especially at the beginning I had some embarrassment in demanding for my purpose, afraid of bothering or being intrusive; instead, I have always encountered great enthusiasm on the other side: I understood people are willing to have their voices heard, as much as possible, about their issues and their efforts.

Overcome the initial timidity, I was able to engage with the CIVS staff members: Nancie was met in a visit trip to another office of CIVS Kenya in the neighbouring region

of Homabay, in Badilisha, where we were shown how they do tree nurseries and their watering system, and comparing with improvement aims to the methods employed in Kuth Awendo. Brian is a volunteer and ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) teacher in CIVS, but also runs an own initiative of development project on territory with his NGO Nyando Community Based Organization (CBO); he is highly schooled, graduated in Mechanical Engineering and with diplomas in Business, ICT and agriculture techniques. Nam volunteers in CIVS in the close village of Ahero and in Brian's organisation; he's studying as a nurse. Mr. Dilman is instead the coordinator of the volunteer groups, both local and international, and the vice-director of the whole organisation, and hence participates to the design and coordination of all the projects. Working with them daily and becoming very soon not colleagues but friends, I was able to allocate some of the free time in the workcamp to speak to them in my researcher clothes. In Kuth Awendo Resource Centre there is also a pre-school funded by the organisation and charging nothing to the families, and I was able to interview the four teachers working there, with whom -by seeing and kindly greeting each other every day- I developed soon a friendly human connection.

The local members of CIVS staff themselves were enthusiastic to help me, and were fundamental to access almost all subjects in the list. First, they introduced me to the people we visited for the CIVS activities in farms and intermediated to get time and space for an interview; that is the case of Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter, and Samuel and Elisabeth, of whom I spoke above. In addition, they even worried about what I could need more and committed to reach new subjects for me. They fixed appointments for me and suspended me from the volunteering activity if necessary to meet the person, providing themselves for the transfer to the place; it is the case of Mr. Paul and Mr. Moses.

The means I used to collect the material was mainly my phone, to both record and take notes during and after the interview. I made this choice for multiple reasons: for practicality, as the recordings and notes would have been directly uploaded in the cloud shared with my computer, and because of being "less invasive" (Semi & Bolzoni, 2022) as an instrument, guaranteeing a more informal environment that would have hopefully created a more personal and trustful connection that encouraged people to freely express their stories, thoughts, feelings.

Some interviews were directly done online, because of time or geographical limits. I did not have the time to interview Mr. Isaac from the ONG The Green World while I was in Kenya, so we caught up online when he was back in Italy. Aurora, volunteers coordinator of the sending organisation IBO Italia was working from Ferrara, so I asked her for an online meeting. Ms. Quinter, working in Kisumu County Office, was also interviewed online. I was able to get her contact by a delegate of the Kenyan mission (Mr. Brian), met at UNCTAD meetings during my internship at the Italian Permanent Mission at the UN and other IOs in Geneva. He was really kind to me and always open to help. The two of them also tried to put me in contact with the head of the Kisumu office (Mr. Hongo), providing me the email address and even his personal phone number; nevertheless, I never received an answer by him. Another person I met thanks to Mr. Brian was Mr. James: one Friday evening he had invited me to a pub for a drink together after work, and there I had the pleasure to meet almost the whole Kenyan delegation to the UN. Besides being really fun, and feeling for a while back in Kenya by sharing their typical dancing energy together, I also exchanged contacts with Mr. James Kiiru, Minister and Head of Chancery at the Permanent Mission of Kenya to the UN, whom I met again a couple of times while working at WTO (World Trade Organisation) during my internship. In that occasion I asked him for an interview, and he agreed enthusiastically. Nevertheless, actually reaching him was less easy, agreeing to meet one day and then receiving no updates, or with delayed answers; however, a last-minute arrangement online in March allowed me to interview him. That was precious because thanks to his experience in both the IOs (especially WTO) and the African Union, he was able to give me valuable comparisons between the international and regional levels of actions impacting on the country. Thanks to my internship in Geneva, I was also able to meet Mr. Reuben Wambui, a climate finance expert who has worked as a consultant for UNCTAD, UNEP, World Bank, World Economic Forum, the Central bank of Kenya and that of African States, and many other institutions and banks specialised in climate action. It was particularly precious to be able to speak to him, as he gave me a new perspective on IOs and introduced me the unneglectable role that the private sector currently holds in the build of the right to a healthy environment, promoting and financing important initiatives in the matter. He was also extremely easy to reach: provided the contact by a colleague of mine, he immediately answered to my message and welcomed my proposal, promptly letting me fix an appointment on his agenda.

During the whole process of data collection, some difficulties inevitably arose. The first regards the concern for the sound quality in the recording: not only most of the interviews took place in open spaces, hence with noises in background, but also and most importantly, culturally, Kenyan people are used to speaking with a very low voice, which I was therefore afraid wouldn't have been clearly recorded. A couple of particular cases verified with Mr. Paul, where a kid was playing in the room where we were talking and making strong noises with chairs and laughs, and with Mr. Moses (*Figure 3.*), whom I reached on his field that is situated just next to one main and trafficked road.

I tried to overcome the issue by repeating myself the most relevant information, in order to be sure to have them recorded, and by straightaway taking notes after each interview of what had been said. The accent is also peculiar, and I needed some days after my arrival before being able to always get everything immediately and correctly: during the first days, it happened that sometimes I asked to repeat specific words.

Figure 3. Mr. Moses, interview at his field in Ahero, 4th October 2024.

A second difficulty regarded the practical means to reach the people supposed to be interviewed: in some cases, as anticipated, my colleagues in CIVS provided for my transfer, and that in Kisumu most frequently happens by *piki piki*, that is motorcycle in Kiswahili. Here the first difficulty was of personal character, as I had always been afraid of motorcycles and had never been on one, and the second of practical nature, since one of the two times we had a flat tyre and had to lose one hour at a mechanic's before reaching the place. Another impediment to reach subjects with programmed interviews

was time constraints: once I did not have the time to interview the expert after the visit to his farm as programmed (Mr. John from Victoria Fresh), and another time I met a person during an activity and agreed to fix an appointment but not able to concretise that intention in the end (Mr. Isaac from The Green World). To cope with these inconvenient, we exchanged our phone numbers to schedule an online meeting once I was home; the strategy succeeded for Mr. Isaac but not for Mr. John, whom I was not able to reach again.

An additional difficulty were accessibility issues: some subjects would have been interesting to collect data from, but getting in touch with them was in the end not possible. It was proposed by Mr. Moses to contact on behalf of me an important woman of his village, to have another female's experience and point of view, but that turn into nothing. Another idea was to make me talk with an ancient woman of the village who was though illiterate and needed a translator between us from the tribal language of the Luo and vice-versa, and that resulted too difficult to organise. Mr. Dilman knew an officer from the Kisumu County office, Keere, who wanted to make me meet, but despite calling him and leaving messages, he never got an answer.

As a result, the way I qualified my choice of the people to be interviewed was widely directed by a matter of reachability: it was not really possible to *choose*, but I simply collected material everywhere I could and left the possibility to eventually cut off later what not useful. If a concrete opportunity to choose was not there, yet there was the intention, by which I for example gave indication to my colleagues in CIVS to direct me to people: I wanted to speak to "common" villagers; to get their perceptions and stories, to NGOs staff, to get why and how they conduct their work; local volunteers, to understand their choice; institutional figures, to get insight on official measures implemented and the perspective of someone working at that level, also to later confront that with the population's perceptions. Even with some difficulties, I was in the end able to get some data by each of the figures desired, and to guarantee a decent eloquence of the data collected for the research. The study includes contrasting categories that could offer multiple perspectives: both people "witnessing" the construction (or not) of right to a healthy environment and people working to that process, and in this latter category, both from below and above; staff from both local and international organisations; men and women; youth and adults.

2.2.2 Participant and naturalistic observation

The data collected through interviews were profoundly integrated by material collected by observation, taking advantage of the fact of having been living there for a couple of months and amidst the community of the village.

In the table below are listed the people from whom I was able to collect interesting information by participant or naturalistic observation.

Table 2. Subjects whom interaction with yielded interesting information in the period September 2024 - October 2024.

Name	Age	Gender	Role/Profession	Context
Rhoda	22	Female	Volunteer at CIVS	Sep-Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo
Linnet	24	Female	Volunteer at CIVS	Sep-Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo
Brian	23	Male	Volunteer at CIVS	Sep-Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo
Mr. Dick	40-45	Male	Teacher	27 th Sep 2024, Rabuor school
Mr. John & Meggie	40-45 20-25	Male Female	Farmers, and Staff of Victoria Fresh	27 th Sep 2024, Nyando
Child asking for water	6-8	Male	Student	2 nd Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo local school
Alani	21	Female	Permaculture expert, volunteer for CIVS	3 rd Oct 2024, Kuth Awendo Resource Centre
Winnie, Angela, Stephanie	30-50	Females	Cookers at the Kuth Awendo Resource Centre	Every day (Sep-Oct 2024), Kuth Awendo Resource Centre
Catherine	50-60	Female	Host of volunteers	October 2024, Nairobi,
Javier	25-30	Male	Staff Okolea Mtaa Foundation	11 th Oct 2024, Nairobi

I will start this section by telling about the standard day of a volunteer for the ECHAV project at CIVS Kenya, to allow the reader to immerse herself in the community culture and ways of living as I did, hence through my eyes better understand the context of the data collected, with specific reference to the list in the table.

Figure 4. The volunteers team in the model farm of Kuth Awendo Resource Centre, 7th October 2024

As anticipated, the project is devoted to empowering local populations with the aim of mitigating flooding and droughts risks, and enhancing environmental resilience and water and food security, in a sustainable and lasting way. This is translated in practice in a series of different activities, to which the volunteers participated actively. First, they are carrying out a model farm, involving work on three pieces of land, among which we worked mainly on the largest one (19,222 m²) (Alani's Masterplan, 2024) almost each morning by planting tomatoes, corns and pumpkins, planting fruit trees, digging new raised beds (my principal activity), weeding, grass cutting, watering plants, and propagating stevia. The local volunteers (seven) were used to that kind of work, so taught us European volunteers the best techniques; that, together with the singing and dancing that we used to do during the working hours to alleviate the effort and heat (September is very hot in Kenya; in fact, we could only work until midday) created since the first days a solid bond of friendship among all us volunteers.

Being friends, it became common to talk on routes or after work and tell personal stories or experiences to each other, some of which were also useful to picture ethnographically the framework of my research. From Rhoda for example, I learnt about the schooling system and the difficulties to get a high-level education; from Linet I learnt the reasons pushing a young and schooled girl (she is a nutritionist) to volunteer in this kind of project; from Brian, whom I also interviewed more formally to get to know about his organisation, I learnt about the environmental story of the area: that was in occasion of the preparation work of a brochure we had to deliver in schools to raise environmental awareness among the young students, inform about the main problematics of Kisumu territory and promote correct agricultural techniques and green behaviours in everyday life. Some information about those topics came also by the experts coming to train us in the first days on agricultural and environmental matters (Mr. Dick), other from the experts and NGO staff members we met at the farms where we worked (Mr. John and Meggie). In the latter especially, I was able, not only by talking and doing, but also by observing, to grasp how concretely different small local NGOs work on field, what they do, their organisation, their values. The photo below (*Figure 5.*) shows the values exposed at the Victoria Fresh NGO, whose slogan is “Treedom”; I noticed that every local organisation and every school have the custom to have their main values painted on the internal or external wall of one of their buildings, and that who works there tends to remark them with pride.

Figure 5. Wall of the Victoria Fresh NGO (left) and wall of the St. Christopher School (right).

After working in the fields or visiting farms we returned to the resource centre in Kuth Awendo, where we lived, and had some time for everyday housework and scrub up. We had a shower, in a fortune bathroom/toilet built in the garden (*Figure 6.*) did laundry, and Rhoda taught me the best techniques to brush my clothes; we cleaned the room and corridor with a brushwood; helped the cooks to prepare the dinner and played with the kids belonging to the staff's family in the breaks or after school (which was in the resource centre, built by CIVS Kenya for families who couldn't afford the classic school, which always has fees).

Figure 6. In order from left to right, first row: laundry; room; bathroom/toilet. Second row: cooking; cooks; kids at resource centre.

This way we became friends, I heard the cooks' stories, learnt about Kenyan traditional recipes and how to prepare them, laughed together when I was not good at it. I learnt how women are used to becoming moms in very young age and keep having

children until older (one of our colleague volunteers was the daughter to a cook and at the same time mom and sister to the kids always around); how they are used to the housework and care of the family's affairs. Other thing: it was unbelievable for them that we don't own nor cultivate any field in my family in Italy, and were surprised (I guessed by their voice tone also someway a bit envious) that I had a cooker at home, and even a laundry machine and a dishwasher. I also got really close and affectionate to the kids, played their games and took care of them, noticing often some details. For example, when Natasha had her face dirty of snot, she was not used to clean it, and when I brought her to the small water provider we had for washing hands, washing her face resulted a game, not like something she was used to (she usually rather licked her hand to wash dirt over her face): that was eloquent to me about the lack of water and scares hygiene conditions family have to face. The toilets were also something definitely usual for a European, and many of my colleagues had difficulties in adapting, but for everybody else there was not strange not to have hot water for the shower and to have the toilet being a hole in the fortune building.

Schools are another place where I was able to observe the Kenyan culture, by interacting with teachers and students and engaging with them in tree planting activities. The volunteering programme foresaw that we went in eleven schools to distribute the brochures we had created and plant a number of trees. What I was surprised to discover is that we -the volunteers- were supposed to teach the kids how to do it, but they were all already able to perfectly and smoothly dig and cover the seedlings: this made me understand that they were used to doing agricultural labour in their households since young age, hence remarking the role that farming has for the village families (intuition that will be confirmed by interviews). Another thing I noticed in schools is the width of the inequality gap between the wealthy and the poor families: it is evident in the differences noticed between high-fees schools, low-fees schools, and schools built by NGOs, in their buildings, the quality of the uniforms, in having the lunch included or not, in the composition of the classes, and in the behaviour of the children. I will analyse further this topic in *Chapter 3*, but start sharing some photos below (*Figure 7*).

Figure 7. From left to right: High-fees school; NGO built x; low-fees school.

The enthusiasm of kids in meeting us and their curious behaviour was another stunning observation: they were constantly touching us, trying to reach our hands (it was impossible to hold all of them, so they went for arms too), caressing our hair, doing compliments (especially on the softness of my hands and of my hair) and willing to take photos with the “mzungu” (that is “white” in Kiswahili). I understood they were fascinated by the fact of meeting white people, and the most surprising thing is that nothing was different with adults (except for the touchy tendency). The teachers too, as well as people met casually while walking in the village sometimes, asked us to take photos with them on their phones; all the kids waving to us all the time; people in the streets pointed their finger or called us “mzungu”. While with the kids can be nice and funny, after a while and especially with adults it started to be weird and causing particular discomfort. The local colleagues explained us that it is rare to see white people around, reason why it appears special, but that meeting some is also source of pride and virtue, probably (and I am keeping to only report what said) because the white man is seen with having the money, being rich and privileged. Privileged is actually how I felt when seeing some situations, and I cannot hide that it often was not easy.

That was actually one of the main difficulties of this method of collecting information (beyond of the whole experience in general): listening to real and harsh difficulties of people you don’t know is already hard, but when it comes from people you have become friends with and when you interact directly in the everyday life is harder.

Even worse, has been *witnessing* in person such cruel scenarios, which is harder especially when it's kids to be protagonists of them (see for example *Section 3.2.1.*).

A less relevant difficulty was instead, when people told me something, to not make them understand that my questions were driven also by an academic interest besides personal. Alongside this, hiding eventually attempts of recording (as happened with Rhoda), as I didn't want to hurt the person's feelings or make friends feel as an "object of study". Field notes were my best instruments in the situations where some information came after participant or naturalistic observation, taking notes of both what witnessed or experienced, but also of following considerations and feelings.

2.2.3 Documents

The last technique used to collect data was the analysis of real or digital data. The material I collected includes: a paper given to us volunteers by the Victoria Fresh NGO about their past and current work, results and objectives; the brochure we created to raise awareness in schools; the numerical data about the results of the work we had carried out at the end of the ECHAV project and work camp, which I report in the tables below. They see a total of 3,362 trees planted and 6,038 students reached.

Table 3. Results of the on-field work over the community territory.

Numerical result	Place
550 tree seedlings implantation	Distributed among the 11 schools
180 seedlings (gravelia, orange)	Kuth Awendo model farm
100 seedlings	Katolo model farm
42 stem seeds	Rabuor Victoria Fresh demo farm
4 seed beds of Markhamia, resulting in 1,992 seedlings sprout	Kuth Awendo model farm

Table 4. Number of students reached, distributing the brochures and tree planting in their schools.

Number of students reached	School
452	St Camulus Secondary School
398	Kuth Awendo Primary School
286	Nyakongo Primary School
200	Nyando Technical Training Institute
386	Oren Secondary School
183	Young Achievers
103	Bristol Academy
791	Rabuor Primary School
735	Rongo Primary School
1,762	Rae Girls High School
742	Kolunga Primary School

2.1

2.3 Data analysis

2.3.1 Qualification of the empirical material collected

Once collected, the data was to be organised and sorted in order to prepare its examination. First, I gathered all the information dividing it into folders according to the categories presented in *Section 2.2*, selected the photos that could be useful to transmit my experience, assembled all my field notes and uploaded the interviews recordings on my computer. To prepare it for the analysis, I decided to qualify the empirical material (Cardano & Ortalda, 2021) according to the three macro-areas that I wanted to investigate: the actual level of enjoyment of a healthy environment, hence people's experiences and comparisons with the past; the role of the government and institutional bodies in building the right; the role of the civil society and the relation among its actors. Within these wide categories, I tried to find patterns and common issues, to better contrast information on the same topic and to later address each issue with specific attention.

In order to do so, I first had to put on paper and in an organised way all information collected from people by means of oral interaction, both interview and informal interactions, and consequent recording. I encountered the first difficulty with regard to the transcriptions in finding a software that was able to catch adequately the discourses, given the frequent disturbances in the background, overlapping of voices, and strong accent. By advice of a colleague at the Italian Mission, I was able to find one specialised in the English language and that also distinguished the speakers: *TurboScribe*. While not always precise when the speakers were many, it delivered a sufficient quality of transcripts that, besides being required for transparency and accountability of the sources for the research, also facilitated my work on the interviews. I listened to each interview, taking notes on the main topics touched and of the content yielded on that, and eventually quoted relevant phrases. In this latter activity the software revealed useful as had been able to understand some words that I could not catch or that I didn't know (eg. manioc, gabions, to cater). The process took quite long time, as the interviews had an average duration of an hour, and it took me almost double that time for each in order to listen carefully and sort the information.

After having produced per person categorisation documents (*Figure 8a.*), I created thematic files (*Figure 8b.*), where I individuated for each of the three macro-areas anticipated above, all the sub-topics related to it encountered across all the data collected.

INTERVIEWS	3. ENVIRONMENT AND HUMANS, mutual impact
<p>INTERVIEW 1 - Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitta</p> <p>JOB DIVERSIFICATION → to have an alternative source of money in case of drought. CHANGE IN RAINS → started in the '90s, now is better, also tx to change in mindset CHANGE IN AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES → shift away from charcoal MINDSET AND AWARENESS: WHO HAS A ROLE → gov, local NGO. Not everybody is WATER PROBLEM → main env problem; insufficient n° of ponds CHANGE IN DROUGHTS → no pattern of rain cycles since 2015, due to CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACT OF DROUGHTS → economic impact: prod down, no harvest, no sell, no money, inflat SOLUTIONS → farming diversification FORMS OF HELP: private financial cooperatives (SACCO) + GOV, but corruption HRHE → "comes from people's initiative"</p> <p>INTERVIEW 2 - Samuel and Elisabeth</p> <p>WATER PROBLEM IMPACT OF DROUGHT (4/5months) → fish die, crops die → poverty IMPACT OF FLOODS → destroys everything: fields, poultries, houses → but "move where?" FORMS OF HELP → almost none; during emergency GOV and RED CROSS, only NGO sth. HRHE → most people are not enjoying, only few. The main obstacle is politics.</p>	<p>CHANGE IN RAINS → '90s with DEFORESTATION, demogr increase + 2015 CLIM CH. ENV HISTORY → adverse weather disasters, 2019 el nino, 2023 decemeber, 2024 april AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES and METHODS → synthetic are bad; change; permaculture. INTERNATIONAL CORPORATION ACTIVITIES → resource exploitation; coca cola case PLASTICS AND WASTE, POLLUTION → air, soil, water → diseases, soil less prod, poverty IMPACT OF DROUGHTS → no harvest, animals die → POVERTY, econ impact. Soil erosion IMPACT OF FLOODS → displacement, death, diseases → no school, no work, roads muddy WATER PROBLEM → biggest issue, would solve all others; IMPACTS OF A FAR STREAM SOLUTIONS → dams, filter lake water, gabions borehole, tree planting to restore rain cycles. CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION STRATEGIES → greenhouses, cassava, new crop varieties IMPACT ON EDUCATION → school not continuous, displacement in floods, heat, fees, dropouts POVERTY → most severe consequence: food security, additional jobs, child labor, no school... CONFLICT and VIOLENCE → in household, among neighbors, in the country (revolts) GENDER INEQUALITY, WOMEN → hold most of household burden and responsibility, violence EMOTIONS and MENTAL HEALTH → frustrating; depression, anxiety, suicide, DRUGS. HRHE → "still building" on avergae judgement</p>

Figure 8. Extract of a page of the categorisations by person (9a, left), v. extracts of a page of the categorisations by theme (9b, right).

2.3.2 Individuation of relations among categorised elements

Once the material had all been gathered, ordered, and classified, relations among various the categories started to emerge, and this is the very first step of my analysis. The ‘zero’ kind of relation was the thematic one, as related to the three macro-areas of study; within this context, logical connections internal to each section stemmed out.

The first macro-area, as anticipated, regards the mutual impact that humans and environment have on each other, and has the objective to lead to an evaluation of the actual realisation of the HRHE in the geographical area under analysis. It was here possible to distinguish all the human actions and behaviours that have negative effects on the environment, and the impacts of an unhealthy environment on its population. Also, a positive narrative of their mutual relationship was individuated. Another kind of connection is of chronological and cause-effect type, seeing an environmentally unfriendly behaviour conducting as a consequence in the long-time to adverse climate and weather conditions. It is true also vice versa that improvements in such human behaviour lead to a slow reparation of the environment.

In the second macro-area, the relation was rather among a series of levels to be intended vertically: international, regional, national and local legal framework can be clearly distinguished and also collaborate between them.

A similar distinction can be made as far as the organisations in the civil society are concerned -international, national, local (e.g. respectively: EU, Red Cross Kenya, CIVS Kenya)-, but also a distinction of subjects by numbers, that is to say groups of people (NGOS, CBOs, social movements) and individuals (volunteers, common citizen, donors). Again, the relationship among all this actors can be further investigated.

More interestingly, can be examined the relationship between the three sections’ actors: how builders of HRHE “from above” and “from below” interact with each other, how they or their actions are perceived by the population, how they impact on it and the environment. Cross-sectional relationship among categories do exist, as drought-poverty, environmental adverse conditions-gender inequality, water scarcity-school dropouts.

The resulting whole collection of the empirical data, and the emerging relationships among them, will be communicated in the incoming three chapters, following the tripartite structure outlined in the previous lines, incorporating critical analysis and reasoning trying to find exhaustive answers to the research question and to qualify the process of HRHE building in Kenya.

2.3.3 *Communication of results: making people's voices heard*

Before jumping into the communication of the results, I care about making a point on the way it will be delivered, as I reckon it is fundamental to understand how to approach (and eventually appreciate) the reading. The voices of the people will be the common thread to the whole discussion. The scope of the research is, in fact, to study the building of HRHE with a human-centred perspective: the *people* are the actors of the process, those who substantially operate it, who suffer from the issues. Social reality is not only rational and numbers, but also and especially *sweat* and *blood*. The aim is not to discover absolute truths, or to find every possible factor contributing to the process, but to make the *people's voices* heard, to analyse their personal experiences, to speak out their stories, suffering, efforts; actions, hopes; their lived and their perceived. After all, what more realistic than first-person narratives to assess the realisation of a *human* right?

CHAPTER III

Environment and Humans: mutual impacts

The following chapter will address the mutual impact that humans and environment have on each other.

When trying to assess the actual enjoyment of the HRHE by the people, the description of a certain current situation emerged, but also the changes through which it has undergone, what brought to it, and how it is already changing again. Therefore, and as anticipated in the previous pages, it was possible, after having collected and categorised the whole empirical data, to find a logical and chronological order among the information: how the relationship with the territory was long-time ago; how it started changing in the '90s and due to which factors; how climate change started manifesting, especially since 2015. It was possible to notice how the stories about this topic were all coinciding, hence it appeared reliable to reconstruct an environmental history of the area, which will also be confronted to official documents (Kenya State, World Bank, UNDP) to compare and contrast scientific analyses and the people's perceptions collected in the field. The consequences suffered by the households along these changes in the environment's health were the topic emerged the most when interviewing people from the community and farmers, often accompanied by large emotional engagement, especially melancholy, resignation, and spirit of resilience. Lots of hope and commitment to reverse the situation, however, stemmed out from the conversations with farmers and local NGO staff members, expressing with pride all the policies, strategies, and paths enacted to work towards a safest environment and more secured life in the community.

It was also possible to distinguish a cause-effect relationship between humans and the environment, and to qualify it as negative or positive: first, human action contributed to provoke damages to the territory; then, it is nature to reverse the consequences of her new unhealthy status on its inhabitants; ultimately, the community starts to try a reversion the curve, engaging in individual behaviours that can have a neutral or positive effect on the environment, in order for this to in turn stop harming the population. The chapter will hence be articulated, along the chronological journey, in two sections reflecting these relationships.

3.1 The negative impact of humans on the environment

3.1.1 Deforestation

“Long ago it was bushy. We had a number of trees; the place was cool. But due to the increase in population, people had to do a lot of deforestation because they had to construct new houses.

I thought deforestation was more driven by external actors, instead... it was the people?

No, it is the people, it is internal. They didn't know the effect it would've had.

And when did this process of deforestation start?

When they started it's around 30 years from now. Yeah, 30 years (long pause), and it's still ongoing.”

(Brian, 27yo, CIVS volunteer and CBO staff)

One of the main problems encountered by people, emerging unanimously, is the alteration of the rain cycle, and the root of this change is placed in the '90s, when a human-driven process of deforestation started. A sudden demographic increase in the '80s implied need for new houses, and hence land, which was to be obtained by cutting trees.

“In the 80s, there was scattered population in our country. But from 90s, population started growing. So, you find community members, especially in rural areas, looking for places of settlement.”

(Mr. Isaac, 45-50yo, The Green World staff)

“If you just come and ask, you ask one person ‘how many kids do you have?’: somebody has nine. Averagely we are having kids from six in a family. So, if for example they are men, all of them have to be constructed houses within the land. Then they also have to give to their own kids. So, you see the circle? Each six men growing up will also have their six children, who will have to construct their house. And if the land is not available, they have to cut [trees].”

(Brian, 27yo, CIVS volunteer and CBO staff)

According to the *Kenya State of Environment Report 2019-2021*, the average forest cover in the '90s reached the worrying datum of only 5% of the total Kenyan territory, in the context of a 10% constitutional target threshold, and ranging across counties from a value of 0.42% to 38% (National Environment Management Authority, 2021). Between 1982 and 2006, 46% of Kenyan forest land degraded, and in particular, the Kakamega Forest -mostly located in Kisumu County- has lost between 1989 and 2001 approximately 21km², which represents a loss of 21% of the forest (Mitchell, 2004). Demographic increase can be addressed as one indirect cause of this period deforestation, as it is the root of other factors which instead directly drove to cut trees. The first is, as explained in the previous lines, tree felling by hand of the very same community, in order to create place for settlement, but according to what emerged during interviews from popular experience, also by institutional initiatives of political bodies: the President of the time, Daniel Arap Moi (in charge from 1978 to 2002), was apparently leveraging the household's need for such space to increase his political support by granting them land.

“So, we realized that some of the environmental challenges that we are facing is because some years back, the past administrations wanted to get votes from the people, they wanted to be supported politically. And the price for that was to give land, to distribute forest lands to people, so they started deforestating.

How long back?

From the administration of Moi, especially. Moi was the dictator president.

In the 80s?

In the 90s. Yes, 90s. So a lot of forest land was taken away”.

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

A second factor is economic: the larger the family, the more the resources needed to sustain it. For this reason, more land would also be required for harvesting, for both nourishing the household's members and producing goods to sell on the market. This will imply cutting more trees. As my local volunteer mate Rhoda (female, 21yo) once told me, “poverty is a thing in Kenya” and “people will always prioritise having place for the fields and business-oriented activities to safeguarding environment's health” (field notes, 24th October 2024, while walking towards a school).

As reported by the National Environment Management Authority (2021), poverty is one crucial vector of deforestation, insofar it leads households to an inappropriate use of wood as source for cooking, heating, housing and crafts: approximately 70% of Kenyan households burn biomasses for these activities. In this context, charcoal production is one of the most relevant sources of income, but also unsustainable and “a major driver of deforestation” (World Bank, 2019, Table 13).

“Two, you find the economic hardship. So, most of these community members are resolving for the business of selling charcoal. So, they cut these trees and change them into the charcoal and sell.”

(Mr. Isaac, 45-50yo, The Green World staff)

The resulting effect on the environment is devastating and detrimental: forests constitute the foundation of trophic niches and natural food chains; thus, their harm is directly translated in severe losses in biodiversity and reduction in ecosystem conservation (National Environment Management Authority, 2021).

The most severe concern following deforestation, however, consists in a major disruption of environment natural equilibria which brings with it a series of devastating and almost irreversible consequences: the alteration of the water cycle. Trees are, in fact, the main contributors to it, and their eradication means the reduction of the evapotranspiration process in the atmosphere, with lesser vapor to condensate into rain and less water getting back to the soil, seas or streams -which will eventually dry.

Figure 9. Effect of deforestation on rainfall in the tropics. Source:(Aragão, 2012)

That water is vital for any form of life on Earth, be it human, animal, or vegetal. The green will not survive, creating a general condition of drought, which also implies land degradation and soil erosion, and impoverishing it of its nutrients and fertility, with negative consequences on food insecurity for all the planet's inhabitants (*Figure 10*).

Figure 10. Starvation caused by drought in Kenya has caused this cow's body to deteriorate. Source: UN News, 2024; in turn from UNEP, Nayim Ahmed Yussuf

“So the issues of soil erosion is there, I told you that land is bad. When it is drought it's totally drought. Everything is cleared. (*long pause*) Then, when now it is raining, it is flooding. And flooding means lots of erosion because of the landscape too. When rain comes from the hills the water floods everything.

It also takes some trees away... everything?

Yeah, / because the big trees were cut down. Now, the remaining things are small things that are not able to keep the floor where it is. / (*sad tone*)”.

(Brian, 27yo, CIVS volunteer and CBO staff)

The droughts and the consequent soil erosion are major drivers of the occurrence of dangerous floods, as trees are no longer there to ensure the land stability in face of water falling on it, and instead eventually sweeps away, destroying and dragging violently with it whatever it finds on its path.

Another direct consequence of deforestation is climatic alteration, as it implies an extension of the area of bare soil: this has a higher albedo²⁸ -reflecting power-, and is hence less able to absorb solar radiations, causing the surface to warm, as it is pictured in *Figure 11*. (Scheffer, 2009). In other words, deforestation is a major cause of the worrying phenomena of global warming and climate change, of which though it will be discussed more extensively in *Section 3.1.4*.

Figure 11. Climatic effects of tropical deforestation. Source: Scheffer, 2009.

3.1.2 Individual environmentally unsustainable behaviours in households

Besides the predominance of wood fuels for domestic energy production and consequent charcoal burning, there also other individual behaviours that have contributed to environmental destruction. In particular unsustainable agricultural practices commonly adopted in households (probably unconsciously) are now recognised to be one, and the first among those emerged to be the use of synthetic fertilizers. Following the historical narrative of the rapid population growth, despite their expansion, the portion of land per household was not large enough for the new increased number of family members, hence there was a shift from extensive to intensive production (Mr. Paul, 45-50yo, agribusiness

²⁸ Albedo is defined as “the amount of the light hitting a surface that it reflects back, especially the surface of a planet or other body in space” (Cambridge Dictionary).

expert), for which people started to look for and use all the methods that could ensure higher yields from their cultivations. “Farmers want to accelerate production processes to yield more and get money” (field notes, 24th September 2024, visit of their farm) told me Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter when asking them about this topic. Again, demographic increase crosses its path with poverty resulting into a reckless behaviour moved by survival urges that does not allow room for environmental reasoning. Synthetic fertilisers and chemical products are an efficient strategy to gain in little time higher results from the crops, especially in small or virgin lands, but present relevant problems: first, they are toxic for the human health, as Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter were further explaining “people in Nairobi, who eat more food from synthetic methods, start to have health problems at 60, like cancer, here at 80” (field notes, *ibidem*); second, they provoke erosion and land degradation, hence also soil fertility depletion. This gives origin to a vicious cycle, where farmers are then forced to apply more fertilizers to enhance the poor productivity of the cultivated soil, and for the reasons above, people will tend to use chemical types instead of organic ones -instead of healthy ones for both humans and environment. According to the two farmers, another incentive not to shift away from these methods comes from the government, which for business reasons often supports companies that produce this strategic means for high production and hence encourages their consumption (field notes, *ibidem*). The negative effects deriving from the use of chemical products are not limited to the soil, but also extend to animals: those being fed from those lands, as humans, are nourished with unhealthy food, and the increasing use of pesticides applications have deadly implications on bees and other valuable insects and species (National Environment Management Authority, 2021). Unsustainable methods, in terms of both intensity and modality, are also employed in fishing activities, damaging the aquatic ecosystems.

3.1.3 Pollution

Improper farming methods and human activities upstream also affect water quality, causing soil erosion and water pollution. This is another significant negative effect on the environment, to the extent that it impacts on the forms of life dependent on it: fish die and contract diseases, but also the land animals, who drink from those water streams and lakes, not to mention humans themselves. A massive use of fertilizers induces, as in the Lake Victoria, the toxic phenomenon of eutrophication: the additional quantity of

nutrients fosters an excessive growth of plants and breaks the ecosystem life balance, insofar those latter will exploit the water's oxygen and deprive of it the other vegetal and animal organisms of the aquatic system (*ibidem*).

Water pollution is itself one of the factors contributing to soil pollution, decreasing further its health and fertility. Another extremely relevant problem is the poor -or inexistent- waste management.

“[Ms. Valery] At the moment there is no recycling of plastic.

Ahm, so everything is being thrown away?

[Ms. Valery] Or burnt, we don't know this.

[Ms. Iphrys] The trash, the residuals -like plastic- paper, everything- is burnt.

We don't have anywhere to recycle them.”

(Ms. Valery and Ms. Iphrys, 40-50y, teachers at Kuth Awendo Resource Centre school)

When I was living in the Resource Centre, I was able to experience this by myself, constrained to ‘aliment the system’. It was strange, and difficult in a sense, due to the

Figure 12. Toilet of the Resource Centre in Kuth Awendo.

force of habit and to the ethical principles, but that was the situation, how it was done there, so I had to adapt. When I had questions on where to throw my trash residuals, some uncertainty was there, but the answer then was “in the toilet”, where the toilet was a hole in the floor of a raised fortune infrastructure (*Figure 12.*). Food waste is the only one to be collected, either to produce some organic fertilizers or to feed the animals. At the workcamp, for example, there were three dogs around.

No differentiation of waste is done in the households, also due to the reason that no industry is there to operate the collection and the recycling. Rather, it is indifferently accumulated or burnt. In both cases, pollution of soil and air is produced, and in severe measures. According to the World Bank (2019), the solid waste scenario is a major challenge affecting environmental and natural resources. Also, it affects the community itself.

“And how does this affect your life, in your opinion?”

[Ms. Iphrys] The environment being toxic.

[Ms. Valery] Making the environment toxic, even the rain.

[Ms. Iphrys] When the rain comes down -you can't- the water is dirty, you cannot drink it because if the trash is around the water is dirty!

[Ms. Karen] The insects, the insects also stay there...

[Ms. Iphrys] Of course the insects stay in the trash, and they bring diseases, so this is a big problem, and also the soil maybe is not productive. There are many consequences; I have to list them in my head! The water is dirty, the insects are more, the soil is more polluted...

[Ms. Christina] Many problems... we have many problems...”

(Ms. Valery, Ms. Iphrys, Ms. Karen, and Mr. Christina; 30-50 yo, teachers at
Kuth Awendo Resource Centre school)

Especially, plastics abandonment in nature and its burning are an issue. There are policies enacted by the government to reduce its consumption, operating at the root of the problem, but obstacles hamper their effectiveness, by hand of private citizens and private companies.

“The current president is trying to regain the forest land, to make things work in terms of environmental protection. And even now, the issue of plastics. Now, we have a framework whereby we are not supposed to dispose plastics everywhere. So yeah, that is also somehow helping. Because if you compare that time and now, there's a very big difference.

So before, plastic was everywhere?

Everywhere, yes.

And you did not have bins or... How do you throw it away now?

Right now, okay: for disposal of plastics, we don't have a very good means of disposing the plastics. But I would say that it is much better than how it was.

Okay, but thanks to whom? The government or...

The government. Because the government, first of all, reduced the number of plastics being manufactured in Kenya. So they went down. So they put a policy, you cannot produce more than [a certain amount], for example.

Do you know if they monitor if there is any penalty if you produce more or throw away plastics? Is there a penalty?

There is a penalty for using plastic bags. But now, people still buy plastic bags from Uganda. They are not produced in Kenya. Yeah, so they smuggle them from Uganda through the border. That's why you'll see a few plastic bags. They are still illegal, but people... they are brought in illegally. (long pause) But now, the government is also trying to come up with something that can stop the plastic bottles. But then, it faces a challenge because the bottling companies like Coca-Cola, they say if you are not giving us this, then we are not supporting your economy in this and this manner.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

As reported by Mr. Dilman in the piece of interview above, individuals break the rule of the limit to plastic bags by importing them illegally and at a low price from the neighbouring country of Uganda, while big private companies as Coca Cola are able to influence the country government and hamper initiatives when inconvenient for them, thanks to their significant economic power. Additionally, multinational corporations account also for contributing to air pollution, by the emission of CO₂ and greenhouse gases (GHG), worsening an already severe situation. Charcoal burning and improper agricultural methods, as already treated in the previous pages, contribute massively to air pollution. In particular, to provide some data, according to the Initial Energy Status Report of Kisumu County, at national level in 2013, the agricultural sector emitted 62.8% of total emissions, followed by the energy sector (31.2%), industrial sector (4.6%) and waste sector (1.4%), while having a narrower look at the statistics relative to Kisumu County, forestry accounts for the 36.6%, agricultural sector for the 24.2%, energy demand for 13.9% and electricity production for 6.4% (C. Buma, 2020).

In conclusion, environmental pollution -anthropologically originated-, is another extremely relevant factor constituting a huge risk for the life and health of living species of the territory, both humans and natural: respectively, it contributes to around 60,000 deaths in Kenya (World Bank, 2019), the endangerment of birds, aquatic and land animals, and the impoverishment of plant biodiversity.

3.1.4 Climate change

The harsher consequences of climate change started to manifest around the half of the second decade of this century, and referring to the research of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) -created in 1988 with the exact purpose to monitor and conduct reliable scientific studies on this newly emerging phenomenon-, we find that 2016 was actually the hottest year ever registered before, and the global temperature was measured to be $+1.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to pre-industrial levels. Since then, climate-related extreme weather disasters disproportionately started to increase globally in both frequency and intensity, peaking in 2023, which outclassed 2016 as hottest year on record, measuring a $+1.45^{\circ}\text{C}$ global temperature (World Meteorological Organization, 2024). Indeed, the first dramatic change occurred the '90s, as the graph below shows (*ibidem*), when the amount of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere had reached the highest level in the last half-million years (Le Treut et al., 2007). Keeping referring to the IPCC

Figure 13. Global Mean Temperature Difference (°C), 1850-2023. Source: WMO (2024).

explanations, greenhouse gases²⁹ are fundamental for the survival of the Earth's forms of life, as they “act as a partial blanket for the longwave radiation coming from the surface” and hence contribute to the warmth of the planet's surface; nonetheless, human activities –“primarily the combustion of fossil fuels and removal of forests”–, provoked additional and massive release of greenhouse gases, altering the chemical composition of the global atmosphere and with substantial implications for the climate due to the sudden artificial intensification of the blanketing effect and consequent increase in global temperature. Scientific studies conducted in the second half of the past century, converge in concluding that “observed climate changes cannot be explained by natural factors alone” and that an anthropogenic contribution is “clearly statistically identifiable in observed data” (*ibidem*, p.97).

Attested the existence of a causal relationship between human activities and climate change, we can now dive into the analysis of its (negative) effects on the environment, through both scientific references and the voices from the community. The increase in GHG emissions and deforestation progressively led to an increasing warming of the planet with the effects shown in *Figure 14*.

Figure 14. Left - Regular levels of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), and nitrous oxide (N₂O), trapping some of the sun's heat and preventing the planet from freezing. Right - The rampant emission of CO₂ from burning fossil fuels traps excess heat and results in an increase in the average temperature of our planet. Source: Elder, 2016

²⁹ The most important greenhouse gases being water vapor and carbon dioxide. The two most abundant constituents of the atmosphere – nitrogen and oxygen – have no such effect, whereas clouds do have some but is offset by their reflectivity. The amount of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere has increased by about 35% in the industrial era (Le Treut et al., 2007).

If climatic change effects were already witnessed in the 90s after the beginning of deforestation and intensified GHG emissions (refer to *Section 3.1.1.*), by escalating in alterations in the water cycle, increased frequency and intensity of droughts and ultimately in violent floods unblocked by soil erosion, with the peak in the rise of global mean temperature occurred in the 2010s (*Figure 14.*) and the relative further changes in many climatic factors (such as temperature and precipitation), the manifesting consequences proportionally followed, exacerbating dramatically the phenomena already witnessed in the '90s:

“[...] so like, the long rain season it's not long anymore, because it's warmer!

Climate is the problem, because it's more warmer and then it's drier.

[...] when did the climate start to change?

Here, it seems something like 10 years back. Yeah, 10 years”.

(Ms. Elisabeth, 30-35yo, farmer)

According to Elisabeth, droughts had always been there, but before they were able to foresee them. In the last ten years, instead, they have become more unpredictable and casual, making it is difficult to adjust the planting to the season (field notes, 25th September 2024). As a premise, the reader must be acknowledged of the fact that in Kenya there are historically two main rainy seasons: the first, of long and heavier rains, is usually since mid-March to May; the second, the shorter one, occurs in November and December. This pattern is very important for Kenyan households, as they will plant different crops accordingly and timely (field notes, knowledge acquired living in the community; also, Brian explicitly mentioned the periods).

“Okay, I have two questions on this. First is, when there is a drought, do you expect it or not? How is it? Like, practically.

[Mr. Bitter] Yeah, we can, because we have seen, sometimes we have seen patterns of rain, but because of the climate change, that pattern, sometimes we miss. So, mostly from the month of May, May through July, we always have drought, then some showers, then it rains.

Okay, and now it changed?

[Mr. Bitter] Now, it's now.

When did it start changing?

[Mr. Bitter] I think from 2015. 2015, yeah. There's a change. For the climate change, because it's warmer, so it doesn't... So, like, the droughts come...

[Mr. Ogando] We have a stream there. Some years back, it was not drying up; now it is.

(Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter, 40-50yo, farmers)

In summary, while changes in rainfall patterns began to manifest in the 1990s, the 2010s experienced more pronounced and widespread alterations, including more severe droughts and increased rainfall variability. The exacerbation of the already severe environmental conditions (such as soil erosion, heat, humidity) has as direct consequences the increase in wildfires -dangerous for living species-, worsening air pollution, and the increase -especially in intensity- of extreme weather events (National Environment Management Authority, 2021). Some examples are the excessive rainfall brought by the climatic phenomenon of El Niño in the years 1997-98, triggering a violent flood (Mr. Dilman, interview 1st October 2024); the 2011 drought hitting severely the whole country, described as the worst in 60 years (NASA Earth Observatory, 2011); the flood occurred in April 2024, with already one in 2023 in the same period provoking harsh devastation.

As a conclusion, it is possible to assert -in light of the precedent pages- that anthropogenic behaviours have actively contributed, if not provoked, negative consequences on the environment, leading to a progressively more unhealthy and degraded condition. The manifestation of such disequilibrated conditions does not, though, limit their negative effects to the environment itself and its biodiversity, but extend -and widely- also to its human inhabitants. The next subchapter will take charge exactly of examination the impact of such an *unhealthy environment* on its people.

3.2 The impact of an unhealthy environment on humans

3.2.1 Impact of droughts

Droughts imply scarcity of water in the rains, streams and soil, and the first and most direct consequence of that regards the individual use of water done by humans: drinking and washing. During one of the visits to the schools –namely Kuth Awendo primary school–, I personally witnessed an extremely cruel scene: kids waiting for water drops from the common fountain (*Figure 15.*). One of them then asked my colleague first for money (common also in the streets), but then for water too, and that broke our hearts.

Figure 15. Child waiting for water drops at the Kuth Awendo primary school.

Mr. David, teacher at the Kuth Awendo school, whom I interviewed a few moments later, told me that this school was one of the poorest in the area, with a low fee and hence without lunch and water included in the services provided. Not only the kids have the problem of getting water, but it is a difficulty for him as well, and when there is the drought the situation is exacerbated.

“Do they bring water from home?”

I normally tell them to bring water; they use to bring it from home. I have a situation about that. Actually, it’s a problem. Sometimes they just go like that. Like now, you can watch. They go like that: they don't bring it from home.”

(Mr. David, 30-40yo, teacher at Kuth Awendo school)

One episode hit me on kids approach to water: I had become close with one of the cooks' grandchildren, Natasha (3-4yo), and even if we spoke different languages, we managed to understand each other on games to play and basic things by gestures. She used to always have a snotty nose and hug me, so I would often wash her face at the water container (*Figure 17.*)³⁰ before holding her in my arms. It was more of a game for her, and when one day I mimed to her to clean up her nose and she used her saliva, there I understood she did not have the habit to *spontaneously* think to the container as source of usable water. This little story brings to the second direct use of clean water, which is washing and hygiene. I could witness that, despite the effort, the hygiene levels were not at their highest (field notes). Again, droughts exacerbate this situation. This is a small and yet still soft insight of how issues of basic drinking needs and primary healthcare, referred to as WASH (Water, Sanitation and Hygiene) in the international development landscape, look like. A harsh consequence of scarce quantity and quality of water is the exposure to diseases.

Figure 17. Container of drinkable boiled water at the camp.

Figure 16. Dishwashing and, on the background, the place where they were put to dry.

³⁰ To make sure it is clean and drinkable, water is usually boiled in households and left available in small containers. At the work camp we had one in the garden and one in the kitchen. The accessibility therefore becomes limited, less spontaneous.

The impact suffered the most by the people during drought, however, is the scarcity of water for their farming activities, and every family relies on household agriculture to survive. I learnt this by the cooks, who could not believe I did not have a piece of land to cultivate at home, and from children in schools, who told me that everybody has one; they were telling me what they grew in theirs, and how they also worked at it; also for this reason, agriculture is one of the prominent subjects at school. Without water, though, it is impossible for things to grow, the crops die, and no harvest is possible. Mr. David told me that for food it is the same as for water: the students are supposed to bring their own lunch, but not always they have one during droughts; the same is for him, especially because having a family he prefers to leave the little produced to his children at home (Kuth Awendo, 2nd October 2024). However, this is an extreme condition, as the Kuth Awendo school gathers the poorest family of the community -it is not the most common situation: according to Rhoda, famine is not excessively severe in Kenya; in some region people struggle, but are still able to get a meal once a day generally; the real problem is poverty, she said, “especially during drought periods” (field notes, 24th September 2024). A statistical correspondence can be found: in 2020, hunger -also referred to as “prevalence of undernourishment”- was measured to account to 24.7% of the total population, while poverty to the high and worrying level of 91.0% (Kenya Hunger Statistics 2001-2024, 2024). The main role of agriculture, in fact, is not only to provide the necessary resources for a self-sufficient survival, but economic: surpluses are sold on the market, and that is the main source of income for most families -the 40% of the total population and more than the 70% of Kenya's rural people, accounting for the 33% (60% if linkages to other sectors are considered) of the country's GDP (FAO, 2023).

“Last years back you can say, oh, August is a rainy season, we plan our things. But right now planning is just... we have to wait for it because, you can plan that August will be rain for us, but no, there's no rain. But you know, you see like right now we expect some rains in August and September, no.

And they're not coming?

Not coming. There's a lot of drought, unexpected drought in August.

I know it was like one of the rainiest months.

Yeah, yeah. But nowadays it's just really...some years there's rain and some years there's not. / So you don't know when to do the things / (*frustrated*).

You just have to wait. You see when you can do it. It really affected many people and it's bringing so many people, I can say, bring poverty because there are many people who depend on farming.”

(Mr. Paul, 40-50yo, agribusiness expert)

Elisabeth and Samuel have pools they fill with the water from a close pond, nourished by the rain, to water fields and grow fishes. With the drought, not only they lose their crops, but also their fish -which is prominent among the products they sell- die. One indirect consequence of droughts, passing through the poverty issue, is the difficulty to grant continuous schooling to children. In such periods, when not only revenues decrease, but also the price of food -due its lower supply on the market- increases, families struggle to pay the expensive school fees. Parents as Elisabeth and Samuel choose to hire teachers to come home, for the necessary period, as it is less expensive.

“We are using the money between the use in educating our children and the farm as a labor; most of them we use as a labor, we pay the labor so we can take some people to come and give them classes.

Ah, so like, teachers come here to your children, and teach from home...

I guess it's more difficult to go to school, because it's expensive, isn't it?

Yeah, it is expensive... / though, we are trying.../ (*sad*).

[...] If we get that water, we'll grow and grow more vegetables, so that we do away with this poverty and its vicious cycle! We get water, grow the plants, they get the water, and the life continues, goes on, the children go to school!”

(Ms. Elisabeth, 30-35yo, farmer)

A strategy that some poorer schools employ is to charge one unique fee at the beginning of the year instead of periodic ones, so that attendance can be granted throughout the whole year independently from income changes that may prevent from paying the second or third part. This is what happens for example at Mr. David's school. Even granting attendance, though, education is still hampered by droughts, due to the unbearable heat it brings with it. The situation is exacerbated when, as frequent in poor or average schools, trees lack, or the infrastructure is made out of iron sheets (*Figure 18*).

“This place becomes very hot at times. That in itself is a challenge. Now when you get out with the children, maybe you do not have the portable boards and such kind of things. But you now need to work out with them.”

(Mr. Dick, 30-35yo, teacher, field notes)

Figure 18. Schools in Kuth Awendo and in Nyakongo.

Other reasons of schooling discontinuity derive from the fact that teachers often need to do also other jobs, in order to earn enough to feed their families, and will not cover the full hours at school. David himself, again voice of the worst scenarios, rendered me participant of his struggle and desperation.

“Me, the director, and only one other teacher. The rest might not come because of the harsh conditions.

But also the teachers do not come for the conditions?

They don't come. So we have to look for other teachers.

But how can they not come?

It's like if they need some money, they have to go. They have to do other jobs.

Do you also struggle sometimes?

Actually.

To feed your family?

Actually, because I have already taken all the salary from this man. And they are closing the school.

In the middle of the year?

Yeah. They are closing the school. Meaning, I don't know what I'm going to eat. / I don't know how I'm going to live. And I have two kids. / (*frustrated*)

And you don't know how to feed them?

I don't know what I'm going to do. I'm going to see if I can get a job around.²

How do you do with the school if you get another job?

The school is just for the owner. If I get another job, I can go and work there.

Okay, so you do two jobs in one day.

Yeah. Normally, what I do is music. I like playing the guitar and the keyboard.”

(Mr. David, 30-40yo, teacher at Kuth Awendo school)

Looking for an additional job is common to offset the difficulties provoked by drought, in a direct way for farmers, but also for the other people, as the prices increase, and they might lose their jobs. Having side business activities is common also in normal times, to hedge against contingencies. According to Rhoda, also thanks to this entrepreneurial mindset, poverty -even if still there- diminished a bit with respect to the past (field notes, 24th October 2024).

“Okay, if you want we can start.

My name is Oskar Ogando. For my daily life I do agriculture and some of internet work. That's what I do for a living.

Oh, okay. So, the farming is...

Farming is the major one. The other is to have like something surer, in the case that something bad happens with the harvest.

Okay, like to diversify the activities.

Yes, if everything goes bad there's another option to have.”

(Mr. Ogando, 40-50yo, farmer)

It results clear that the impact of droughts is not limited to direct effects of reducing drinkable water and hygiene, but through its worst consequence of creating poverty, it also affects food security and education, and leads to the stress of looking how to cope with it.

3.2.2 *Impact of floods*

“If I asked you to think about environmental issues -like which they are, how they impact the life of the people-, what would you say?”

The environmental issues I would like to talk about mostly, one of the things, is the flooding. Flooding has been a very serious thing, especially in the area we work with in Kano Plains. So Ahero, Kuth Awendo, these areas are in Kano Plains. The major issue we've been having is flooding. And whenever it floods, then you find that people are displaced. Like last, this year, when we had long rains, there were floods in Kenya and many people died.

What month was it?

In May. In May, very many people died in Kenya because of floods. In Nairobi, even in Kisumu. But this time round in Kisumu, it was not as bad as it is usually, as it usually happens.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

The March-to-May floods, additionally worsened by the El Niño³¹ climate phenomenon, provoked 294 deaths in Kenya, as stated in the 2024 Kenya Red Cross flood operations report (Mutura, 2025), 188 injured, and 281,835 people (56,367 families) were displaced. Among these, 14,060 is the number of the displaced people counted in Kisumu County, keeping in mind that this event was not even one of the most serious for the region, according to Mr. Dilman’s words. In the teachers’ voices I could grasp the emotions connected to this event: scared by the flood hitting so bad even the capital; sympathetic with those involved, having already experienced on their own skin the same distress; suffering, fear, and a sense of feeling overwhelmed and powerless, emerged.

“April: in April people were dying in Nairobi, which is a city, and you don't expect the water can go into Nairobi! The area was completely flooded.

[...] During the flood people get sick... some might die, and there is nowhere they can be buried [...]”.

(Ms. Valery, 28yo, teacher at Kuth Awendo school)

³¹ El Niño is a periodic climate pattern by which trade winds in the Pacific ocean weaken, causing the surface water of central and eastern Pacific to unusually warm up and the Pacific jet stream to move south. This affects phenomenon affects global weather patterns, rendering drier warmer and drier areas in Canada and Northern United States, and bringing heavy rains to some areas, as like East Africa (NOAA 2024).

“Have you particularly suffered any of the effects of climate change?

If we can start with, to say, rain, flooding. During floods, we experience a lot of effects of climate change.

And I can tell you, during that period, there is loss of life and properties.

Lots of lives?

Yes, there are so many people are drowning.

Do you have a friend or a relative who has died?

Yeah, I have a friend who died, who was drowned in Ombaka area.”

(Mr. Moses, 35-40 yo, Farmer and permaculture expert, Red Cross staff)

In addition, an unpredictable massive flood disaster is generally associated with an increased risk of waterborne infectious diseases due to the direct impact of floodwater (Shafii *et.al*, 2023) as the cholera and typhoid reported by Brian (4th October, Kuth Awendo). The risk of proliferation of disease-causing pathogens increases on a longer term, due to the physical vulnerability experienced by those hit by the disaster, in reason of contaminated drinking water after the heavy rain, food scarcity, displacement, and lack of accessibility to basic healthcare services (likely destruction of hospitals, and roads).

Figure 19. Overall vulnerability by sector: every sector is negatively affected by floods (Transparency International Kenya, n.d.).

Death, be it by direct impact of the flood or by related health issues, is only one of the many risks linked to floods, which with respect to other environmental issues are the one impacting the highest number of sectors related to human life (Figure.19); furthermore, as it will be exemplified in the following lines, the connections among these sectors amplify exponentially the overall people’s vulnerability.

Displacement is at the centre of such a case. First, it is very common in relation to floods especially in the rural areas of Kenya because the houses are generally made of soil and cow dung, wood and mud, or at best, of iron sheets (field notes, Nam, while on a *piki piki* together crossing Ahero village, 3rd October 2024), see *Figure 21*.

“Because you know, *it’s about poverty*. It’s too expensive to build a house, like a permanent one. Maybe what you can afford is just wood, then you call your friends to come and use the mud to help you”: explained Mr. Paul to me when I was observing the fragility of the houses, which for sure would not bear the power of water. When houses get destroyed “people get scattered. They leave their houses there and go to some places. The government, mostly the government takes them to schools” (3rd October, Ahero), as in most cases there is at least one school built with solid walls (see *Figure 20*.) close to each village, capable to resist to the floodings and give shelter to displaced families.

Figure 20. Average house in rural villages. Figure 21. School in Ahero, 3rd October. Katolo, 24th September.

This situation implies several vulnerabilities. First, the living conditions in these schools are terrible: Christine, teacher at Kuth Awendo Resource Centre (3rd October), tells it happened to her to stay, for the whole three-four weeks until the water dried, in the same one room of the school with other 12 people. Food also becomes an issue, and people start fight for it (field notes, Mr. David, 2nd October, Kuth Awendo).

The right to education is also implicitly violated by the environmental insecurity directly connected to floods: children of the poorest families see their schools, likely also built in iron sheets, to get filled by high levels of water (50-60cm according to Mr. David), while children of richer households see their schools to become emergency shelters. In any case, the roads would be impracticable, and neither the children nor the teachers could reach the schools. The same story characterises health facilities, either destroyed or inaccessible, and this exacerbates the health conditions, already endangered by the low hygiene, nourishment and hydration of people, weak and at risk of contracting diseases. According to the Kenya Human Rights Commission (2024), the March-to-May floods submerged or destroyed at least 62 primary schools throughout Kenya -with the projection by the government that an estimated 15,000 children may have not got back to school-, and raised the risk of waterborne diseases, given more than 20,000 toilet blocks either sunken or severely damaged, “posing serious health risks to over 1.5 million school children across the country”.

Another consequence indirectly impacts the life of the people: not only the houses get destroyed by waterfloods, but also the fields and the animals grown by the households. “It destroys everything: the house, the harvest, plus the poultry’s dying. You lose everything and you have to build, to build again the things in your house” (Elisabeth, 25th September, Katolo). As the newspaper The Star (2024) reports, keeping in consideration only the Kisumu country, 1,756 acres of farmland and crops were destroyed and 2,000 livestock were affected, during the April flood. If poverty is one of the leading causes of vulnerability to the extreme weather events happening in Kenya, it is also one of their consequences, in a vicious cycle that exacerbates already frail living conditions. While farming activities are in general enough for the families in the Kisumu area and in most of Kenya -according to the words of Rhoda (field notes, 24th September)- to get enough food for self-nourishment (“people are usually able to get at least one meal a day”), they become insufficient to create profit on the products during floods and droughts. The harvest and livestock are essential for a family’s business, and when floods destroys everything they lose their main source of income. At that point, families have to start over again, but with an impoverished soil; in view of that, I asked Elisabeth and Samuel whether they were willing to move after a flood: “move? And move where?” she replied. If forced displacement is an issue, also the impossibility to move away is one.

3.2.3 Mental health, gender inequality, and armed conflicts

The words of Elisabeth were filled with frustration and resignation, but also of hope of a different future for their children. Emotions are often overlooked when analysing the consequences of extreme events or conditions, but the impact on mental health should not be neglected. The consequences related to environmental insecurity -as poverty, hunger, threats to life- can lead to intense level of stress and anxiety: “a high number of people goes through depression, some even through suicide attempts” told me Mr. Moses (4th October, Ahero). He cared about underlining the psychological dimension of the effects of droughts and floods on the life of the people, and it surprised me, as he was the only one to observe explicitly the problem, while in the other interviews the results were more implicit in the answers and in the stories. For example, when I asked Elisabeth and Samuel how they felt during droughts, in connection to the economic difficulties they were telling me about, and answered describing the situation: “You see, we are using our effort, with little money, and we are putting something: unfortunately that thing is dry” (Samuel); almost the same happened with the four teachers: I had asked them how they felt when they had to move to schools after floods and they replied only referring again to hunger and thirst, never explicitly mentioning any emotion. It seemed to me that in such bad conditions there is no space to think around feelings, but only about physical sensations; yet, mental health and psychological well-being are also a fundamental dimension of the broader human right to health and well-being, another one violated by environmental insecurity.

Negative spillover effects are had also on the conditions of women, widening gender inequalities: Valery, Christina, Karen and Iphrys, were telling me that, within a household organisation, “everything is upon the mother”: women are traditionally invested of the most of the house tasks: cleaning, cooking, taking care of the children and of their school needs, ensuring that food and water are there, and often also have a job. “So”, explained Iphrys, “if the mother cannot answer to the needs of the family” -for instance, if food lacks in a period of drought when the business is poorer- “there is a conflict between the husband and the wife” and “there are some which can bring you to war. When you answer, you answer it rudely, to him.” These conflicts often end up in physical violence. Mr. Moses was also reporting on situations provoked by the difficult

times induced by droughts and floods, which create ground for discussions in the household. He told how this circumstance exacerbates an already unfair discrimination of women: “The constitution is very clear: a woman should own a land. [...] But here in the community, you find that women, they don't have it”, the sons will most likely get land. This way, every woman remains dependent on the father and then on the husband, with limited decisional power and without the possibility choose to divorce or get separated, for example when situations of such violence happen, as she would be deadbeat.

In addition to internally in household, divergencies often arises in times of crisis generated by environmental threats, between neighbours, fighting over land or water use for example. General discontent and conflict propagate easily within the society, provoking social unrest and instability. Environmental issues consequences, and in the study of Professor Louis-Alexandre Berg of Sciences Po (2024) climate change specifically, exacerbates the risk factors for armed conflict, namely grievances, opportunities, and weak state institutions. Respectively, increasing prices of food and fuel alongside with poverty, loss of livelihoods and land, forced displacement, all contribute to enhance pre-existing societal cleavages and create opportunity for grievances and uprisings, while the incapability of the State to efficaciously tackle the root problems weaken the institution in front of this social unrest, paving the way for effective armed conflict. This is the story behind the Syrian Civil war (2011): between 2007 and 2010, in fact, severe droughts in Syria triggered mass rural-to-urban migration, rising poverty, and limited economic opportunities, fuelling political protest against the Assad government and adherence to the ISIS forces as employment opportunity, and ultimately leading to the civil war. Similar mechanisms were witnessed in the lake Chad region. In Kenya, social unrest is currently manifesting, in correlation to the lack of State effective response to the challenges also related to extreme weather conditions, through protests in the capital carried on by the youth, organised in the “Gen Z” movement (Brian, 30th September, Kuth Awendo).

3.2.4 Environmental issues as risk multipliers

It emerges, from all of the previous sections of this chapter, that the environment in the Kisumu region is unhealthy, and that this has a wide range of severely negative impacts on its population. The conceptual map below (Figure 22.) summarises the results of the data collected in the community picturing, in a simplified way for the sake of synthesis, cause-effect relations between specific issues deriving from an unhealthy environment and the consequences suffered by the people, highlighting the related human rights violated.

Figure 22. Conceptual map of the impact of environmental issues in the Kisumu region on its community.

“*” := also linked concepts; pollution, food insecurity and poverty, given the limited accessibility of healthcare services, are also increasing the exposure to diseases and the risk of suffering from them. The numbers in brackets indicate the corresponding article in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948)

As the map shows, numerous human rights, among those listed in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948), are violated, and in many different ways. Environmental issues can be a direct cause of this violation, as in the case of forced

displacement (the drought destroys the house hampering the right to home -art. 8 UDHR); however, the violation can also be indirect, or manifest only in the long-term: those extreme weather events may fuel ongoing crises exacerbating them to the point to lead to new violations; this is often the case of food insecurity and poverty. They may trigger the realisation of latent problems, as gender violence, which breaks out *additionally* in the moment food is not brought on the table (Iphrys, refer to 3.2.3); or, they can generate a *new* violation, that would have not existed without an extreme weather event provoking the worsening of the economic conditions of the household, as in the case of school dropout induced by the unaffordability of the fee following a drought period. Living in an unhealthy environment, as emerges from the study, acts as a *risk multiplier*, in the sense that it increases the possibilities that a human right is violated, and also the very same range of rights under such risk.

The concept of “climate change as a threat multiplier”, indeed, has become widely used by scholars and practitioners, to describe its implications for security in both the policy realm and climate-security literature (Goodman & Baudu, 2023); yet, I would like to widen this reflection to a broader consideration. As described in *Section 3.1.4*, climate change is yes a major one, but not the *only* factor contributing to anthropogenic environmental disruption: recall deforestation, poor waste management, pollution, industrial activities, unsustainable agricultural and energy production methods, excessive resources exploitation. For this reason, I reckon that limiting the concept to climate change might be restrictive and insufficient to address all the issues in the environmental field that act as risk multipliers. On the effect side, likewise, the term “threat” is usually understood to refer to national security matters³², whereas the consequences affecting people are much broader, impacting on a wide range of human rights; for the reasons above, it appears more appropriate to use the term “risks”.

These effects, it stemmed out, may not be *directly* connected to an environmental issue, but maybe indirectly through other conditions worsened by that event, or on the

³² “Threat multiplier” became since 2006, the U.S. Center for Naval Analyses’ (CNA) Military Advisory Board on Climate Change and National Security signature phrase and has become a key concept in the global debate on climate change and its connections to national security, with substantial influence on U.S. and international security policy (Goodman & Baudu, 2023).

long term, or again only crystalising the occurrence of an abuse concurring to its determinant factors. This proves the point of the necessity, under the legal framework, for a *substantial* human right to a healthy environment: to overcome not only the insufficiency of an eco-centric approach (environmental law) to encompass the effects on people, but also that of the anthropocentric approach consisting of “greening” human rights, as it would not be able to catch indirect or long-term effects, or to include exacerbated situations as gender violence. But most of all, the results of this study showing the tremendous consequences that living in an unhealthy environment has on its community, call for the impellent necessity to *act*, for a cessation of the environmental degradation, a reparation of its damages, mitigation of its effects, and adaptation to the new irreversible circumstances.

The next section will exactly go through these behaviours of resilience, investigating how the switch to sustainable approaches and innovative ways of coping with an unhealthy environment can benefit both nature itself and its living communities.

3.2.5 Reparation, mitigation, and adaptation: positive effects

Despite being often very slow, the majority of environmental processes are not irreversible: according to the scientists, the risk of reaching at least one of the sixteen individuated tipping points is high (62%) but not inevitable (Gray, 2025): it is imperative to immediately cease damaging anthropogenic practices, and possibly to start reparation ones. This is true also at micro-level, and in the Kisumu area the effects of doing so have already become visible in Badilisha. Here resides one of the offices and sites of action of the CIVS Kenya, where the organisation started in 2012 a drainage project, organic-only farming, and a reforestation activity to induce a restoration of the water cycle. When I visited the office with my volunteering team, Nancie -from the CIVS staff there (28th September)- showed us the grown trees and told us that the rains had already re-acquired regularity, the soil was not dry anymore compared to ten years before, and the climate had changed. Despite being very little far from Kuth Awendo, I could tell myself that difference: the air was much more humid, and the landscape green and flourishing. This reversion has also allowed the community to restart their businesses, planning their crops according to the restored regular rain seasons, harvesting with success and selling on the market the expected surpluses.

Among the mitigation measures adopted in the Kano Plains communities, the shift away from charcoal as main source of domestic energy production is for sure one of the most important ones. According to Mr. Bitter (24th September, Nyando), around 20 years ago, environmental rights “were pathetic”, but now some improvement is witnessed:

“I think now there's some improvement because people are now becoming aware of the good environment, like planting trees. Yes, most of the time, like if you go to every home at the moment, you'll find though even though some people are still using the traditional charcoal, the rate has now gone down. Some of us, like me, I do solar at home. And for the cooking at the moment I'm using the LPG³³, but I moved from the charcoal itself.”

Switching the energy production to more sustainable methods and sources reduces the emissions of GHG in the atmosphere and mitigates in this case the effects of climate change (European Environment Agency, 2024), where *mitigation* is to be intended as an active intervention aimed at reducing environmental issues and risks.

Different is the case for adaptation, which does not consist in an act *on* the environment, but through it, to mitigate the *effects* of existing environmental issues, in the view that reparation is yes possible, but also slow, and that in the meanwhile communities shall be enabled to find a safe way through the dangers. It aims at enhancing the people's coping mechanisms. For example, Brian (30th September, Kuth Awendo) he was telling that there are some species of trees that with their extensive root system are stable in the ground even in front of a waterflood, and if planted in strategic points they may reduce the violence of the stream and prevent disastrous impacts on the community; similarly, he suggested the farmers of the village to grow cassava in their households, as it is a tuberous edible plant, great source of carbohydrates and calories, and also a drought-resistant crop, to cope with food insecurity when it's dry. Mr. Paul (3rd October, Ahero) promotes instead new maize varieties that mature earlier adapting to the climate, and the use of greenhouses can as an anthropogenic method to cultivate in a humid environment as needed, with constant characteristics and obtaining successful crops regardless of the

³³ LPG = Liquefied Petroleum Gas. It is still a derivate from oil, but produces around 15-20% less emissions than petrol and diesel.

weather outside it them. To cope with the water problem during drought periods, dams and ponds can be built to exploit rain and flood waters -then appropriately filtered-, or boreholes to collect already clean water from the ground (Samuel and Elisabeth, 25th September, Katolo). Another example would be farming and job diversification, to diversify the sources of income in case one is disrupted by drought or floods, the strategy employed by Mr. Bitter (24th September, Nyando). These behaviours demonstrate that humanity can still evolve together with her environment, and eventually perceive it as healthy once adapted to it.

Given the research and results of the whole chapter, it is in conclusion possible to affirm, with regard to the assessment of the degree of realisation of the HRHE in the examined area in Kisumu County, that despite “the situation has improved a bit, [a HRHE] is still being built.” (field notes, from the specific words of Brian; also, this is the average answer provided by all of the community members interviewed at the question “at which point do you think we are in the enjoyment of a HRHE?”). The next chapter will investigate all of the processes contributing to the consolidation of a HRHE in the region.

CHAPTER IV

Consolidation processes

The present chapter will extensively investigate *how* the human right to a healthy environment “is being built”, exploring in two dedicated sections the contributions and impact of institutional initiatives “from above” and of the civil society “from below”.

In the context of the inputs “from above”, a first section will be opened by the analysis of the introduction and impact of the human right to live in a clean and healthy environment in the Kenyan Constitution in 2010, by act of President Kibaki. It will emerge an empirical confirmation of what in *Section 1.1.5* that legislative recognition does not imply immediate realisation of human right of third generation as the HRHE; however, it plays a considerable role in its consolidation. A second section will examine the policy currently enacted at international, regional, and local (county) level, including their interactions and relationship with the civil society, which results a successful collaboration. Some issues will also emerge from the analysis of institutional attitudes and mechanisms, reinforcing the thesis of the necessity of an active engagement of the civil society.

This will be broken down in three clusters of analysis: organisations (NGOs and CSOs), individuals, and financial and business companies. Civil society organisations can be pivotal to the construction of HRHE, as they are able to catalyse knowledge and a structured action at local level directly engaging with the community, where the realisation actually happens. To do so, they implement specific operational activities, but also and most importantly social measures, that can guarantee ownership and durability of the technical initiatives studied to contribute to an effective consolidation over time. Cooperation with other entities, as for the institutional actors, can be fundamental and accelerate the process. Underlying the necessity for social measures is the fact that the single individual is the ultimate responsible for change when all the rest converges to sustain the process. This can entail neutrality and adaptation to a behavioural pattern alongside an evolving right, or even personally adding value through “active citizenship”, engaging in sensitisation, fights for justice, movements, volunteering, or donating. Financial support for the projects contribution to HRHE is also a relevant element: banking entities and the private sector emerge as a possible third actor of human rights building, giving ground for further research on their role and relation with the other two.

4.1 Building HRHE “from above”

4.1.1 *The necessity for institutional participation: the example of President Kibaki*

“Would you say that Kenya started rebuilding its environmental rights?

If yes, when did the process of resilience start?

When the new Constitution came in.

Ah, so 2010, right?

Yes. So when we had the new Constitution and a new president, President Mwai Kibaki, things started to change.

So the legal framework has a role.

Yes. So that's when they put in more policies to safeguard the environment, and to send people away from the forest. That's when we started regaining the Mao forest and things are beginning to improve now.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

The Constitution introduced in 2010 by the luminary and appreciated President Mwai Kibaki (2002-2013) marks a new era for the consolidation of the right to a healthy environment in Kenya. It is clear from the beginning of the document the considered centrality of the respect of the environment, by stating in the very Preamble that “[t]he people of Kenya” choose to adopt and enact the Constitution “respectful of the environment, which is our heritage, and determined to sustain it for the benefit of future generations”, and including a full chapter (V) dedicated to land, environment, and natural resource management. Then, in its Article 42, it explicitly establishes the right of every person to a clean and healthy environment, becoming one of the only one hundred Constitutions globally to formally recognise it:

“Every person has the right to a clean and healthy environment, which includes the right:

(a) to have the environment protected for the benefit of present and future generations through legislative and other measures, particularly those contemplated in Article 69; and

(b) to have obligations relating to the environment fulfilled under Article 70”.

(Republic of Kenya, 2010, Article 42)

The Article is in few lines very powerful: it recognises the eco- and anthropocentric perspectives of environmental rights and states the sustainability and intergenerational equity principles; through the reference to more specific and operational articles, it also establishes obligations for both the State and for individuals to cooperate with it to ensure environmental protection and sustainable development (Article 69)³⁴; last, it includes provisions for the legal enforcement of such a right (Article 70)³⁵, by allowing for the pursuit of justice on the matter and recognising the “polluter pays” principle. The Kenyan Supreme Court’s decision in the *Metal Refinery (EPZ) Ltd v. Owino Uhuru Residents* case constitutes a landmark ruling for the enforcement of these articles and principles: between 2007 and 2014, the Metal Refinery (EPZ) Ltd operated a lead-acid battery recycling plant adjacent to the Owino Uhuru settlement in Mombasa County, producing toxic waste in the surrounding environment, and contaminating the air, soil, and water; this pollution provoked severe health issues -with at least 20 reported deaths- among residents, who decided to file -led by the activist Phyllis Omido- a constitutional petition in 2016 against the company. After judgements before the Environment and Land Court (ELC) in 2020 and before the Court of Appeal in 2023, in December 2024 the Supreme Court took a final decision in favour of the applicants, establishing a KES 1.3 billion compensation for personal injuries and deaths, and a KES 700 million allocation for environmental restoration to be accomplished by the company (Mupita, 2025). The implications of the ruling are profound: first, it enforces the polluter pays principle and creates a fundamental precedent that responsibility for environmental damage cannot be evaded, which could act as a deterrent against ecologically unsustainable and population-harming behaviours. Besides fostering corporate accountability and compliance with sustainability standards, it also constitutes a precedent of judicial accountability for a concrete possibility to pursue and obtain environmental justice, likely encouraging similarly harmed communities to appeal to the Constitution’s Articles for cessation and

³⁴ These include, among others, “ensuring sustainable exploitation, utilisation, management and conservation of the environment and natural resources, and the equitable sharing of the accruing benefits; work to achieve and maintain a tree cover of at least ten per cent of the land area of Kenya; encouraging public participation in the management, protection and conservation of the environment; protecting genetic resources and biological diversity and eliminating processes and activities that are likely to endanger the environment” (Republic of Kenya, 2010, Article 69).

³⁵ “If a person alleges that a right to a clean and healthy environment recognised and protected under Article 42 has been, is being or is likely to be, denied, violated, infringed or threatened, the person may apply to a court for redress in addition to any other legal remedies that are available in respect to the same matter” (Republic of Kenya, 2010, Article 70(1)).

reparation of unfair behaviours. Also in Kisumu County, which is more rural than Mombasa, a case has been brought before the ELC claiming for a violation of Article 42 (*Olang & 18 others v. Lake Victoria South Water Works Development Agency Limited & 7 others* [KEELC 1320 (KLR)], 2024). The Court did not find merit in the Notice of Motion filed by the applicants, but the mere fact that the community mobilised before a tribunal to obtain justice in environmental matters is already a great result: it indicates awareness by the citizens of possessing such a right, and trust in the legal instruments and judicial institutions to enforce it.

Also Mr. Isaac Odhiambo (agribusiness expert, 45-50yo, The Green World staff) affirmed a change was witnessed after the introduction of the new Constitution: before 2010, policy implementation by the government was very slow and bribing was a common practice, making also the community respect for the environment and laws protecting it very poor. “So, this is why you find most of the community members are so reluctant: if you find someone clearing the forest or cutting a tree, once you've bribed the officer who was in charge, then you're just left and continue with the business” he told. The new Constitution imposed stricter measures, both in terms of environmental policy deriving by the obligations imposed by the new Articles (42, 69) and in terms of control of their enforcement, with severe punishment for corrupted officers (firing).

“So, this until 2010, whereby stringent measures have been put in place and whereby the government is strictly following the policies. So, you find the county government, that is devolved and is following the relevant ministries in county levels, making sure that the Constitution is implemented fully on the size of environment and also they make sure that the environment is conserved. The gazetted forests are taken good care of. There are a number of days you find the county governments are mobilizing the communities, are going to those forests and plant trees.

Okay. So, there was a change.

Yeah, there's a great change after 2010.”

(Mr. Isaac Odhiambo, agribusiness expert, 45-50yo, The Green World staff)

The change brought by this Constitution articulates in multiple facets: the legislative command to implement policies for environmental conservation, awareness of possessing a right to live in a healthy environment and judicial enforcement to promote environmental justice, and a transformation of the people's mindset towards nature. This latter element is highly important, as it allows for a spread and durable implementation of environmental protection and sustainability: as seen in *Chapter III*, individual behaviours can be harm and damaging, and correcting this attitude can prevent further degradation. Various policy were put in place by President Kibaki in this direction:

“Mwai Kibaki, he brought so many changes across the board, not only economically, but also the environment. There are so many changes that came in because of him.

For example?

That is when the plastics were stopped. There are so many things that came in, like he's the one who said: ‘no, people should move away from the forest’. Yes, he's the one who said people should be encouraged to plant more trees. So there was a policy that if you cut one tree, you must plant two.

[...] The other good thing he brought in was to lower the cost of fuel, like the cost of cooking gas, the cost of electricity. So when he lowered this, then people started to buy cooking gas. Normally, even me, I did not know. I had never seen a cooking gas, like I had never seen a cooking cylinder. I only saw the first cooking cylinder when I went to Nairobi in 2009.

Really?

Yes, so now when these things started to come in, then people stopped to cut down trees to make charcoal.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

President Kibaki at the head of the Republic and of the government from 2002 to 2013 has been a real turning point for the process building the human right to a healthy environment among the people of Kenya, reaching every region with concrete and durable change, both in terms of policy and of mentality. He boosted the awareness of the importance of sustainable household behaviours –as plastic consume, energy production–, of their practice and of reforestation, making the process survive the end of his mandate.

Another fundamental contribution of the President was to render schooling free and mandatory (penalty the imprisonment of the parents if a child was found not to go) with the *Primary Education Programme*, and charging only a small fee for university studies. According to Mr. Paul this has also brought a great change, generational awareness, knowledge and open-mindedness that was absent in such a spread way before. This came out in the moment he was telling me, as an agribusiness expert, about sustainable and still strategic agricultural techniques, and I asked him how these were not applied or know in the decades before. He replied that the possibility to study enlarged to the whole population, also in rural areas as those in Kisumu County, allowed for household to get to know about them and to employ them. Unfortunately, this Programme was not continued by the subsequent Presidents, and the number of pupils enrolled in primary school drastically dropped from approximately 200,000 in 2007 (Education Policy and Data Center) to 30,800 in 2020 (Ministry of Education, Kenya), with consequent drop in schooling prosecution absolute numbers. In cases as this one, the institutions can be the only in power to bring or trigger a concrete step forward in the concrete consolidation of a right. The other takeaway message from this testimonial is that in building processes of a human right education is they key: it constructs the open-mindedness and provides the means needed to every human to pursue that right construction for herself and the community. The institutions per se do not accomplish a new right in the moment they recognise it, and are not the subjects enabled to complete this realisation; nevertheless, they are fundamental and necessary, with legislation, enforcement, and policies, to allow for the individuals to do so. Absent or even opposite action can be highly dangerous: an example would be the political line of President Moi supporting deforestation to give a place for housing to the growing population in order to gain votes (refer to *Section 3.1.1.*).

The next section will critically examine the policies currently in place at local, national, and international level, with effect in Kisumu County, exploring their effectiveness in the process, their mutual relations and roles played.

4.1.2 Policies currently in place at local, national and international level

THE LOCAL GOVERNMENT

The County Government of Kisumu is deeply committed and active in the field of building environmental human rights, implementing a wide range of strategies spanning from long-term planning aimed at a healthy environment and an equitable development, to shorter-term measures designed to mitigate the consequences of the still unhealthy environment. In 2020, the county government issued Kisumu County Climate Change Act, establishing a Climate Change Action Plan and a County Climate Finance Framework for related purposes; in this context, ward committees were set up to oversee the activities, incorporating five community representatives (youth, marginalized gender, persons with disabilities, a climate change expert, and a CBO representative) to foster public participation, and embarked in numerous projects specifically and explicitly “designed to give Kisumu residents their right to a clean, healthy environment devoid of diseases” (County Government of Kisumu, 2023) and involving multi-sector partnership. In fact, it targets sustainability and health -in collaboration with Complex Urban Systems for Sustainability and Health-, but also water security with initiatives undertaken by the Water, Environment, Climate Change and Natural Resources department. The community was engaged in 2021 to individuate and discuss jointly environmental challenges within Kisumu County (emerging to be in that occasion decommissioned quarries and pollution problems) and outline lasting solutions, including sensitisation against single-use plastics. Another, among others, example of successful initiatives of the county is the Sustainable Energy Access and Climate Action (SEACAP) project working on increasing the access to clean energy. Under SEACAP, a youth group was involved to raise public awareness on proper solid waste management along with posing the requirement on the resident of the designated area to segregate their waste disposing it in the different bins and bags donated by the Covenant of Mayors of Sub-Saharan Africa. These and other projects are aimed at building a healthier environment and to drive a change in the society mindset and behaviour that can sustain the durability of the improvements brought. This is a perfect example of what “building a new human right” successfully means.

The county government is also taking decisive steps to mitigate climate change effects and to contrast environmental destruction in Kisumu: noteworthy is the action

undertaken, enforcing regulations, to actively tackle illegal sand harvesting, deforestation and wetland degradation, and ensure restoration and protection of sensitive ecosystems. The Ward Climate Change Planning Committees (WCCPCs) was launched with the purpose of identifying local climate risks and planning targeted adaptation and mitigation strategies, in line with the Kisumu County Climate Change Act 2020, leveraging on decentralisation and inclusive participation. Kisumu County Climate Change Adaptation Policy Framework, in fact, “draws attention to the principle of community-led adaptation and the centrality of locally relevant and appropriate climate adaptation measures” in order to enhance a “successful adaptation and resilience” (County Government of Kisumu, 2024). To provide a concrete example, in relation to the community’s acknowledgment of climate impacts on the rice irrigation scheme, the county launched the Ahero Rice Mill (recall Ahero is one of the main villages where data were directly collected on the field, in Nyando sub-county) supporting sustainable agro-industrial development with energy-efficient technologies and value-added production chains. It has also started a climate-smart-seeds distribution campaign, and invested in a data-driven decision-making through a comprehensive vulnerability assessment, that identifies high-risk zones and socio-economic groups most exposed to the effects of climate change, thereby enabling targeted planning and resource allocation (*ibidem*, 2025). In addition, Kisumu approach integrates mainstreaming principles to ensure that climate action is inclusive and equitable: gender mainstreaming, for example, has been prioritized through training programs for community leaders in places like Seme, empowering women and marginalized groups to participate in decision-making processes.

Considerably, the county government emerges as a winning model, in particular, in the study of a strategic building process of the human right to a healthy environment, thanks to its two pillars of public engagement focus and a multi-sectorial approach. In fact, without the aware and conscious participation of *the people*, that are those who provoke and/or suffer the *unhealthiness* of the environment, no lasting change would ever be possible; furthermore, given the multi-faceted nature of this right, multidimensionality is essential when dealing with it, in addressing both the root causes and the effects connected to the environment (e.g. household pollution, water accessibility, food security, agri-business and poverty, etc., recalling *Figure 22*).

“What do you think is the relationship between these dimensions?”

Water and Environment is an autonomous department. But they work closely with almost all the departments. In health, or when you go to agriculture, you'll find them; in trade, you're also going to find them. They work with all the departments.

But what do they do?

They must also do EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) for them. So they are everywhere. Their policies will touch on agriculture; their policies will touch on health; their policies will touch on education. / Do you see them at work? It's always you / (laughs). Whatever you do, they are there.”

(Ms. Quinter, staff of the County Government of Kisumu, 40yo, 12th Feb 2025)

Ms. Quinter, agricultural engineer working in the Irrigation Department of the County Government of Kisumu, spent strong words about the centrality of the community in the studied process:

“In building a human right to a healthy environment, who plays the major role? In general, among county departments and the community.

The community. I think the community plays a very big role.

Why?

It is us who are generating even the waste. It starts at the family level. So if these policies are instilled at the community, I think it starts. The people play the major roles at the community. We just assist them in doing the right thing.

But it's the community.”

This vision must be shared also at institutional level of the county, as it promotes not only community engagement, but also a wide range of initiatives to raise awareness about environmental conservation. It has established an “Environmental Day” to formalise its importance; the officers participate in television programmes and radio channels to reach families in promoting sustainability, but also visit schools to sensitise youths and children. They organise tree planting and care activities in schools and provide seeds to the students to encourage crops and tree planting in their households too, enhancing food security and reforestation from below. The institutions may plant a billion

trees, but without the people to take care, or at least not to cut or harm them over time, conscious of their preciousness for the health of both nature itself but also the population, the right would not be really built, it would break down in a little time: durability is key to realisation, and it cannot exist without the people ownership and substantial participation. A well-structured operational plan of action is outlined in the County Integrated Development Plan (CIDP), a five-year plan -currently at its third edition 2023-2027- that counties prepare to guide their development activities and public investment. The plan is designed through extensive public participation, involving citizens in identifying local needs and priorities. This “above-below” collaborative approach ensures that development initiatives reflect grassroots realities, fostering ownership, and transparency, as well as structured responsiveness to the diverse socio-economic and environmental challenges across the Kisumu territory. Ms. Quinter described:

“This is like a bottom-up approach, whereby the people of Kisumu, they tell us their challenges, their problems, and how they want us to solve their problems, the challenges. It comes *from down*. It is a policy that the community must be involved in their problems.

And how do you involve them?

Through planning, it's a participatory work. We don't just come with a project and say: ‘now we want to do this project’. The project must come from the community. What do they want? What problem do they have? How do they want to solve this problem? What are the interventions? In the interventions, this is where now we come in and assist them.”

The assessment of the previous CIDP cycle (CIDP II, 2017-2022) showed great achievements: access to safe water improved from 58% to 72%; tree cover was improved from less than 1% to 8.6 % through planting and nurturing of tree; one gabion and two dykes on rivers to protect against landfill flooding. Also in relation to food insecurity and poverty, connected to environmental issues, positive improvements were registered, with increases in agricultural production -maize, rice, cotton, cassava, and sweet potatoes-, in livestock production by 20%, and in fisheries by 10% (County Government of Kisumu, 2023). The CIDP participative strategy results to be a successful model to a build a lasting and sustainable right to live in a healthy environment.

THE NATIONAL GOVERNMENT

The national government also promotes environmental awareness and community engagement, with the similar modalities to the county employing media broadcasting, seeds distribution, households and schools greening activities. To address pollution problems, President Ruto has also enacted a ban on single-use plastics to reduce its consume and irresponsible waste -abandonment or even burning. The Government also issued and “World Environmental Day” on 5th June and a National Tree planting day on 13th November, occasion on which it distributes for free tree seeds and urges families and schools to plant them, in the effort to build on the whole national territory a healthy environment. It is also on the front line in case of environmental disasters as floods, providing the affected population with emergency rescue, bringing them into schools and fetching them food and water (refer to *Section 3.2.2.*), and works on disaster risk reduction (DRR) by sending field officers among the communities to share strategies to prevent disasters (Mr. Dilman).

“What does the [national] government do?”

The government, we have people in government who do sensitization on how to regain arable land, for example. So they usually have some programs. We have the Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture. This is a very good programme because it teaches the farmers how to better cultivate the land, in a sustainable way and also to get some money.

Are they free to access?

Yes.

And how do you do it? Like how do you apply?

Normally, okay, first there is a website for Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture where everybody can access the information. But again, we have groups. We have people who have been employed by the government. And we also have volunteers. So they go to the communities. We have one closer here in Ahero. I will link you to also one of them.” (but he never replied to his messages)
“He's the leader of Climate Smart Agriculture here.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

The Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project (KCSAP) is a Government of Kenya project jointly supported by the World Bank. KCSAP is being implemented over a five year period (2023-2027) with the objective to “increase agricultural productivity, enhance resilience and coping mechanisms to climate change risks in the targeted smallholder farming and pastoral communities in Kenya, and in the event of a crisis or emergency, provide immediate and effective response” (Republic of Kenya, 2017). Most of the initiatives of ownership of the national government regard mitigation and adaptation measures, rather than aimed at building a safe environment; this is important, but probably not enough in view of realising that right envisaged in Article 42 of the Constitution. Appreciable is instead the collaboration with communities, in view of what above.

The collaboration is tight throughout the whole vertical line of levels, not only the civil society but also the counties and international institutions. Ms. Quinter was explaining that the Counties governments do not have the financial resources to fund projects by itself, but receive resources by the national government or international organisations, and what county officers provide is skills and training. For instance, she worked with the Kisumu Water and Sanitation Company on an EU-funded project to support the Water Resource User Association on conservation of catchment areas. In this case, the funds were issued by the EU to the national government, which manages those finances and employs the county human resources to provide the technical knowledge and training necessary to community groups to actually implement the project. “This [project] is also a collaboration. [...] I was the one who was training the rowers on the conservation measures in the river” (Ms. Quinter, 12th February 2025).

Mostly, indeed, the national government acts as a bridge between the international and the local on two sides: the first is the incorporation and enforcement in the national legislative framework of legal provisions established at regional and international level (Mr. James Kiru, minister at the Permanent Mission of the Republic of Kenya to the UN and other IOs in Geneva, 10th March 2025); the second is the management of the funds received from international public institutions and their employment in collaboration with local governments and communities.

REGIONAL AND INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

The public institutions from the international panorama also play a role in the building of a right. As seen in *Chapter I*, this is the venue of the development of formal definitions, conceptualisations, discussions, of emerging new rights-to-be. After the formal recognition of the human right to a healthy environment in African regional framework in 1981 (African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, Article 24), more thirty-five states have included this right in their constitutions, with a peak of proliferation between the late '80s and the 2000s. While a direct correlation cannot be proved, the international recognition may have likely acted as a catalyst for normative proliferation in the African region at domestic level, by proving normative legitimacy and a concrete language example. Also subsequent formal recognitions at international levels, as the one in the 2022 UN resolution [A/RES/76/300] reinforce the legitimacy of the national provision, enhancing its enforceability and operational consolidation. It is essential to recall, though, that such recognition does not regard the *existence* of a new right, but rather a *claim* of it: it reflects the convergence of democratic transitions and environmental urgency emerged from the population, demanding for a sustainable and ecologically just future.

On the operational side, one of the ways international organisations contribute to the actual *realisation* of the right is by funding projects to be implemented on field; the EU and the World Bank are examples mentioned by the interviewed subjects. As explained in the previous lines by the words of Ms. Quinter, these organisations can provide financial resources for projects, prior approval, presented by the national government, which will employ the county human resources as technical support and the local communities to implement the project. Often, the organisations put conditions for the fruition of such resources: first and foremost, social and environmental impact assessment need to yield positive -or at least neutral- results. In the case of the initiative carried on by Ms. Quinter, for example, one condition was to have at least 50% of the involved participants to be women.

However, the role of donors is less played than what the public opinion might think.

The range of ways they provide support in the building of a right is wide, and financing is not even the predominant one. First, large of the action is regulatory, not only in terms of universal declarations about principles as mentioned above, but also in more substantial terms, holding negotiations among states or regional organisations to lead to agreements, policy frameworks or guidelines to be incorporated nationally (Mr. James Kiru, minister at the Kenyan Mission in Geneva). In order to support the process of implementation of those agreements and policies, multilateral organisations often deliver technical assistance and to build capacity: from an example of Mr. Kiru, the World Trade Organisation (WTO) had funded, together with the International Trade Center (ITC), a Joint Integrated Technical Assistance Programme in charge of helping governments to find gaps in their national laws, pieces that need to change or be integrated to comply with IOs or regional regulations, and propose amendments. IOs also act as ‘conveners’, in the words of Mr. Reuben Wambui -expert in green finance-, creating a network framework for different stakeholders to meet and cooperate: one example from his experience in UNEP was that the organisation acted as a third-party connecting UNEP FI (Financial Initiative), producing principles for responsible banking, and the banks interested in this sustainable finance. Also, they can act as global monitoring bodies and standard setters, “because as a multilateral body, you're able to do like some global estimates and tracking. And then based on those statistics, people can make investment decisions” (Mr. Reuben, 26th March 2025, Geneva). When working as a consultant in UNCTAD, he was asked to help in the production of a SDG investment trend monitoring, and me myself, when working at the Italian Mission at the UN in Geneva, was tasked with the analysis and summary redaction of the reports produced by UNCTAD to transmit them to Rome. Reporting, analysing, setting objectives and possible policies is largely an activity of international organisations, together with providing technical assistance and capacity building to national governments in order for them to develop and implement successfully specific strategies for their peculiar situations and needs.

In the context of the aid received from international organisations, this *capacity building* approach appears to be successful and strategically aimed to build a lasting right, as it does neither entail just the donation of a sum of money with risk of dispersion or misallocation, nor a “dismissive and temporary” solution to the effects of not enjoying a healthy environment (e.g.: delivering water to the population without solving the problem

of not being able to get it autonomously from the environment): it is positive that it aims at building the *capacity* to own that right (recall Sen's capabilities as essential element for an actual fruition of a right). It hasn't always been this way: according to Brian and other respondents, there has been a shift in mentality and approach of the international aid, away from a "giving pattern". According to them, the previous mechanism of just giving money to the government was useless and ineffective, due to the high levels of corruption diffused in the Kenyan institutions.

4.1.3 Shortcomings and issues within institutional actions

Corruption is one of the main issues hampering a fair use of resources for the sake of truly and committedly building a sustainable right to a healthy environment.

From what I know, from Europe we are also sending money, right?

Not to the rural communities.

Do you know who does this money go to? The government?

All the money collected goes to the government. Then the government put it in the line ministries. But I want to tell you, with corruption, this money is being diverted. It's either diverted to somebody's pocket, or not used properly.

(Mr. Moses, 35-40 yo, Farmer and permaculture expert, Red Cross staff)

Among the population, especially that from rural areas, corruption is unanimously perceived as one of the most severe obstacles to a fair use of resources and efficient implementation of strategic policies: it has been addressed by Samuel and Elisabeth as the main problem in Kenya to its development, and it was alleged by them, but also Nancie, Brian, Mr. Paul and Mr. Moses, that if any money is being provided by international organisations or by the African Union, they do not arrive to the community. Another form of corruption passes through the aiding and abetting by the government of multinational corporations activities that ignore sustainability or even damage the environment and its social fruition, just for the sake of business and country enrichment. One concrete example is the favourable or even just neutral attitude of the presidency towards the Coca Cola company, which not only hampers the ban on plastic policy, but also holds the

monopoly of water in the Kenyan territory, unfairly using a huge quantity of it while the population struggles to get some and establishing the price of water itself; just think that most of Kenyans are more used to drinking Coca-Cola than water, given its lower price and higher availability. Recently, was telling Mr. Moses, President Ruto allowed licences to companies that for their business are cutting trees. Another example is that the Kenyan territory, included Kisumu County, is rich of gold mines and places to refine oil, but the people do not possess the means and the knowledge to leverage this resources; the government gives the procurement of those areas to foreign and high-paying companies, especially from China, who unfairly exploit resources and even sell them back at high prices to the population; “that sounds like a joke” ironically commented Brian with anger.

“Again, it is a problem because it is a political affair. Like, for example, in north-east, we have oil pipes that are passing to other countries. North-east is purely dry. Then, we were now asking, why is it that they can pass oil pipes but cannot pass pipes of water from those countries to come and help people in northeastern? So, you realize that their politics is there.”

A different opinion emerges from respondents with a different social and working background: Ms. Quinter, Mr. Isaac, Mr. Reuben, and even Mr. Dilman (who is a teacher in Nairobi before than an NGO staff member) contended that corruption is almost absent in the Kenyan institutions. One reason is according to Ms. Quinter that given that funds would be cut by international organisations if they found them to be misused, the government is discouraged to misallocate them; it might be a more common phenomenon among contractors, but the anti-corruption policy, where anybody is entitled to report any suspect, is severe and a person would lose her job if caught to be corrupted, which also discourages the practice. A common ground between the two perspectives might be deduced by Mr. Isaac words, who was telling that with the new Constitution more stringent measures were introduced to tackle corruption: probably, corruption *has* been a real and significant obstacle to development, especially as the trend of action of IOs was a money-giving pattern, but it has changed to the present day due to provisions against it. Another meaningful technique to fight it, notified by Mr. James, is the digitalisation of national services and procedures, which guarantees more transparency and forces a higher accountability, audit and reporting.

Another shortcoming of the institutional action, even admitted the transparency of the government and a full and efficient implementation of the policies, is the nature of those policies: most of them operate only on the *consequences* of the currently unhealthy environment, with too little effort aimed at building an enduringly healthy one addressing its root factors. In fact, it operates mostly through mitigation measures, copying mechanisms to climate change, and emergency rescue after disasters, which build resilience, but not a substantial right to live in a healthy environment. On the side of disaster risk reduction (DRR), which could potentially give a positive contribution, the government enlightens people on ways to prevent disasters through field volunteering officers, informed Mr. Dilman, but “sometimes they are not working. They only start working when a disaster happens. That's when they come to the ground and start enlightening people”: too late. The action on environmental restoration and conservation is there, but not enough. Seeds are distributed, yes, but only once a year (Nancie, Badilisha CIVS staff); advocacy and sensitisation are essential, but not sufficient without resources and projects to put those principles in practice; CIDP is a great model of participative and constructive strategy, but remains an exception in the domain of policies, especially national ones. In addition, monitoring and enforcement of potentially strategic policies is often too low to yield any effective change. This is the case of the ban on single-use plastics issued by the current President Ruto: not only plastic waste is still abandoned and burnt, and companies as Coca Cola exercise lobbying against it, but single-use plastics (as bags and bottles) are imported by small merchants from the neighbouring Uganda, nullifying the legal provision's purpose. Similarly, the law establishes to plant two trees per each tree that is cut, but nobody checks that this is done, and in fact households tend not to respect it.

Low monitoring, however, is not the main drawback of the enforcement problem, but the one that reveals the core of this policy ineffectiveness: the lack of people's ownership. Ownership is a fundamental factor to guarantee a lasting effect, because if the members of a community believe in the purpose of a provision, share its principle and objective, then at that point will be committed to respect and implement it. Otherwise, unless the monitoring is so tight and the punishment severe enough to discourage non-compliance, people will find a workaround. Also a tight monitoring, though, without agreement to the policy would not be a correct path: first, is not sustainable over time,

given the political turnover, and would not be democratic. Ownership is one key. Mr. Moses raised an interesting issue related to this topic, about the law being written in English only constituting a language barrier for people in rural areas, and impeding its shareability and consequent commitment. A premise the reader should be acknowledged about to better understand this argument, is that English and Kiswahili are the official languages of the Kenyan state, but 42 are the counties and the relative tribal language actually spoken commonly. To talk with people across counties Kiswahili is employed, while the use of English is usually limited to high school and formal venues.

“Legislation in my opinion is really lacking. And it should be communicated in a language that the local people can understand. It should not be in English.

Why shouldn't it be in English?

Not everybody in Kenya understands Kiswahili and English. There are some who are understanding the local language. So those legislations should be put in the local language where mama was not going to school, was not educated.

Yes, of course. And she also, I think she also works in the land.

I can read and say: ‘okay, this works’.

So it would be needed that legislation was translated in tribal languages?

It should be in the local vernacular languages.

And how should it reach the people? Like television, newspaper, radio?

For the majority of people on radio.”

(Mr. Moses, 35-40 yo, Farmer and permaculture expert, Red Cross staff)

What emerges overall by the present study, is that ownership of the cause, the feeling of necessity for change, the sincere will to build that healthy environment, are essential to the realisation of a right, recalling from *Chapter I* that it is a *social construct* (Waters, 1996). Where a right, in order to consolidate concretely and durably, is to be built “from below”, this does not imply that the institutions –“the above”– have no role, which we have seen to be false. An element that is appears to be lacking at the moment is policies that can allow the population to have the *means* to autonomously build that right, to accelerate the process. Education is the first and most indispensable means to do this. When President Kibaki issued and enforced the Free Education Programme, the government contributed to grow educated and open minds, who in fact now have the

mindset to bring that necessary change in the environment health to also get to enjoy its benefits and human rights entailed (Mr. Paul, 3rd October, Ahero). Education does not only provide open-mindedness, but the very technical instruments and knowledge to operate substantially, for instance, knowing which trees to plant to reverse soil erosion. Mr. Paul, just before my interview, was studying a new method to grow plants faster by propagating fruit seeds cuttings, developing the idea from some insights he got from YouTube. Internet is an incredibly powerful means to build capacity and provide technical assistance, and it would be a good policy by the government to provide free or low-fee connection to the whole territory. Here, instead, Mr. Paul had enough money, differently from most of his fellow villagers, to afford a personal 10GB “Safaricom” (sim card) worth 2,000 shillings; until sometime before, it was the NGO to provide Wi-Fi in the office. The government should provide these means, and enact policies that might be apparently disconnected from environment action, but are actually fundamental.

“[t]o use in cooking *ugali* (typical Kenyan dish), I cannot give you flour every day, but I can give you seeds and a *jembe* (a mattock)”.

(Brian, 27yo, CIVS volunteer and CBO staff)

4.2 Building HRHE “from below”

4.2.1 Organisations (NGOs):

Civil society organisations –as associations, foundations, and NGOs most of all– represent one of the most structured ways of building a right “from below”. This because in the chain of the construction process, they are the first ring of organised action that is encountered by the community, which is the main actor of change, hence they can directly receive from it, engage with it in concrete policy enactment, and intermediate with higher level bodies (county and national government, international organisations). They are the main implementer of effective policies.

TECHNICAL MEASURES

The technical measures deployed by NGOs respond to the needs of the community, which in the field of environmental security in Kisumu County mainly relate to the difficulties implied by the irregularity of rains, severe droughts, and destructive floodings. Therefore, the first urges of the community are ways to survive these troubles and make it through them: “More water is the key”, “[...] if just we could get a borehole of drilling water...” (Elisabeth and Samuel, Katolo). Boreholes are one of the most effective copying mechanisms to get clean water, both during drought periods when it cannot be found in streams or from rains, and when it floods and remains dirty. For this reason they are much desired among the villages and are provided by NGOs and donors when possible. Their shortcoming is that the financial cost of build and maintaining their system is very high (on average around USD 2 million just to drill for example), and they require significant levels of electric energy to pump the water up, which renders them requiring a huge financial effort, hence difficult to undertake and to sustain over time. The borehole in the Ahero CIVS Resource Centre, for example, which Nam (CIVS local volunteers staff) showed me during our interview was not working that day, as the solar panels they had installed to get electric energy were broken since some months, and electric wires were not working that day. Consequently, the women who had come to fetch water had to leave and look for some elsewhere. The other borehole in the Centre was completely dismissed, after a couple of years of activity. In the Kuth Awendo Resource Centre, which was our basecamp, we also had one, new and functioning, and students were coming every day

with big watering cans to get water, for free, for them and for their families. When operative, it is a great instrument and help for the community. Other measures enacted to deal with water scarcity or low quality are the construction of dams, dykes and gabions to contain flood water, filters to clean it and make it usable, or pools to collect heavy rain. In the CIVS Resource Centre in Badilisha, on Lake Victoria, they were filtering and collecting the lake water and giving free access to it to every member of the community.

Figure 23. On the left, the dismissed borehole in Ahero CIVS Resource Center; on the right, the students coming every morning to the Kuth Awendo Resource Center to fetch water to their schools.

Another method to cope with the environmental and related problems of the area is to adapt crops and trees planted: cassava, for example, can be cultivated in households, as it is a highly energetic but drought-resistant edible tuberous, to ensure a source of food also during unexpected dry periods; some species of trees are able to resist to floods, slowing their stream and impact, as well as avoiding further erosion of the soil; to mitigate the effects of climate change, the growth of new maize varieties that mature earlier (adapting to the lately higher temperatures), and the use of greenhouses, which allow to cultivate crops regardless of the temperature outside, are a good stratagem. CIVS employs experts to inform and educate the community on these strategies, to enhance food, water and housing security, put in danger by the unhealthy environment. Also, they develop programmes of agribusiness aimed at empowering the population to get some income from their farming activities, as well as ICT courses to increase the possibilities of finding an alternative job, to fight the poverty trends that come with droughts. A free-of-fees primary school and kindergarten were also built in Kuth Awendo and Ahero for the children of families who could not afford one.

All of these provisions respond to urgent needs of the population against droughts, floods, rains irregularity, climate change, pollution, but do not tackle the roots of these problems. They remain necessary, because while working for eliminating them, it cannot be denied or neglected that these environmental issues actually exist at the moment, hindering the enjoyment of a vast range of human rights (*Figure 22*). While indispensable, they are yet insufficient: they do not *per se* contribute to build a *human right to a healthy environment*. A successful action, whereby the mission of the organisation is “to improve the quality of life and the environment” (Victoria Fresh NGO, Nyando, refer to *Figure 5*.) or similar, cannot avoid designing measures aimed at operating on the roots of the issues, consolidating that right on the long-term, and in a durable and sustainable way.

The first of these measures, among the NGOs operating on Kisumu County territory –CIVS Kenya, The Green World, Victoria Fresh, CBO, to mention those I got to know personally– is tree planting. The benefits of tree planting, already exposed in the previous chapters, are numerous and essential: they nourish the cycle of water, providing regular patterns of rain, mitigate the temperature of the air and yield shade to workers and students when it’s hot, they protect against floods and keep the soil stable and full of nutrients, provide fruits and food. “Tree is life, environment is life” said the principal of one of the schools we visited (field notes, RAE school, 1st October 2024). I was impressed

Figure 24. Tree planting activities in schools, in active collaboration with the students.

by his speech full of gratitude towards the organisation of Victoria Fresh, that had planted in the previous years a considerable number of trees in the school, and completely transformed the area according to the principal; now the students were able to get some fruits during the day and to have classes outside in the drier months.

“You know, doing something little can have a very big impact.

Very small, little things; like, I made this tree, a small tree. It will grow big and then somebody will be seated in the shade.” (Mr. Moses, CIVS and Red Cross)

Besides actively planting trees in the main spaces of the village as schools, churches and hospitals, and promoting initiatives to raise awareness, CIVS and other local NGOs also distribute seedlings for free. In fact, they do organic farming within their centres (growing a “model farm”), produce autonomously a sustainable compost with the organic residuals, and use it to fill the seed beds of the seedlings they will deliver; they usually distribute them twice a year, in correspondence (as much as possible) with the two rain seasons (field notes). I experienced the whole process in first person: within the core tasks of my volunteering experience in CIVS Kenya was included exactly to help the organisations with the production of these seedlings, nourishing rich tree nurseries of different plants (*Figure 26.*), and we had to be trained on that in order to learn how to do it properly.

Figure 25. Left and centre pictures are the tree seedlings of the tree nursery of the Victoria Fresh organisation. The picture on the right shows the seed beds prepared by the students of the Ahero primary school.

SOCIAL MEASURES

The immediate measure implementation alone is not enough to ensure contribution to the right to a healthy environment consolidation. Recalling its nature as right of third generation (*Section 1.2.2.*), measures that build it are ‘programmatic’, yielding effect only in the long-run, reason why both the effort and the results shall be durable and sustainable over time. This entails that they cannot stem out from a political decision or single act, as seen above: the recognition in the Constitution is not enough; implementation of measures without continued ownership and participation of the community is not effective; planting a tree without taking care of it will be useless. For these reasons, the projects implemented to build a healthy environment need to include effective “social measures”, that are those which involve the collective management of the technical measures seen above. To study them in the process of the right’s consolidation, they will be investigated aspects as the ownership (who decided and designed the measure), the participation (how the community was involved in the project implementation), equal accessibility (to such participation and to the benefit of the right), the impacts (environmental and social sustainability), the durability (how efforts and effects are held sustainable over time), the monitoring (how it is ensured that the measures are implemented, correctly, and not obstructed), the avoidance of free riding attitudes (awareness of the problematic and need for action).

“Who decides to start that project and why?”

We do a bridge assessment. When I was new in CIVS in 2018, we visited this region, and we met Isaiah” (the community chief). “We met Isaiah in some old school and then we started to host community meetings. And then they told us that they would like to have a resource center. Then we were asking them, ‘do you have land? Do you have this? Are you willing to donate land? Are you willing to do this? Then we asked them, which project do you want?’ They told us ‘we want a kindergarten for children.’ ”

So you ask directly to the community.

Yes. And after we have that information, then we go to look for partners.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

As in the CIDP county government plan, the design of the project starts from a dialogue with the community. This is a positive feature, to gain the local knowledge of the problem suffered, the needings and urges of the people. At the same time, taken alone and without a critical analysis, it may not contribute to build a right, as it often happens that immediate needs only are asked to be dealt with (e.g. provide a borehole). The answer of the population is to be inquired deeply to find the underlying root cause of the real problem and design parallel programmatic measures that operate on it while alleviating the manifest negative effects in the present. For example, opening a kindergarten, as it has then been done by CIVS in its resource centres in Kuth Awendo and Ahero, responds to the need of mothers to have the time to work in the fields. An investigation of why these mothers need to work in the fields (food security? poverty?), how they do it (sustainably or intensively? Efficaciously or wasting resources?), operating for long-term solutions to the underlying difficulties, is to be considered and discussed back with the community. It emerged, by confronting proposals and feasibility, that those women were using synthetic fertilisers to yield harvest more quickly (not aware that it was impoverishing the soil and polluting the products), and that they would have found useful trainings on better agricultural practices. This is how the *ownership* of the actions of a project aimed at building a right to a healthy environment is developed, where without ownership it cannot be guaranteed commitment to carry on the cause durably.

Awareness of the problem, of the solutions, and how to implement them correctly is the other necessary factor. For this reason, CIVS and the other local NGOs organised seminars and meetings in the communities to yield information to the population. Tree planting in the main communal spaces of the villages also has the aim of raising awareness about its importance. With this purpose, the project designed by CIVS also envisaged the creation of a flyer (*Figure 25.*) informing about the main environmental problems of the area and behaviours that could contribute to stop the harm and build a healthy environment for the future, to be then distributed to the students in the visited schools with the hope of informing both the growing youths and their families.

Figure 26. Flyer about environmental problems and solutions of Kisumu territories, to be distributed in schools.

When the people get knowledge of the terrible impact that some practices as cutting trees, using synthetic fertilisers, or burning waste and sugarcane residuals, have on the environment and -in the bigger picture- to their own lives, then they become willing to live in a healthy environment, to claim a right to it, and to get knowledge and means to actively participate to realise it. Information and education empower to think critically, claim, act. They develop individual and pure ownership of the will and actions to build that right, for themselves; it is a broader and more complete kind of ownership, as it regards the whole cause, and not only an NGO project: it will ensure individual committed everyday action, and here lies the core of the consolidation process of a new human right.

Education is freedom, education is power.

When visiting the schools, distributing and explaining the flyers, and planting the trees in the garden, the students are always actively engaged: this reinforces awareness, but also the skills on how to plant. Indeed, children in rural Kenya learn how to dig, plant seeds and water them since little age, as they are often involved in farming activities at home, but there is always something that can be learnt either practically or ideologically. Their participation to the tree planting activities contributes to creating a sense of belonging to a community that wants to create a healthy environment, pursuing this mentality also at home and in the future; it teaches how to take care of the environment and the responsibility to do so, building the survival of those trees over time and the possibility that they can yield their positive effects over time. “For a plant to grow, you need care” (Nancie, CIVS Badilisha, 28th September, field notes). Even at school the kids are taught how to do and maintain seed beds (Figure 26., right picture). The focus on the

education of the kids and youths, who will make the world of tomorrow, is a key element for the durability of a measure and for allowing an autonomous continuation of a right's consolidation process.

Participation and education, however, are not limited to the school students, but extend to adults and whoever needs it or asks for it, as it is especially by women and persons with disabilities (Mr. Paul). What renders their programmes successful is that each initiative is not finishing in the moment a tree is planted, or a seed is donated: the very main activity of the organisations, in fact, is *teaching* and *training*. Every person can be educated on how to reproduce in the correct form these good practices at home, how to take care of the plants, and has the possibility to demand for assistance in whatever moment. People do not passively receive, but actively participate, learn and replicate. Mr. Paul (3rd October 2024, Ahero CIVS Resource Center) was telling that training sessions are organised on a group or individual base, according to the number of people that daily asks for teaching (to provide some numbers, since 2021 he alone has trained more than 1,200 farmers). He will explain them theory and strategies for a sustainable agriculture, show them and let practice in the model farm of the Resource Centre, aiming at giving the community the *means* and *capabilities* to build their wanted right by themselves. CIVS Kenya carries on a “model farm” in each one of its centres across the county, where the members of the community can freely go to observe and learn sustainable agricultural techniques, take inspiration, or ask questions. This also has an encouraging effect, by giving the example, to employ the correct practices. One of the other core tasks of us volunteers was to work, each morning, at the Resource Center farm, digging new raised beds, planting vegetables, fruit trees, cutting the grass, propagating stevia (*Figure 27*).

Figure 27. The CIVS volunteering team work in the Kuth Awendo model farm.

In the view of being a model, and minimise environmental negative impacts of their projects, the organisation is also always looking for more sustainable methods to be implemented and shared; now, for example, they are trying to find alternatives to the plastic bags used for the seedlings, and whenever the funds renders it possible they try to implement renewable energy production system, investing in solar panels. This is to both enhance the energy delivery to the community, and to promote sustainable energy generation methods. The one in Ahero is an example, despite it is currently not working and the financial resources are not enough to fix it. Probably, in this kind of field, it would be needed a more structured action with more access to funds, run by public institutions.

Funds constraint constituted in the case of CIVS projects the only source of limitation of accessibility to their services, as in the case of the broken solar panels not allowing the functioning of the borehole and impeding the women to access water. Otherwise, boreholes (Kuth Awendo, Ahero, Awasi) and filtered water (Badilisha) are accessible in any moment for free or a minimal fee (5 shillings in Kuth Awendo); the kindergarten and primary school in the resource center are free and available for any family who cannot afford private or public schools (Mr. Dilman, field notes); ICT and agribusiness courses are joinable by whoever registers to it (Brian, field notes); in whatever moment people can go to the organisation and ask for seeds or seedlings, or go to the model farm to look how things are done, what they yield, and eventually ask for information, technical advice, or training (Nam, field notes, 3rd October, Ahero).

“Mostly I always do like, in a day, two, two and a half hours. One hour is for theory, with the board; then another one and a half hours are just practical, which means we walk around by explaining this and this.

And that training is enough or they will need to come back after?

Enough. Some people, one may come, if they have questions, they can come back, say ‘oh, what did you say about this?’ ‘Oh, this and this’. Yeah, I always say that I'm free. Anytime you can call me, anytime you can visit me.”

(Mr. Paul, 40-50yo, agribusiness expert, working for CIVS in Ahero)

When I asked him who were the categories of people joining the most their activities he replied that is “mostly women, young guys and the disabled”, and for specific reasons: men usually need to work elsewhere or are already into farming, so do not ask for training (even if sometimes they would probably need to, to learn more sustainable practices); person with disabilities are often “neglected. We say that, no, disability is not inability, you can do something”; women instead, as are those in charge of the nourishment of the family, are happy to learn farming practices to grow some crops at home, especially when facing droughts –“when it's drought there's no *sukuma wiki*, the kales (common vegetable in the Kenyan diet, mentioned here in Kiswahili and then in English) is not around; so, maybe they [usually] have to walk far to get it, but if they can have it at home it's more advantage for them” (Mr. Paul). In the projects promoted by the county government women participation is often “required” by the funding organisation, and to ensure the activities are actually accessible to them, the implementer officers intercede with the chief of the village, “so that the women who are not really involved in these projects are involved. And with capacity. Even their partners are told the reason why they need to involve the women.” (Ms. Quinter) She added:

“When you train women, *women are mostly ambassadors of change*, right from the family level. Even from their children. Who are going to initiate these things that they want in their children when they are young? It is the women.”

The attention to the involvement and accessibility of women to the tools and capabilities to pursue environmental sustainability is fundamental in this territory, as they are in charge of taking care the family and of growing the adults of tomorrow, so they can equip them with open-mindedness and capacity to continue the process of building their right to live in a healthy environment.

Accessibility to the services provided is fundamental, because otherwise any effort would be useless; for this reason, organisations employ many different methods to reach as many persons as possible: they do mobilisations among the village through their volunteers, seminars held by their experts, campaigns and calls on social media, and often receives new members by referral.

Monitoring is another fundamental social measure that is essential to build right, besides the success of a single project. On the lines of the importance of taking care, maintain the services in function, and give continuity to immediate measures, monitoring results fundamental, to avoid inefficiency, negligence, or unconscious errors. In the case of CIVS activities, this is fundamental especially in the case of checking on the care of the trees planted in the community and of the seedlings given to households.

“What about your monitoring systems? For example on the seedlings you give to households? How do you know they are actually growing them?”

Yeah first, we train them on how to do it, how to manage and how to protect them. Then if you provide them with the seedlings, I will do like monitoring which means I have to go and look if they are doing something.

Physically?

Yeah, not by phone. (laughs) I have to walk around and see are they doing it exactly what I tell them. Because not all are perfect. Some are just going back but you have to tell them ‘no this is how it should be’.

And how many times a year?

If I go once, I can go back again, so maybe I go like three times.

Per household? Yeah. And how are they good or not in your opinion?

Yeah some are good, but also I can say because most of them are mothers, so it's just like ‘wow it's like my mom, I have to help her’.

It's not like penalty but more teaching.

It's good also because you learn.”

(Mr. Paul, 40-50yo, agribusiness expert, working for CIVS in Ahero)

It is not only a check on the peculiar behaviour of the beneficiaries that needs monitoring by the NGO members, but also the whole activity of the organisation that has to be checked in its sustainability and appropriateness by the local authorities. Mr. Dilman was explaining that immediately after talking with the community at the start of a project, they involve the sub-county government officers, to ask for their advice and support.

“And what do you talk about? You go like ‘hi, we would like to make this project because we know there is this problem’?”

Yes, and then we ask them ‘what do you think? what is your advice? do you think this is a good project for this?’. We also do this so that you can have goodwill from the local government. Because the local government has to support your project. If they don't support it...

Sorry, you mean monetary or morally?

They have to support it by monitoring. And also by making sure that it is moving on well and maybe providing security or something of the sort. Otherwise if you just do a project without involving them, it will backfire. It will not happen. Even if it's construction of something, it will reach somewhere, and they will block it.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

To ensure accessibility, participation, and durability of an action aimed at building a healthy environment, it is necessary also to confront with the institutions. This can also enhance the quality of the project, more structure and coordination, hence more efficaciousness. The relations that civil society organisations establish both with public authorities and among them are very tight, and functional to the process of consolidation of a right, and will be hence investigated in the next paragraphs.

COOPERATION WITH OTHER ENTITIES

As it emerges from Mr. Dilman’s words, confrontation with the institutions is necessary in order for civil society organisations to work properly. Local NGOs and CBOs have to be registered by the government and obtain a certificate before starting their activities on the territory, and any project has to be presented and approved to be put in place, for a number of benefits. It will certify the project’s constructive objectives and methods of work, as it has to pass the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) and show how it is thought to yield positive effects on environmental and social aspects. It will ensure compliance, transparency and accountability of the organisation, as its activities will be monitored by the government, and will have to respond of their actions and investments; on the other side, it will allow the organisation to work undisturbed, as having the project approved and going on properly, it will not be obstructed (Mr. Dilman).

Knowing what is already being done by the side of the civil society will allow to avoid duplication with initiatives of the government (Ms. Quinter), for example CIDP, and to maximise a good resources allocation with this coordinated and multistakeholder approach. Also, the government, at its various levels (national, county, sub-county) may decide to support the very same organisations; examples are providing the seeds to be distributed in form of seedlings to the community (Nancie), offering trainings and skills by sending their experts in the field or organising seminars (Ms. Quinter), or they might enhance the credibility and trust of the organisation at the eyes of the community by cooperating or advocating through ministerial or other high-level figures. The relation between local organisations and the public institutions is tight and empirically fruitful, whereby the more active is their cooperation, the more can an action aimed at building right be structured and lasting. Territorial NGOs are the subject that the community feels closer and more active in building their rights and in helping them to mitigate the issues of the current situation. This does mean that the government is not doing anything or can refrain from it: while local associations are indispensable as they actually are the closest form of organised action and which directly engages with the community, coordination with the public institutions is equally necessary in order to enhance that action, and allow all the positive aspects above.

A number of NGOs operating territorially in the sectors of main interest is hence necessary, and it also common to be there. The Nyando sub-county, for example, with a community of around 20-24,000 people, is served by 3/4/5 local organisations, where one concentrates on the environment (CIVS), one on education, one on health, and another couple (Mr. Moses). As they operate in different fields of community needs, they do not interact a lot, but may collaborate in case any cross-cutting issue raises.

Big NGOs operating nationally mostly engage in mitigation or emergency measures in the territory of Kisumu. ActionAid Kenya, for example, is active in 22 counties of the nation included Kisumu, with projects aimed at building the power of the community, especially women living in poverty and exclusion, and at achieving economic security and leadership while promoting land rights, sustainable livelihoods, access to public services, and the defence of civic space in face of social, political, and climate challenges (ActionAid International Kenya, n.d.). Big NGOs, given their higher resources and

configuration, are able to yield a more structured impact over a wider territory than a local one, reproducing their projects in different regions and learning from each previous experience. However, they tend to operate more on the side of the effects of not being enjoying a right to a healthy environment, mitigating its consequences from climate change or of poverty, and building on rights (e.g. right to land) to cope with food insecurity and violence issues. Their action can be helpful to secure the population while a healthy environment is not achieved yet, and even to accelerate the process to obtain, but it is not sufficient *per se* to construct the right discusses in the present paper. Other organisations as the Red Cross instead, directly operate on the rescue side of extreme weather events and disasters, working in humanitarian aid rather than development.

“Like Kenya Red Cross, these are a big organization. They work for emergencies. I decided to become a member because I realized that during the time of floods people really suffer. So, through their capacity building trainings, they train us. Maybe when somebody is drowning, I can save a life.

Of course. Like really emergency measures to save lives.

Yeah, like emergency measures to save lives. During those emergencies, they also do some distributions: they come and give food, plant hospital beds,...

(Mr. Moses, 35-40 yo, Farmer and permaculture expert, Red Cross staff)

However, they may also provide training and expertise on specific matters, as done with Brian when designing a project to control soil erosion in the village of Nyakatch: “So what I did: I did a small research on soil erosion control and measures. And I had to look for specialists from Kenya Red Cross. They came and helped me to understand the topography of the land; then what would be the best solution for us” (30th September 2024).

International NGOs have a tighter relation with local ones, especially when they share the same or connected mission and vision. Usually, international ones cooperate with local ones to implement a project on the territory, exchanging knowledge and support, or provide material and mostly human resources to implement projects designed locally, in form of experts or volunteers (or volunteering experts). This is the case of IBO Italia, an Italian NGOs which collaborates with other European NGOs to select volunteers, as it was my case, to send to CIVS for the implementation of their projects on

the territory of Kisumu. Aurora from the IBO Italia staff (10th Jan 2025) was explaining that they found CIVS Kenya on the ESC (European Solidarity Corps) portal for humanitarian aid organisations, read their project and found it matching their values and their mission to involve youths to be active in society, under the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA) of the European Commission, by which they get the funds to finance their proposals. They entered in touch with CIVS, confronting on what they needed and on how IBO Italia could have contributed to those needs, ultimately reaching a point of efficient cooperation for the common mission. The pattern of organisations of the same nature from the world North and South collaborating directly together for development, with funds of mixed provenience (public, private), has been indicated by the expert in development project management Javier Schunk (7th April 2025) in a lecture at the Italian Institute for International Politics Studies (ISPI) as the methodological approach of international cooperation of the future, called “global social innovation”. This consists in a bottom-up model, whereby the final project is elaborated and implemented *jointly* between North and South, investigating the problem on the ground and starting from it to build the collaboration on the basis of what each can do to contribute to enhance the reached objective, as IBO Italia and CIVS did. The innovation of this model is embedded in the fact that up to recent times the tendency in international cooperation approaches was to gather among donors and public funds a sum of money to be sent directly to local NGOs or to buy material to be delivered in the field for immediate aid measures (e.g. boreholes), but without elaborating a common and structured strategy for an impact on the long-term. As for international IGOs, the tendency of Northern NGOs to employ a “giving pattern” has lately been dismissed.

“Do you think that it can be harmful in a way, this giving pattern that international organization have -I mean if they give and don't teach-? Can this be harmful or is it still better than nothing?”

In the past we used to be happy of receiving the support from them, but now we say ‘if you give me and you don't teach me, how am I going to do without you? It's equal to nothing. So, it's better for the international organizations to teach us, to teach how they get so that we also learn how to get like them, so that even if you give me I also know how I can do it without your presence.”

(Brian, 27yo, CIVS volunteer and CBO staff)

4.2.2 *Individuals: active citizenship*

COMMON CITIZENS

What emerges clearly from the results above is that individuals are the main actor of the process of building a right to a healthy environment that can last over time: the people of the community are those who need to know how to run everyday activities (as farming, housing, or energy production) in a sustainable way, how to take care of the environment they are living in (as planting trees and maintaining them); privates are those at the head of corporations who can decide to run the company in a sustainable way without polluting or exploiting the resources; those at the head of government units take the most structured decisions by legislative and executive acts. Informed knowledge, awareness of the problem and solutions, ownership of the cause, and the possession of means and capabilities to be part of the process are fundamental to allow the realisation of all these sustainable individual and day-to-day behaviours. In this sense, each one can be an “active citizen” (Ambrosini, 2021) in the development of the right, recalling the fundamental role that private citizens can have in the consolidation of a new human right as a social construct *Section 1.2.3*.

ACTIVISTS AND SOCIAL MOVEMENTS

Active citizenship, according to the scholar Ambrosini, can be conceived as mundane actions –as those above–, but the core of its meaning is the *active* engagement of individuals in the society, giving more than the ordinary, adding value and accelerating the processes. Some individuals spend time and effort to advocate for the cause and spread that awareness that is necessary to lodge mundane change in mentality and behaviours of which above to build right over time. Even one single person can have a huge impact: the proof of this is the advocacy work of the activist Wangari Maathai (1940-2011), who according to Mr. Dilman has had a cardinal role in raising the awareness of Kenyan people towards environmental issues.

“Do you think the mindset is changing in general?”

Yeah, it is changing slowly, slowly, slowly.

And who do you think boosted this change? Like social media, organizations, social movements, the government...?”

There was an environmentalist called Mata, Mata... I've forgotten the name. But we consider her as the person who brought changes in Kenya in terms of environment.

When?

During the time... She's been there since 1990s.”

Okay, Mata something.

Yes. I will look up. The one who was preserving Karura Forest. She won the Nobel Peace Prize; it should be easy to find.

Even when she died, she said that she don't want to be buried in a casket, in a wooden casket. I think she was cremated, I think.

So she's the one who championed the changes that took place. Even though she died, yes, but now we had civil societies coming in to say ‘no, we have to change something. We don't want to continue doing this’. Yeah, so that's when we started to have some changes.”

(Mr. Dilman, 32yo, CIVS staff and coordinator of the volunteers)

One person can trigger a huge change, a sudden awareness and a will to change things, to build something. Wangari Maathai was a Kenyan environmental, social and political activist who founded the Green Belt Movement in 1977, an NGO that addressed deforestation, environmental degradation, and women's rights. The movement encouraged communities, particularly women, to plant trees to combat soil erosion, restore biodiversity, and secure sustainable livelihoods, by providing them the resources and training to do so, improving their economic status and fostering environmental stewardship. Over time, the Green Belt Movement expanded beyond Kenya, contributing to the planting of over 30 million trees across Africa (The Green Movement, n.d.). She was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize in 2004, and it was noted her contribution to “sustainable development, democracy and peace”, as well as her holistic approach to “think globally and act locally” (The Nobel Prize, n.d.). Advocating, acting, training and empowering communities she actively built right, as she brought operational change, planting trees and raising awareness and responsibility to keep doing so among the population. Many, however, are the “active citizens” who contribute to sensitise people, becoming participating to and accelerating the process of consolidation. One example:

“[...] And the researchers, Kenyan researchers, I remember there was a professor, somebody called Professor Omondi.

Professor Omondi?

Yeah, Omondi; he started sensitizing people in the local radio stations.”

(Mr. Moses, 35-40 yo, Farmer and permaculture expert, Red Cross staff)

According to Mr. Moses, he started his activity after the international environmental movement had started, started by Greta Thunberg and mobilising youths and researchers from all over the world. International action can serve as a booster for local initiative. Social movements have the huge power of being pervasive, directly reaching the people and eventually multiplying their outreach extension, being able to reach larger areas and also, the more people are active locally, more in-depth in communities.

Social movements can consolidate in structured forms of organisation as association for of advocacy and right defence, as in the case of the Center for Justice Governance and Environmental Action (CJGEA), which mainstreams a human rights approach to environmental protection of communities (Stanley, 2015). The organisation was founded by Phyllis Omido, who has been advocating for environmental rights for over a decade, culminating her activity with an important judicial victory. She lodged a lawsuit against the metal refinery she was working for, for lead poisoning proved by testing children feeling sick (among which her son too), and receiving pressures by the company and government officers to stop her investigations, arriving to physical threats and an assassination attempt in 2014. She started campaigning. Many journalists joined the trainings on human rights- and environmental issues offered by the organisation KIOS in support to Phyllis’ case, and were able to get a number of media houses to report the news, arriving to have a TV documentary on it made by Kenya Television Network, causing an uproar in Kenya. The publicity pressured government officials to start an investigation, and ultimately to the victory of the case, with the court ordering the contaminated environment to be cleaned in four months and a sum of money to be paid by the metal refinery and by government agencies that refused to investigate the matter for damages to the community. This case shows the power of social engagement and the commitment of each single individual as “active citizen” to fight for their rights; in the words of Ms. Omondi, “This means access to health, access to a clean and healthy environment, and socioeconomic empowerment for the community” (KIOS, 2020).

VOLUNTEERS

One example of this are volunteers, who put their time, skills and operativity at disposal of organisations to implement projects they adhere to or to help people in need. In this case, I can contribute to the study with a direct testimony wearing here my clothes of volunteer myself instead of researcher: one of the reasons that lead to engage this kind of activity is the will to actively participate to a cause in which one believes, and to learn more on how to contribute to it. Volunteering, in fact and maybe counterintuitively, more about learning and gaining than giving. It can also be a way of “giving back”: Nam, who was one of the coordinators of us volunteers but still also taking part to every activity, was telling that he had started his relation with CIVS as beneficiary of their courses; he had got to know by referral of a seminar to be held by them the following day and decided without much thinking to participate, having nothing to lose. It turned out in a great opportunity to get knowledge and skills, certified on paper and useful on the professional field. Feeling grateful for that help, and sharing their mission to turn the area of the county back to be healthy and prosperous, also for the health of its people, he decided to join their activities as a volunteer, arriving after many years to coordinate himself the teams. Now he is moving a step forward trying to set up also another organisation that can produce, distribute and train on the care of seedlings, while starting his academic path as nurse. Volunteering can be highly beneficial for the society, and is a concrete example of active citizenship, as it increases the number of people that are operative in the process, and this can accelerate it or improve its quality.

Rhoda and Linet, two young girls and local volunteers in my team in Kuth Awendo, were telling that they joined CIVS as volunteers mainly to get practical skills that could enhance their professional profiles, while contributing positively for the society (field notes, 5th October 2025). Linet has studied nutrition at university and wanted to learn about sustainable farming and crops to enhance the completeness of her education, and be able to then provide a more complete and green counselling in matters of food security; in particular, she would ideally follow and educate mostly women. While from books she learnt the nutritional values of the most available sources of foods in the area, volunteering with CIVS in the resource centre model farm and helping in other organisations' farms, she had the possibility to learn about the ecological aspect of those crops, about new ones (e.g.: the kalro new maize variety maturing earlier), how to produce

organic compost and strategies to grow successfully certain plants, and so on. This gave her a more realistic idea of what families could have done to enhance their household food security in a healthy, ecological and climate change resilient way. Rhoda found the experience useful also because she could access ICT courses in exchange of working in the farm, and even obtain a certificate accredited by the government to prove the acquisition of the new skills and increase her employability possibilities. By her initial surprise, she discovered that networking is another advantage that comes with the experience: a couple of years ago, one of the European volunteers of team, who -as everybody of us- had also become a friend and decided to financially help her to sustain her university studies. He covered her university fees until last year, then he was no longer able to sustain the cost for personal reasons and had to suspend the aid; without that, Rhoda had to drop out university because of its unaffordability, and moved to Nairobi looking for income opportunities, accepting even the most humiliating or underpaid jobs.

DONORS

Donating is another way to be an “active citizen”, as in the case of Rhoda, where this enabled her, at least for a period, to continue higher education and try to realise her dreams (she was studying finance). As for education, financial resources are fundamental also in the field of environmental protection, in many different ways. Financial support to a local NGO can concretely enable it to provide its services to the community on a larger scale, or to increase the number of initiatives offered (e.g.: distributing more seedlings; hiring more human resources; finance more activities). In the case of CIVS, some historical German have been substantially contributing to their budget and work for some years already. Donating can be an effective way to participate to a right consolidation, especially when the person shares the cause but lacks skills or time to give an operative help, by providing the necessary resources to assist who instead has those skills and time to do operational and effective action. Some other times a donation can take the form of an immediate and quite dismissive measure (consciously or not), as in the case of donating a borehole (or the money to do so), as the one in the CIVS resource centre of Ahero, offered by a Kenyan donor; if a person will think that this is alone-standing building right then she will be wrong, but nonetheless it has is a helpful means of assistance for the community in the meanwhile that right is constructed consistently.

Similarly, donors can procure useful material to NGOs, alighting the system by which they programmed to contribute to a long-term process: one example is the donation of medical machineries and of computers for ICT courses to CIVS medical and didactic projects respectively in Kakamega and Ahero, enhancing health and education. Without them it would have been more difficult to provide services of higher quality or accessible to more people, reducing the resilience of the community and the schooling opportunity of youths. Recalling that joining the ICT course was an occasion which got Nam and Rhoda to also work with CIVS yielding their sensitisation and personal commitment to the organisation's cause for the environment, it is not to be neglected the role that "side" projects can have in the process for HRHE. Material and financial resources, for any individual and organisation, can be a precious a concrete support and a catalyst for action.

4.2.3 The growing role of the financial and the private sectors

Resources are fundamental to put in action almost whatever development action, included those participating to and accelerating the process of right construction. NGOs funds mainly derive from donations; for CIVS, for instance, Mr. Dilman spoke about a German donor as main contributor, and also Nam mentioned a German company to have donated the computers for ICT classes. The county government is not able does not finance per se projects in local territories, but helps in their coordination and implementation by providing skills and expertise (Ms. Quinter). The national government most often distributes and manages money received from international institutions, to employed locally through a vertical collaboration. Intergovernmental organisations as the UN agencies and similar (e.g., UNEP, WTO), mostly provide technical assistance and capacity building, help in analysing the context drafting reports and recommendations, do advocacy and campaigning, issue regulations, legislative framework and agreements, without directly financing or implementing projects in the field; rather, they give support to those who operationalise them (Mr. Kiru). This does not mean they are not part of the process building right; instead, they are an active part to accelerate the process and yields useful means to deploy a more conscious, structured and quality action. It only means that their (main, at least) role is not the one of funding. In a capitalist global economic structure as ours, resources are mostly and increasingly concentrated in the hands of privates.

DEVELOPMENT BANKS, FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS AND INSTRUMENTS

From the different interviews, it emerged that those most frequently financing development projects are international banks and financial institutions (IFI). The most prominent example is the World Bank, giving funds to the government to implement specific projects of capacity building. According to Ms. Quinter, they impose very rigid conditions in terms of sustainability (environmental and social), and this is positive in order to stimulate right-building action and awareness. One example is the requirement of 50% of women participating to the training on tree planting and sustainable agriculture, which is positive for what discussed in previous sections. Through budgetary assistance and structural adjustment programs, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) provides macroeconomic support that can condition or enable environmental reforms, with national impact. At regional level, the African Development Bank (AfDB) channels significant investment into energy and connectivity projects, expanding access to clean electricity in rural areas, directly contributing to environmental health and social equity, while the European Investment Bank (EIB) supports sustainable agriculture by facilitating private-sector lending for climate-smart agri-businesses. All of these are examples of development banks, that are public or multilateral institutions created to promote economic and social development, especially in low- and middle-income countries; unlike commercial banks, which are driven by profit and tend to avoid high-risk or low-return projects, development banks focus on sectors that are critical for long-term societal well-being, such as education, healthcare, environmental protection, and infrastructure. Those banks, as their name suggests, focus on development, which entails by nature the attention to sustainability and the will to create an equitable future as well as a healthy environment for all; due to this, in addition to their operational commitment to the long-term result and the structural impact, they are a pivotal actor in the process of building a human right to live in a healthy and clean environment. To do so, they provide long-term, low-interest financing, often in the form of concessional loans, grants, or blended finance mechanisms that combine public and private capital, collaborating with governments, NGOs, and private actors to support projects that may not attract traditional investment but are essential for achieving sustainable development goals. Some entities are specialised in a definite field, as the Green Climate Fund (GCF) which mobilises climate finance for developing countries to fund adaptation and mitigation projects.

Working at the Italian Permanent Mission at the UN and other IOs in Geneva in the Development and Environment sector, I was able to attend many meetings of UNCTAD, UNECE, the speeches of many ministries from all over the world, and what emerged with homogeneity is a need to leverage private investment and employ green financial instruments as a strategy to attract resources towards development projects, leading also privates to engage in a financial behaviour that is similar to that of development banks. Among the most prominent are green bonds, which allow governments and corporations to raise capital specifically for climate-friendly projects such as renewable energy, clean transport, or sustainable water systems. Similarly, sustainable finance and green finance frameworks aim to integrate environmental, social, and governance (ESG) criteria into decision-making, encouraging long-term investment in low-carbon, inclusive economies. Climate and adaptation finance, often channelled through entities like the GCF, support more measures related to adaptation and mitigation of climate change effects, hence not projects directly building right, but rather resilience (e.g., investing in drought-resistant agriculture or flood defences), while nature finance refers to investments in ecosystem restoration and biodiversity conservation (Satta, *et al.*, 2025). Risk management, and the study of how climate risk affects the big economy, is one of the main interest and activities of banks, in order to help direct investments towards green assets (Mr. Reuben, green finance expert, 26th March 2025, Geneva). In this context, development finance, consists in concessional loans and guarantees provided by development banks to de-risk projects and crowd in private capital. With similar aim, the Italian Ministry for the Environment and Energy Security (MESA) and Vice-chair of the UNECE Committee on Environmental Policy, Alessandra Fidanza (2025) underlined, at the MESA-UNECE meeting on nature-based-solutions, how blended should be leveraged to catalyse private investments towards sustainable projects.

What emerges is that at institutional level, international organisations and national government entities do not have the financial resources to support alone local or large-scale action to build right, but are working to gather and find those resources catalysing them towards the wanted direction. At legislative level, much work his being done in the creation of carbon markets, including cap-and-trade systems and voluntary carbon credits, to internalize the cost of emissions and generate resources for mitigation projects.

Also at local level, banks and financial institutions play a central role as resources providers to NGOs and territorial organisations. When asking to Mr. Isaac, director of The Green World ONG (January 3rd, 2025), how do they sustain themselves as an organisation (giving out seedlings and trainings employing both material and human resources), he answered that to get funds they partner with financial institutions. For example, one of their partners is SME Bank, towards which they stand as guarantors: the people who get trained by the NGO and receive the seedlings will be able, once grown, to make profit from it; the earned money will go through the designated SME Bank accounts, enabling lenders to recover their advance, while the remaining profit is shared among group members. Another example of local financial support can be found in private financial cooperatives as SACCO (Savings and Credit Cooperative), which issues affordable credit to its members (Mr. Ogando and Mr. Bitter, farmers, September 2024).

PRIVATE COMPANIES: BUSINESS AND CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY

Not only financial institutions from public or private sectors do actively contribute to finance constructive initiatives in the field of environmental human rights building, but also private companies; one example is provided again by Mr. Isaac of The Green World:

“Besides the local financial institutions, we are also appealing to guarantors. You find Simulo Seeds, you find Calro. So once in a while, they have some demonstration sites; once they have a demonstration site in a region, they also give free trainings and seedlings to the farmers in the community.

Okay, but why do they do this? Like, what is their interest?

Their interest as seed companies, you know, we are creating market for them. Because when they give out these seeds, as they demonstrate, more members will start buying these seeds, [this way] they create market for themselves.

Ahm, so it's like a cycle. If those people produce a lot, hence need other seeds, they will buy theirs. So they have interest in sponsoring them at the beginning of the business, let's say, right? Right.”

Private companies may decide to financially support NGOs in capacity building activities or providing material with the aim of benefitting in terms of profit in the future.

For them it is an investment. The same logic can be applied in the field of international cooperation: while some contributions may take the form of philanthropy or donations, corporations may cooperate with NGOs for development projects in the Global South for a number of strategic and reputational reasons.

First, such engagement might represent a way to create new market opportunities, expand their potential client base over territory or time (as in the case of Simulo Seeds locally), or strengthen local supply chains, contributing indirectly to their own long-term growth; it can also take the form of a short-term marketing.

Secondly, partnering with development actors can enhance the corporate image and public relations, with a high reputational payoff at the eye of their consumers, stimulating their loyalty or new acquisitions. Increasingly more it is required by international institutions (e.g., UN Global Compact, 1999³⁶) and by the spreading ethically conscious consumers among the global community, that companies try to hold their activities and products sustainable in their impact on the environment and on communities. Such actions are embedded within a company's Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) strategy, aimed at reinforcing brand reputation and stakeholder trust (Schunk, 2025). These motivations can lead a company to act as a financial partner to an NGO, either by responding to a fundraising campaign aligned with its own thematic or geographic priorities, or by themselves proactively seeking an organization capable of implementing a project under its ownership or direction. In some cases, this collaboration evolves into formal public-private partnerships (PPPs), where companies co-design and co-finance development programmes together with public authorities and civil society actors, blending impact with innovation.

In other cases, support for environmental or social initiatives may serve to offset or mitigate the impact of unsustainable practices previously carried out by the company in the same area; it is the case of Coca Cola, which on the whole territory of Kenya is providing points of free access to clean water for the community, offsetting the monopoly and exploitation of this precious resource that it is carrying on (*Figure 28.*) (field notes).

³⁶ The UN Global Compact is a voluntary initiative launched by the United Nations in 1999 to encourage businesses worldwide to align their operations and strategies with ten universal principles in the areas of human rights, labor, environment, and anti-corruption. It provides a global platform for corporate sustainability and responsible business conduct. Its influence on private companies has been significant: it has pushed thousands of firms—especially multinationals—to adopt Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria, enhance transparency, and integrate sustainability into their core strategies, especially in relation to climate action and human rights (United Nations Global Compact, 2015).

The sustainability of this kind of initiatives, however, it highly doubtful: it would more appropriate to stop the unsustainable behaviours rather than mitigating it with apparently responsible programmes.

Figure 28. Coca Cola production site close to Badilisha, October 2024.

For all of the reasons above, the rate of private companies financially supporting development projects or carrying their activities in a sustainable way is increasingly significant. This trend reveals a dual logic. On the one hand, such engagement is almost purely profit-driven, coherently with the private sector intrinsic logic of business, and does not respond to the requirements of ownership of the cause and aware participation to the process of building a right as it is for individuals. On the other hand, ethically committed or not, this seems less important in the case of corporations with respect to single citizens: previous sections showed to which considerable extent multinational and territorial corporations provoke environmental degradation by exploiting resources and/or polluting, with negative impact on the ecosystem and on its human population. Whether it is for ethical commitment or for other market logics, as marketing or reputational factors, this does not change the benefit of having them stopping dangerous production behaviours or implementing positive reparation projects.

The same discourse could be done where the reasons of this commitment for development and protection are “imposed” from above: international frameworks as the UN Global Compact and increasingly stringent EU regulations on standards³⁷ are pushing

³⁷ Examples are the European Green Deal; Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM); Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD); Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).

corporations to comply with principles of environmental and social sustainability. In the context of companies, compliance controls with the rules are tighter and monitoring is easier than the one related to single citizens, hence the ownership of the cause and the driving principles behind the rule appear less important. The impact of the actions coming “from above”, when directed towards the private sector, appear to be more effective for the sake of contributing to create a healthy environment than when directed towards the community.

It could also be implicitly developed by private companies, as a positive side result, a sincere sense of responsibility, changing the mindset of heads of corporations of new generations. However, this would not be fundamental, as the market and the institutions already seem to provide a solid ground for compliance to more sustainable business models and for an even active participation to the construction of a healthy environment financing related development projects.

Carbon markets can be intended as a both market and institutional driver of environmental responsibility for corporations, regulating production in order to ensure global carbon neutrality and overall business sustainability. However, it does not come without controversies. Developing countries argue that these mechanisms constrain their economic growth, imposing environmental standards without adequately accounting for historical emissions disparities, in a context where they suffer the most from environmental degradation despite having contributed the least to global emissions. This concern is rooted in the principle of *Common But Differentiated Responsibilities* (CBDR), which recognizes that while all countries must address climate change, they do not share equal historical responsibility or capacity. Moreover, concerns arise regarding the equitable distribution of benefits from carbon credit schemes, with many projects failing to deliver promised advantages to local communities (field notes from meetings attended in UNCTAD and WTO, Geneva, 2025). As for the case of “offsetting projects”, the apparent alignment of the private sector to sustainability and the new guise of corporations as actors of the process building a healthy environment may be deceitful. A deeper investigation of the actual effect of private sector participation to development processes would be necessary to assess their actual impact.

CHAPTER V

Interpretation of results

The present chapter will recap the results obtained from the research, contrasting the empirical outcome to the literature (*Chapter I*), and drawing further considerations on such bond and on their material implications.

The human right to a healthy environment, as extensively explored in *Section 1.1.4*, started to emerge as a social claim in the '50-'60s, obtaining a first legislative response in the recognition of the profound connection between the environment and human rights in the Stockholm Treaty (1972). The Rio Declaration (1992) established a mechanism of protection of the environment, but with a purely eco-centric approach that overlooked human rights violations, foreseeing their use only in their procedural form in environmental matters. Judiciary bodies hence started to employ the strategy of "greening" human rights, in order to foster their protection under environmental issues, but also this anthropocentric approach was problematic neglecting nature conservation. The best solution resulted to be the framing of a *substantial* human right to a healthy environment, that was able to ensure both environment and people protection, and the recognition as such in the international panorama only came in 2022 by a resolution of the UN General Assembly. The African region, probably due to the prematurely harsh impact of extreme weather events with respect to other regional realities, was earlier onset on recognition at the legal level: this right was enshrined already in 1981 in the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, and peculiarly to our study, also by the new Kenyan Constitution in 2010. The facts hence yield that the human right to a healthy environment already *exists*, and even at international level. What could instead be further investigated is whether this existence also coincided with its *realisation*. It was studied the level of its practice and achievement in a small and limited area, that of Kisumu County, Kenya, through the voices of the people, at their perception, being those in a direct relation with the environment around them. It was explored, coherently with the research questions posed at the beginning, whether the environment is healthy; how this impacts its villagers; if it has improved or worsened with respect to the past and eventually due to which factors. The third chapter concentrated on this set of inquiries.

5.1 Results on the assessment of the HRHE realisation

5.1.1 Results

HRHE IS CONSOLIDATING BUT IS NOT ACHIEVED YET

The main result of the investigation on the ground about the level of realisation of the HRHE in Kisumu County is that “the situation has improved a little, but environmental rights are still building” (Elisabeth): it is not possible yet to affirm it is achieved and enjoyed by people. On the contrary, environmental issues remain one of the most prominent and severe problems affecting the population and they have a strong impact on them. When asking about the worse difficulties, all of the people interviewed on the ground, from the villages, expressed concern about this specifically, and the tone of their voices was most often disguising desperation, stress, sadness and exhaustion. Answers were for example: “environment is the main problem” (Mr. Ogando), “floods destroy everything” (Ms. Valery), “if have to say one, floods. During floods, we experience a lot of effects of climate change. And I can tell you, during that period, there is loss of life and properties, so many people drowning” (Mr. Moses); or again “water is the main problem. If only we could have more water we...” (Elisabeth). Violent deadly floods, unpredictable and prolonged periods of severe droughts, climate change, polluted air, soil and waters, are not signs of a healthy environment.

THE ENVIRONMENT IS NOT HEALTHY

According to the interviewed subjects a change started to be witnessed in the ‘90s, in direct connection with the commencement of a process of deforestation in response to a sudden demographic increase and need for more land to farm and to build new houses, encouraged by the at the time President Moi, giving land to gain political support. The tree felling process, since trees are the most important source of evaporating water, provoked an alteration in the hydric cycle and the disruption of rain patterns, which in Kenya used to be long rains since mid-March to May, and shorter rains in November and December. Prolonged periods of harsh drought started to manifest, getting vegetation to dry and eventually die, animals deprived of water and food (vegetables) to starve to death, with great losses in biodiversity. Dryness also implies soil erosion, which combined with

the absence of solid trees, provokes that then “when it’s raining, it’s flooding” (Brian). Trees keep being cut down also to produce wood fuels as charcoal, still the most common source of domestic energy, e.g.: for cooking, due to poverty and lack of structured and efficient electric energy systems. Deforestation, in addition, means an extension of the area of bare soil, less able to absorb solar radiations, hence causing the surface to warm and contributing further to climate alteration.

Global warming was already ongoing as result of the fast industrialisation process all over the world during the twentieth century, connected with a sudden and massive release of greenhouse gases from fossil fuel combustion in factories. The effects of climate change became visible at their most around 2015, according to the people, exacerbating an already dramatic situation for the environment: with effective +1.45°C on the global mean temperature (registered in 2016, the hottest year on record), droughts become harsher and even more unbearable by forms of life, and consequently all the factors in turn implied, as soil erosion and floods violence. Multinational corporations account for a very large part in having damaged the environment both globally and locally, as global effects are also affecting small realities, but also because of their unfair and disproportionate exploitation of resources, included those of Kisumu County. Significant is the example of Coca Cola holding a *de facto* monopoly of water resources, which already are scarce, and that can be run at convenience of the company (people are used to drinking more Coca Cola than water as main drinking source, as one can of it is less expensive than a Dasani water bottle, being it a water company under control of Coca Cola). Careless and excessive exploitation of natural resources also contributes to environmental degradation. Furthermore, the emissions of those company pollute the air on large scales. To air pollution, contribute also local households and individuals, by their unsustainable domestic behaviours as burning charcoal and especially waste, which is a practice still common today, even where the people are aware of its harmfulness for the environment, due to the lack of a structured system of collection (not even a differentiated one) of waste or of recycling. Not only plastics is commonly burnt, but its consumption levels also remain high due to the people in compliance with the ban on single-use plastics; most of the rural population is in fact very poor, and low sustainable but widely affordable products are more attracting to them, even at cost of illegally importing it from the neighbouring Rwanda, especially given the practically absent monitoring.

The systemic domestic application of monoculture and employment of synthetic fertilizers with the aim producing more in the same portion of land, neglecting or unaware that this causes a contamination of the environment (included the produced food that will be consumed), contribute respectively to impoverishment and pollution of the soil. Improper farming methods and human activities upstream also affect water quality, causing soil erosion and water pollution.

THE ENVIRONMENT IS NOT HEALTHY...FOR THE PEOPLE LIVING IN IT EITHER

Anthropogenic factors have actively contributed to, if not provoked, negative consequences on the environment, nourishing a progressively increasing unhealthy condition of it. The human dimension of the HRHE, however, does not regard only its causes, but also its consequences: the impact of such an unhealthy environment is huge and devastating for the population, implying a status of *unhealth* also for the people living in it. The degree of health and security of the people is a second dimension of the HRHE that cannot be neglected in assessing the level of its realisation, and until both dimensions will remain precarious the right will not be able to be defined as achieved.

The result of the interviews is that environmental issues in Kisumu County are at the core of the most suffering problems for its inhabitants, with both direct and indirect, immediate and long-term consequences, often exacerbating each other, or pre-existing difficulties, and ultimately violating a high number of human rights (listed in the UDHR). The chain of the adverse effects will be summarised below, with reference to *Chapter 3.2* and, in particular, to *Figure 22*.

The alteration of rain patterns and the occurrence of unpredictable and prolonged periods of drought, worsened in severity by global warming, implies a strain drain of rivers, wells, aquifers, and ponds, with the first and foremost direct impact of hampering access to safe and clean water for drinking and hygiene and creating immediately inadequate standards of life (Art. 25). The insufficiency of hydration and hygiene weakens the immunitary system, coupled with resorting to contaminated sources, exposes communities to the risk of contracting water-borne diseases as cholera and typhoid, undermining the right to life and health (Art. 3).

Man is not the only one impacted by water scarcity: animals die, plants die; this, besides threatening forms of life, means for the inhabitants of rural villages -as those in Kisumu County- loss of livestock and crops, eliminating both subsistence food and especially saleable surpluses. In addition, the already eroded soil brought by droughts is further impoverished by monoculture and use chemical substances, aggravating its decreasing productivity even after the dry period passes. Water and soil pollution, resulting mainly from plastics and general waste abandonment or even burning, play a great role in enhancing the severity of such condition. The irregularity of rains and dry seasons, moreover, impedes households to plan their cultivations accordingly and might each time lose everything. The resulting food insecurity and rising poverty strike further the right to an adequate standard of living and to decent work (Art. 25). While most of the people in the area usually get to have at least one meal per day (Rhoda), extreme poverty is a much more infectious phenomenon, with numerous and tremendous spillover effects and regarded as “the main issue in Kenya” (Rhoda).

First, income loss can push households towards proliferation of coping strategies as intensive agriculture, casual and additional jobs, or child work, hindering soil health, rights to decent work (Art. 23) and the rights of children. Among those matters, one of the main violated is the right to education (Art. 26), given the unaffordability in times of crisis of the school fees, forcing withdrawal or discontinuous attendance. Then, persistent economic concern precipitates anxiety, depression and, in severe cases, suicide attempts, undermining the right to rest, leisure and well-being (Art. 24) –where the latter could, in a progressive attitude, be included in a violation of Art. 3 framed as mental health. Poverty exhausting conditions create tensions, at several levels, expanding at each subsequent degree. While the first level of tension can be individual, as already mentioned in terms of emotional stability, the second level is internal to the household, where intensifying arguments when women cannot meet their families’ needs (as they are traditionally in charge of in the Kenyan rural culture) can easily escalate in domestic gender-based violence, infringing the right to equality and non-discrimination (Art. 1) and freedom from degrading treatment (Art. 5). A third level would be collective, whereby frictions among neighbours over land and resources, as well as general social unrest arise in responses to desperate conditions and mistrust in authorities; these might even soar into armed confrontation, endangering the right to social security and public order (Art. 22).

Another huge set of rights is violated in relation to floods: torrential rains on hardened soil encountering no tree as obstacle, furiously overwhelm whatever is on their path, causing first and foremost death and destruction, violating the right to life and many others more. Health (still Art. 3) is threatened in multiple ways, ranging from the magnification of the WASH crisis and exposure to waterborne diseases by consuming unclean or contaminated water brought by the flooding stream, to the to the inaccessibility of healthcare facilities crushed during the calamity. Housing collapse and consequent forced displacement deny to people the right to property (Art. 17), the right to home and private life (Art. 8), of liberty (Art. 3) and free movement (Art. 13), but also intensify poverty conditions, due to livestock and crops destruction and inability to care of them, exacerbating the connected difficulties already described above. Most of the people are rescued and brought to schools –richer ones have concrete walls– and remain there for weeks until the water gets back to normal level, and live for that period all in the same room, without any privacy, disrupting their dignity (Art. 25), right to decent work (Art. 23), and also the right to education of children (art. 26), who –other than in this condition– might have their school destroyed or hosting those in need.

Pollution effects are not to be underestimated, as they might be less visible on the short-term but yet very dangerous: on the long-term they can extensively reduce life expectancy and physical health, due to a combined persistent exposure to CO₂ emissions and waste burning in the air, water and soil contamination with plastics and general waste abandonment, as well as consumption of food produced out of synthetic fertilisers.

The voices of the people interviewed in the villages were often broken, filled with sentiments of distress, exhaustion, melancholy, unveiling effort and a strong spirit of resilience, but also hope and belief in a better future, with a genuine smile of brotherhood.

5.1.2 Implications of results

ENVIRONMENTAL UNHEALTH IS A “RISK MULTIPLIER”: ACTION IS URGENT

The human right to a healthy environment emerged not to be realised yet, due to a still unhealthy condition of the environment *per se* and for its inhabitants, with devastating consequences on both. More than ten human rights have been, in particular,

individuated from the interviews on the ground to be violated or threatened by a direct (e.g. death), long-term (e.g. health and living conditions), or indirect effect, though the exacerbation of pre-existing situations (e.g. domestic gender-violence, poverty) or as implication of other direct effects (e.g. discontinuous education due to poverty in drought periods).

The foremost consideration that can be done in light of these results, is that an unhealthy environment is a *risk multiplier*, as it increases both the probability that rights will be breached and the very same number of rights under threat. A similar concept has already circulated widely among agreed literature, namely “climate change as a threat multiplier”, but this appears with regard to what emerged a restrictive and incomplete definition. First of all, climate change is limitative, as it is not the only driving factor of the disrupted status of health of the environment; secondly, the term “threat” is usually understood to refer to national security matters, whereas the consequences affecting people are much broader, impacting on a very wide range of human rights.

The implication of being a risk multiplier is a urgent need to *substantially* recognise, more broadly and with operative intention, the right to a healthy environment as one of the fundamental human rights, to be implemented as much and as soon as possible to prevent severe effects and other rights violations. *The call for action is impelling.* Who shall be the receiver of this call and take charge of it was investigated in the fourth chapter, with its results being exposed in the incoming *Secion 5.2*. The urgency of spreading locally but also worldwide awareness of the essentiality to keep attention and effort to consolidate this right is grounded in its nature of lying at the root causes of such a high number of other human issues and is functional to the attainment of other human rights in a consolidated and durable manner: taking poverty in rural areas as Kisumu is, for example, it would be possible to dispose measures to contain the impact it has on households, but would not *eliminate* the problem; reducing the occurrence of unexpected and prolonged droughts, instead, could cut out disruption fatalities and allow people to plan a long-term strategy to get out of poverty conditions, would allow development. Development is a key element for the realisation of stable and durable adequate conditions of life and accomplishment of other human rights, and it is in the hands of local communities, but these can nothing against the power of a nature manifesting its unhealth.

As a recommendation, to local, but also international people, as well as to the kind reader of this piece, the human right to a healthy environment should receive more attention and engagement of active citizens to be realised, as the voices I have reported in all of the previous pages reveal an imperative need for it to consolidate further.

AN EMPIRICAL CONFIRMATION: LEGAL RECOGNITION IS NOT ENOUGH

From the assessment of the degree of realisation of the HRHE in the limited territory of Kisumu County, it resulted that while it is being built, it is definitely not achieved yet, showing the harsh consequences on the environment and people summarised in the previous paragraph. One implication of this outcome is an empirical confirmation of what stated in *Section 1.1.5*, that legal recognition is not enough. In fact, Kenya was among those one hundred constitutions to recognise the *right to a clean and healthy environment* (Art. 42, Constitution of Kenya, 2010), but it is clear from the stories and tone of voice of the people interviewed that the attainment of the right has not come forward with the issuance of the piece of legislation. However, it appears from the conversations that it had a cornerstone role as a trigger for change, boosting environmental policy and raising awareness among the population. It can be said hence empirically validated, at least in the examined territory, Amartya Sen's conceptualisation of proclamations of human rights as "really strong ethical pronouncements as to what *should be done*" (2009, p.357). The formal recognition asserted the existence of such right, being claimed by social movements already since the late '70s (for instance, by the Green Belt Movement, 1977), but this does not coincide with an assertion of *realisation*; rather, it launches a prompt to start or reinforce its consolidation process towards the desired achievement.

THE HUMAN DIMENSION OF THE HRHE

The research yielded grounded and strong evidence of the tight connection between environment and human beings recognised by the Stockholm Treaty in 1972: it emerged how much human activities can impact on the environment health, and to which huge extent the condition of the latter can influence the life of its inhabitants. The implication of this empirical evidence is that it proofs how essential it is to frame the health of the environment as a human right itself, not only as a legislative or judicial matter for

enforcement, but also conceptually and ideologically in relation to its mere ontology. Besides the formal one, academic and common-sense recognition are also essential, in order to be able to consolidate its existence –and possibly its realisation– in its highest and most efficient form durably over time. It is in this indissoluble bond between environment and man that proclamation from above cannot be enough to determine its realisation: its very human nature requires *individuals* to actively participate to its attainment. As a matter of fact, if the causes of environment unhealth are of anthropogenic nature, then man shall also be able to –and *should*–imperatively commit to reverse them.

THE SOCIAL DIMENSION OF THE HRHE

The result of the research suggests that not only man is individually involved in the influence on and by the environment, but it is the human *collective* dimension to have an effective impact. The evidence confirms the constructionist theory of human rights that sees them as a social construct, as ethical claims. Social movements and claims for environmental justice started to emerge since the late '70s (*Section 4.2.2*), establishing the emergence of the human right to a healthy environment and progressively consolidating its existence. What can be complemented to the reasoning behind this theory related to the HRHE is that not only its origin relies in social systems, but also its effects (both from enjoying it and not) and its realisation processes, which emerged – especially in Chapter 4– to require a participated action from below. This also reflects the conceptualisation of the category of human rights of third generation, to which the HRHE belongs, in fact also called “collective” rights. When inquiring whether the right was perceived as achieved, most people answered it is still “building”, word that intrinsically entails a sense of collective action, confirming the “constructivist” theory and the social aspect of environmental human rights.

As a final conclusion, answering to the first main research question of this study – “assessment of the degree of realisation of the human right to a healthy environment in Kisumu County, through the voices of the people”–, the investigation on the ground yielded averagely that “the situation has improved, but environmental rights are still building –from the specific words of Elisabeth–, suggesting that action is ongoing and the right is consolidating, but it will take continuing the effort to get closer to its achievement.

5.2 Results on the study of HRHE consolidation process

The first set of research yielded that, although much is yet to be done, with still terrible consequences on the population, action to achieve the HRHE is actually underway. The second set of research, carried on in *Chapter 4*, studied this action with an in-depth qualitative attitude of analysis: if the first wanted to preliminarily assess *whether* and at *what degree* a HRHE has consolidated in the Kisumu county, the second wanted to assess *how* it consolidated, examining the process up to date, with academic but also operational purposes for learning and improving or replicating.

The questions driving the research in this part deepened *in which way* and to which extent the changes brought “from above”, as the establishment of the Constitution or of relevant national and international policies, contributed to the consolidation process of HRHE in the area; how much do initiatives undertaken “from below” contribute; how do the two parts interact with each other and with which effect on the overall process; *who* actually are the actors of those “above” and “below” individuated in the literature, and whether there are other players to take in consideration; how do international, national, and local levels account; what are the specific activities undertaken by each of them; which of those measures are actually building right and why.

Even despite good intention or significant investment, not all measures resulted to bring sustainable change in the trajectory of building a durable human right to a healthy environment; this section will investigate the factors underlying behind this difference and try to individuate failure and successful patterns, in order to provide guidelines for actors willing to effectively participate the right-building process.

One important aspect to consider is that, as for the first set of the study, the focus remains on maintaining an ethnographic approach, listening and giving echo to voices of the people *living* what investigated, from both above and below.

5.2.1 Which elements do actually contribute to HRHE consolidation?

ELEMENTS THAT DO *NOT* BUILD RIGHT

A wide range of measures emerged from the interviews to be implemented in order to contrast the unhealth of the environment emerged. This section will convey a critical analysis of such initiatives, with an eye to the literature and an ear to the experience of the people, to determine which of those are actually contributing to build a human right to a healthy environment and which are only coping mechanism, or -to use a metaphor- which are *healing* the disease, and which are only *painkillers*.

The UNDP Human Development Report 2016 suggests that any policy making should be founded on four principles, namely: inclusivity for universal validity, specific attention to groups with special needs, empowerment of those left out, and development resilience (UNDP, p. iii). The health of the environment perfectly falls in the domain of development, as -from what results from the first set of research- it is at the core of the economic and social improvement essential elements of development to enhance human well-being, therefore the four principles shall also be valid in order to reach it. In particular, the aspect of resilience is fundamental: the durability of a desired condition underlying the attainment of a human right is fundamental to ensure its enjoyment *de facto* and *in potentia*, creating a security that also over time that right will be exercised, and not only the day the measure is taken. It is a reflection of the concept of sustainability, which keeps an eye on the future enjoyment of the same right.

As an implication of this, “giving patterns” that international NGOs and donors have employed for long time, now in diminishing trend, are not building right, as they quickly and easily support the attainment of some human rights hindered by the unhealthy environment, but first, they do not operate on their root cause, and second, they do not provide a durable solution. The donation of a borehole, which is highly aspired by the people in the village (field notes), is able to grant water today, offsetting droughts issues, but if in one/two years it breaks then the population gets back to point zero of not having water, due to the unsustainable costs of repairing and maintaining the facility. This mechanism not only does not build right, but also creates a dangerous dependency on external actors (Brian, 4.2.1.). The best measure in which it is benefitting the population is as a temporary coping mechanism in the meanwhile the environment is slowly healed.

With the same logic, also emergency measures are hence not building right: after floods, as it is more frequent, big national and international NGOs contribute to rescue the affected population with distributions of food, providing hospital beds, and other services, and this is fundamental for the protection of the people, but has an impact only on them, and none on the environment. It is extremely useful, but it is not building the “healthy environment” at the core of the right discussed here. One might counterargue that this is not correct, and that the protection of the subjects who are to benefit of the right is part of the process; this argument might be valid, but is not able *per se* to build right: it can be asserted as preferable, if not even necessary, but definitely not sufficient.

A similar conclusion can be reached about mitigation and adaptation strategies.

The first ones generally include initiatives aimed at diminishing the damaging power of human activities on the environment and vice versa the severity of the impact of the unhealthy environment effects on the people. Examples are respectively a cap on carbon emissions, which only decreases how much man is continuing to pollute but has no active impact towards a positive and constructive effect, and measures applied to school fees, which help to guarantee the right to education when the consequences of living in an unhealthy environment would impair it (e.g.: paying only one fee at the beginning of the year in order to avoid problems of unaffordability if drought comes and hence avoid forced school discontinuity (Mr. David).

Adaptation measures operate likewise, to diminish the impact of environmental issues by bringing adjustments to human activities, anticipating the disaster adversities with something that is able to resist it: the most prominent examples are the use of greenhouses for farming; the spread by local NGOs of the knowledge and distribution of seeds of cassava, which is a drought-resistant crop, and of new maize-varieties as Kalro that start maturing earlier, before it gets too hot. This way they ensure that food security is less endangered by environmental extreme events, but do nothing for them to cease. Adaptation measures rather build a right to live [*safely*] in an *unhealthy* environment.

The problem with both mitigation and adaptation measures is that they operate on the *consequences* rather than on the causes, *id est* on reducing the magnitude of an unhealthy environment effects on other human rights rather than on eliminating the very origin of those negative effects. As for emergency ones, these measures are extremely

useful and important, but for the sake of the research, they are not building HRHE. Again, one might counterargue that they do participate to it because ensures protection of the people over time, and it is true that if one looks at reality, achieving a healthy environment intuitively requires a lot of time, hence all of these measures can be pragmatically said to build HRHE in the measure that they provide protection *in the meantime* a healthy environment is achieved. However, this approach can be harmful itself: first, action on consequences can result highly fragmented, due to the risk multiplier effect seen in *Section 5.1.2*, and thus dispersive and inefficient; secondly, it can drive people and institutions to give up the idea to work on the environment, because in any case they will reduce or adapt, leading towards stagnation or even aggravation of the current health status of nature.

ELEMENTS THAT *DO* BUILD RIGHT

Initiatives that build right result to be long-term and root-aiming ones, in a process that includes cessation (not mitigation) of any possible damaging behaviour, reparation (active construction of a healthy environment), and conservation of it (for a durable enjoyment of the right).

Cessation of unsustainable behaviours concerns remarkably individuals and multinational corporations. The shift away from wood fuels as charcoal and deforestation trends, the sensitisation to do organic farming instead of employing synthetic fertilisers, the stop to monoculture that further impoverishes the soil, are being fundamental to move towards more a sustainable human stay on Mother Earth. The next step should be to also stop waste (especially plastics) abandonment and burning, and set up a structured waste management. Multinational corporations are currently being limited by a ban on single-use plastics in their plastic production, yet always lobbying and pushing to ease the policy; it would be precious if they would stop exploiting excessively and unfairly the territorial resources (especially those already limited as water), and if they consistently reduced their carbon footprint. National and international policy making has a high impact on the way corporations conduct their productive processes, and the recommendation and hope is that further tightening, in a sustainable measure in economic terms, will be issued.

Environment healing process cannot be carried on efficiently if degrading activities keep going on; however, cessation is not enough, and an active action of reparation and reconstruction is equally needed. Activities of reparation include first and foremost tree planting in Kisumu County, where the alteration of the water cycle is at the core of the most severe environmental issues (prolonged droughts, violent floods). Cut-one-tree-plant-two policy from the government, sensitisation from local activists social movements, implementation from local environmental organisations and associations, are measures that actively contribute to restore the health of the environment. From what emerged during the research on field, this in particular seems the phase that is prominently being gone through in the examined villages and surrounding area, while cessation routes have already been taken by many individuals, less by business enterprises.

If “the situation has improved, but environmental rights are still building”, it is because reparation and cessation are both equally important, especially as some features of environmental health cannot be anthropogenic: pollution for example, can only be quitted to grant vegetation and animal well-being, it cannot be offset as deforestation.

The common feature to both key actions is their continuity: stopping polluting for one day only or planting a tree but do not take care of it are useless if not endured over time. Stability of sustainable behaviour and durable results are a key to build a healthy environment, both in the sense of just reaching that status and maintain it (realising a right ensuring it *de facto*, in the present, and *in potentia*, in the future). The implication is that without conservation strategies of both attitudes and results, a right cannot be said “consolidated”: as the adjective says, it has to be “solid” over generations, as prescribed by the principle of sustainability intrinsically embedded in any type of environmental rights. It is the characteristic that grants *durability*, the key feature of right construction.

5.2.2 *From above and from below: considerations on their roles and relationship*

ACTION FROM ABOVE

Institutional bodies broadly contribute in a wide range of modalities to the HRHE consolidation. The first is by having recognised it. Legal recognition, as already concluded in the previous section, mostly acts as an “ethical pronouncements as to what *should be done*”, confirming Sen’s intuition, and this is the role played by the inclusion of the right to live in a healthy environment in the Kenyan Constitution (Art.42, 2010) by President Kibaki. This formal assertion has been a trigger of change, boosting legislative and social activism, giving a direction to policymakers and raising awareness among the community.

Ontological consolidation processes of the HRHE have here started at international level, within global or regional bodies, developing language and conceptualisation that could be useful to frame the right in smaller contexts as the national one: the Stockholm Treaty, the Rio Declaration, the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights, and UNGA resolution. For the rest, the core of the activities of international organisations is reporting and standard setting, with an informative and a regulatory role. IOs, such as UNCTAD, WTO, UNEP, UNDP, mostly collect data, analyse them and produce statistical reports that can be useful to set objectives and standards to be employed as reference in agreements stipulation and national or local policy making on the matter.

Vertical subsidiarity and cooperation among institutions of different levels resulted to be highly important, with the national government acting as a bridge between IOs and local communities by incorporating and enforcing international regulations and standards, and managing the funds received. In fact, even if in a smaller measure than what be commonly thought, IOs also issue funds to implement development projects at local level, which can enable targeted and hence more efficacious action locally. The international funds reaching the most Kisumu County come from development banks as the WB and the EU. They often also put conditions, based on academic research and scholarly agreed features, which drive those projects towards larger inclusivity and enhanced efficacy over time, for instance the involvement of at least 50% of women.

According to the perception of people from the village, money-giving strategies have not been successful, especially in past times when they were more frequent, due to

the high levels of corruption in the Kenyan institutions. Different perceptions, however, came from respondents with an institutional social and working background, claiming for the impossibility of money retention over the vertical chain, due to the severe anti-corruption measures and thanks to digitalisation processes enhancing transparency. The truth appeared to be in the middle: corruption might have been high and hindering aid from abroad, but being decreasing in latter times. Bribing, however, remains commonly practiced in less formal contexts, for instance not fining when finding someone cutting trees, and this, together with low monitoring is a considerable obstacle to the success of national and local policy, even when they appear to be strategic as in the case of cut-one-tree-plant-two and of the ban on single-use plastics. This latter example, whereby people simply illegally imports it from the neighbouring Rwanda, was key to reveal an important conclusion: the core of policy ineffectiveness is the lack of people's ownership. A circumventing strategy will always be possible to find if really wanted to, and it is just easier when monitoring and enforcement are low; top-down imposition of measures is useless, even if they might potentially build right, if not sincerely shared by those who should put them in practice. Neither a tight monitoring, though, without agreement to the policy would be a correct path: first, is not sustainable over time, given the political turnover, and secondly, it would not be democratic.

Raising awareness is the only way to lead to community ownership of a cause, and provided how much the latter is important, this becomes a very important element of HRHE construction. While the origin of the claim is rooted in the society, the institutions start to play an echo role of those voices, by not only bringing the topic on international tables or recognising the right, but also actively promoting initiatives and campaigning among the population to spread awareness. Policy enforcement, as those already mentioned, results not to be enough alone standing, but projects as the SEACAP (Sustainable Energy Access and Climate Action), where a youth group was involved to raise public awareness on proper solid waste management, and the recruitment of experts sent to hold trainings and teaching in the community, stemmed out to be more effective.

The CIDP (County Integrated Development Plan) initiative of Kenyan counties, that is a plan designed through extensive public participation aimed at providing a guide for the county development activities and public investment, resulted to yield in Kisumu

County highly fruitful results and significant achievements in the construction of a durably healthier environment. Another governmental policy remarked by many interviewed for its relevance and success was the Kenya Climate Smart Agriculture Project (KCSAP), this time at national level, which provides support in case of emergency and in ordinary times engages territorially with local farmers to teach them more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices and enhance resilience. Other relevant projects from above were identified in the SEACAP and the Kisumu County Climate Change Act. The common element to all these policies, distinguishing them from all the others, is the centrality of community engagement within their design and implementation processes.

The key takeaway from this evidence is that an “above-below” collaborative approach is the most successful strategy for the sake of pursuing a lasting and sustainable HRHE, with “the above” having the role of “assisting [the community] in doing the right thing”, given that “the community plays the major role” in building a HRHE (Ms. Quinter, from the Irrigation Department of the County Government of Kisumu). In light of this, the next paragraph will consider and evaluate the action from below, drawing conclusions on whether it actually plays the major role, and eventually how and for which reasons, within the process analysed.

ACTION FROM BELOW

The community is an actor that builds right from below, but also not the only one of the category, in which were identified in the considered territory: associations in organised forms of people from the community (CBOs or NGOs) constitute different autonomous players that act autonomously and even interact with this same community from which they stem out from; similar organisations originated on a national base (as Red Cross Kenya), established abroad or of international range of action (respectively as IBO Italia and Action Aid); individuals from the local community, or from abroad, playing different roles, such as a villager, a volunteer, a donor, or a head of corporation; banks and companies also revealed as an emerging actor in their way.

Among these, local NGOs resulted to be with regard to the construction of HRHE, the most prominent actor, in terms of activeness and impact. Given their closeness to the community, from which they directly stem out from, they play a significant role of bridge between institutions and the people of the different villages, facilitating policy implementation on the ground in a top-down mechanism, and interaction over a bottom-up approach. Respectively, they may operate on behalf of the national government in some projects for the sake of effectiveness, for example in seedlings distribution, being trusted and having a wider outreach over individual households, and they can empower people to have their voices heard, with their issues and needs reaching institutional fora.

Not only NGOs play as an echo to those voices towards the top, but also implement measures themselves on the “down” level. Those activities will not have to be the same as actions from above, and any initiative shall always have to be approved and monitored by county or national authorities. This is significant as it highlights some implications about the relationship between above and below: first, it shows that the interaction is overall meant to be constructive, collaborative, and complementary, discouraging forms of full horizontal subsidiarity (or NGOs would otherwise lose their non-governmental character), or competition, where the two operate independently from each other risking duplicating projects or even conflict. Instead, sharing skills and resources, as in the successful CIDP model, and a continuous dialectic exchange between above and below can be beneficial and exponentially boost progress, for the sake of building right. Also, it emerges, on the one hand, how authorities have the ultimate power to obstacle or block civil society activities to build right, hence it becomes necessary that those who rule are themselves owners of the cause of protection of the environment, and/or not influenced by any economic or political interests that could be in contrast with environmental human rights; on the other hand, they have a check on community initiatives, which shall not be taken as absolute good as a matter of principle, but always analysed and advised by professionals where possible, and monitored as for their implementation by a super-partes entity. In both cases, corruption can be highly detrimental, and it is for this reason that the lately issued anti-corruption and transparency policies are essential.

Asserted the horizontal relation with the above as part of the process of building a right to a healthy environment in Kisumu County, the study of local NGOs' (CIVS Kenya, Victoria Fresh, The Green World, CBO) activity, and in general of the whole civil society, on the ground also yielded material for further considerations about successful models and fundamental elements that participate to right construction. While the appropriateness of the technical measures is already substantiated by academy and science (e.g. tree planting efficacy for the hydric cycle restoration), it possible to analyse which of them are effective only in the field of mitigation or adaptation and which do actually build right, as well as the role that social measures play (such as sensitisation, calls for joining, community engagement and empowerment, accessibility guarantees, teaching and trainings, monitoring), revealing important implications also on the role of the community and of the other actors of the civil society.

First, NGOs, stemming out directly from the community as associations of individuals to tackle community problems –in this case of environmental nature–, inevitably have already an intrinsic community ownership of their initiatives; besides this, they all resulted to operate with a very tight engagement of the whole village collectivity from the design to the implementation of any project, enhancing that ownership that already proved to be necessary to build right. Not all measures that come from people's needs, however, actually contribute to restore the environment health: the popular opinion on boreholes as solutions to water scarcity indeed only contributes to a pathologic mechanism of dependency on external resources to mitigate its consequent harsh effects, but does nothing to eliminate the problem of droughts, recalling *Section 0*. While sometimes not pertaining the process under study in this research, nevertheless the dialectic exchange and confrontation with the community from the more attentive ear of NGOs can lead the very same community to discover the root cause of their problems to be grounded in environmental issue, raising their awareness and ownership of any initiative aiming at solving it. This successful model is perfectly explained by the experience of Mr. Dilman having asked the community what they would have wanted CIVS to do for them, and having the women soliciting for a kindergarten to have time to farm. He investigated in-depth the reasons behind this need by asking them, and discovered a problem of food and economic security related to the period of drought, to which those girls tried to respond with more extensive and intensive farming, employing

also synthetic boosters, without knowing they were doing theirs and the environment's bad in terms of health. He convened with them to also offer for free classes and trainings for sustainable agriculture and agribusiness. This deeply inquiring attitude and strategy to individuate the root cause operating (also) on that one besides that on effects mitigation is highly successful and will be indicated within the considerations of this research as a model for any intention to build HRHE in this and similar areas from whatever level of action. By collaborative study and investigation with the community it allows to raise awareness of the problem and ownership of the measures, granting committed participation and durability of the actions undertaken, among which the cessation of the unsustainable behaviour, and eventually also of reparation and conservation activities.

To raise this fundamental awareness, NGOs not only engage in dialogue with the people to discover the problem together, but also spread knowledge and information about already scientifically accredited unsustainable behaviours, to raise sensitisation to stop them (e.g., deforestation, sugarcane and waste burning, chemical agricultural methods), and about eco-friendly practices to start employing, trying to transmit the urgent character of environmental protection for the sake of nature and of humans. In order to do so they hold seminars, distribute flyers, and visit schools with the aim of informing and educating adults of today and of tomorrow.

Awareness is also raised within the civil society by international social movements as FridaysForFuture, especially through internet and social media among the youth, and by national and local activists, that reach people through the radio, television, transmitting their campaigning and their battles. Particularly influential at local level has been the Kenyan Peace Nobel Prize Wangari Maathai, who founded the Green Belt Movement in 1977, and advocated to highlight the urgency of reforestation, respect for the environment and restoration of its biodiversity and conservation. The movement lead and started by Greta Thunberg, instead has triggered an international mobilisation of youth claiming for environmental protection and reparation, that has attracted attention also from public and private sectors, which cannot ignore anymore the calls for sustainability. Social claims, confirming the literature, have a great power to start processes to build a new human right felt as needing recognition and implementation.

The two awareness and ownership are indispensable to solicit another element that resulted to be essential to build durably a HRHE: participation to the process. It would be insufficient, if not almost useless, to have only some NGOs planting trees, or only some households to stop using chemicals in farming, or again only one company to cut emissions, in order to bring structural change. Yet, each of them is indispensable. It results necessary that the community is actively involved in the implementation of cessation, reparation, and conservation measures, to consistently build right. This means not only local people, but the whole part of the society that can have an impact on the environment shall be involved and be an “active citizen”: it would require those at the head of companies or multilateral corporations to cease unfair resources exploitation or CO₂ emissions; banks and businesses to support financially sustainability schemes; international NGOs to share knowledge, material and human resources, and to cooperate to build right; volunteers from local areas and from abroad helping in projects implementation; donors providing monetary or material resources when lacking other means to participate to the process. In active (aware and committed, owning the cause!) participation as element of the realisation process, emerges the importance of the individual and collective dimension of HRHE, confirming the literature and the implications regarding its ontology and impacts concluded in the previous Section.

The importance of participation is clear to the NGOs operating in Kisumu, who work extensively to engage as many individuals as possible from the villages: they spread the news of free seminars and lessons by word-of-mouth and referral, or sending volunteer to mobilise the people. They remain always ready to welcome newcomers, and if they are too many they plan a collective class to answer their questions. Such availability and accessibility encourages people to join, having nothing to lose but only to gain. NGOs staff members also visit community common spaces, as churches and schools, planting trees to give an example and reach the people, and leave open the possibility to give seedlings to households if they will learn to grow them sustainably.

The main technical strategy employed by environmental NGOs in Kisumu, in sum, is tree planting, by themselves and by spreading the practice among the community, to restore the cycle of water, hence predictable the rain patterns, bearable droughts and flooding avoidance, through reforestation. “Tree is life, environment is life!”, with the words of the principal of one of the schools we visited.

However, the real strategic measure is the social approach of implementing it: education. They equip people with the information, knowledge, and material means, needed to cease unsustainable behaviours and employ eco-friendly ones, raising a collective aware and committed participation of as many as possible. They do this by providing the classes, but also by carrying on a “model farm” where they grow crops with organic fertilisers autonomously produced from compost and prepare seedlings to plant or distribute, with the ultimate scope of providing people with a living example that they can visit whenever they want. Recalling the found need for “conservation” measures (*id est* keeping not polluting, or taking care of a tree after planting it, etc.), they also employ the social measure of monitoring the work of those who take the seedlings, to check they take care correctly of them visiting them two or three times a year, with an attitude of constructive teaching rather than punitive, as Mr. Paul demonstrated. As for institutional policy, it not would be possible to carry monitoring activities forever or play the role of watchdog: it is imperative that the same who engage in ceasing a degrading behaviour, in neutral ones, or in repairing practices, *autonomously* keep doing so.

“To use in cooking *ugali* (typical Kenyan dish), I cannot give you flour every day, but I can give you seeds and a *jembe* (a mattock).”

(Brian, 27yo, CIVS volunteer and CBO staff)

What organisations, international and local ones, but also institutions, should do, is to provide the community, internationally and locally, with the *means and capabilities* to build right themselves, engaging autonomously and successfully in the three measures of cessation, reparation and conservation on their own durably over time. The research yields empirical verification of the effectiveness of Amartya Sen’s “capability approach” (see *Section 1.2.2*), as combination of individual “abilities” and external “opportunities”: to reach the “functioning” of living in a healthy environment, the person shall be capable to build that condition by herself. Actors from above and from below, –and even better– their synergetic collaboration, can fundamentally accelerate the development of those abilities and create opportunities, or at least live space to build, refraining obstacles. They can and shall “assist the community in doing the right thing”, but “the community plays the major role” (Ms. Quinter, 2025).

Conclusions

Synthesis of findings

The research, conducted with an ethnographic approach and analysing the subject from the voices of the people involved, yielded that the environment in Kisumu County, the Kenyan region under study, is not healthy. It presents evidence of deadly violent floods, unpredictable and prolonged periods of severe drought, unprecedented anthropogenic climate change, polluted air, soil and waters, which had never manifested to this extent before human activities started to have such a degrading impact on the environment, nourishing a progressively unhealthy and unclean condition of it.

The human dimension of the right at stake does not regard only the leading causes of the current status, but also the subjects of the consequent impacts. The environment is not healthy also for the people living in it, provoking devastating effects, sufferance and distress, hindering and violating innumerable other human rights. Environmental unhealth, in fact, resulted to be a *risk multiplier*, increasing both the very same number of rights under threat, and the probability that those rights will be breached. In this area, the reported issues are drivers of low quality or scarce water for drinking and hygiene, exposing the population to water-borne and other diseases, with vulnerability increased by the inaccessibility of healthcare facilities and infrastructure that get damaged or destroyed by floods; floods also destroy the fragile schools and houses in mud and cow dung causing displacement and school discontinuity; also the common emergency measure of rescuing people in schools contributes to hinder education; water scarcity also fuels crops failure and livestock mortality, provoking food insecurity and poverty, eventually leading to stress and mental health issues, household conflicts and domestic violence, or again social unrest and threats to peace and security. Human rights to life and health (Art. 3), adequate standards of living (Art.25), desirable work (Art.23), quality (Art. 1), to liberty (Art. 3), property (Art. 17), family and home (Art. 8), and free movement (Art.13), as well as to education (Art. 26), to rest and leisure (Art. 24), and social security (Art. 22), are all hindered by one single condition. For this reason, for its wide impact, the need to *substantially* build a human right to a healthy environment is more urgent than ever.

The voices of the people interviewed in the villages were often broken, filled with sentiments of distress, exhaustion, melancholy, unveiling effort and a strong spirit of resilience, yet also hope and belief in a better future, with a genuine smile of brotherhood. The need to act now is impellent.

Indeed, the research yielded that action is already ongoing, although it definitely has to continue and grow, but this allowed to carry and in-depth qualitative study of the undergoing processes of HRHE consolidation in the area, understanding what measures are building right and which not, and how do the several actors participate and interact. As a result, mitigation and adaptation measures operate to reduce the impact of the consequences listed above, but not on their root cause, which is the environment unhealth; for this to build it is necessary that subjects engage in *cessation* of any possible damaging behaviour, active *reparation* of the environment's health, and *conservation* of each of these measures, to ensure a sustainable and durable realisation of the right over time.

The community –local and international, each single person– is the ultimate and only one indispensable actor that can realise the human right to a healthy environment. People's *participation* to the process, in their individual and collective dimension, is fundamental, with the means and *capabilities* to actively and correctly build right, in terms of knowledge and practice. This is not possible without *awareness* of the problem, without full and transparent information, and without *ownership* of the cause, of the will and commitment to change and construct.

Notwithstanding the centrality of the community, the synergy of institutional entities (the “above”) and actors from the civil society (the “below”) results fundamental to develop those elements mentioned above as essential to build right. The consolidation of the human right to a healthy environment unfolds through a constant dialectic between action from above and from below, each indispensable yet insufficient alone. Institutions have proven crucial in boosting the HRHE consolidation process through legal recognition (see the case of the 2010 Constitution), and in enabling progress conditions through data collection, reporting, strategic funding (especially international organisations), and policy design (in particular, at national and county level). Yet, their impact resulted limited when not met by an aware ownership of the community. It is the most successful when engaging directly with the people living those environmental issues

in both designing and implementing measures, to expand the investigation leading to individuate the root problems on which to operate, decide together a strategy, and ensuring adherence to its realisation. In this process, NGOs have in Kisumu County an important bridging role between the above and the receivers, being entrusted by and closer to the latter. Also, they work independently with the aim of empowering the community, by providing them, through training courses and by running a model farm, with knowledge and means to operationalise the desired change by themselves every day. Their activity of empowerment consists of both education and listening, giving them the power to do, but also to have raise their voices and have them heard. In sum, local NGOs translate top-down mechanisms into practical, lasting change on the ground, and support day-by-day community capacity building to construct the right by themselves, avoiding any dependence. International organisations have also a bridging role, but between international institutional organisations, which usually provide funds (this is especially the case for the EU) and local NGOs, for them to use them properly on the ground. Individuals play a fundamental role too in the process: volunteers and donors on the operational side, social movements and activists on raising awareness and accelerating the process of the human right ontological consolidation and encouraging will of participation to its realisation, at both local and international level. The people, in the end, are the ultimately responsible of the real change, in their individual and collective dimensions: they are the only ones needed to cease those damaging behaviours, engage in reparation ones, and conserving both these two initiatives durably over time.

As an overall conclusion, the community is at the centre of the process that can build the human right to a healthy environment, giving empirical meaning to its theoretical ontology of “collective right”. Its construction results successful when the people are *aware* of the problem, *own* the cause and the measures to solve it over the long-term, *participate* to process, and have the *capabilities* to carry it on their own.

Nevertheless, a synergetic action of actors from above and from below is equally necessary, as a support the community in the process, which alone would be too slow or even not be able to develop the four elements above. Most impactful outcomes remain those stemmed from the continuous dialectic exchange between the two levels, with a constructive, collaborative, and complementary attitude (not of subsidiarity, indifferent or even competitive or conflicting) aimed at empowering the community.

If the human right to a healthy environment is “still building”, it is imperative to keep working and to involve more and more people in taking action. The process to reach a collective human right as this is, can be very long, or even endless, as it does not have a defined “arrival point”; however, it is fundamental to work consistently and collectively to tend towards it as much as possible, in a perspective of “reducing social injustice”, as Amartya Sen theorised.

Further research directions

Interesting insights also emerged from the study on intersectional topics and would need further research to be deepened in their relation to the construction of the HRHE in this part of Kenya, verifying if a bond also exists in other geographical or political contexts, or in connection to the consolidation process of other human rights.

Education is the first macro-area to raise interest: the implications of the empirical results of the analysis yielded that teaching and training are essential to have awareness of the importance to preserve the health of the environment, knowledge of the core issues, ability to distinguish sustainable or regenerative behaviours from harmful ones, and means and capabilities to put them in practice. The major attention in this regard has been put on the development of specific environment-related coaching (e.g.: the experts sent by the county government, or Mr. Paul demonstrating in the community or within his model farm), but it emerged that also general schooling has had a positive effect on the population: the generation grown up with the *Free Education Programme* of President Kibaki, which for the first time rendered school accessible to everybody -even the poorest families-, perceived herself as more open in mindset towards environmental consideration and ready to learn new sustainable practices than previous and present generations (even if in smaller measure). This first confirms that policy from above can have huge impact in enabling or obstacle conditions for developing capabilities, and secondly suggests that in the same measure and modality in which the environment status of health can indirectly impact many other rights, then also the realisation of other human rights can have an indirect impact on building a healthy (or unhealthy) environment. If children can access school, then they might grow more open-minded and learning-oriented, but also develop

professional skills to be more likely employed when adults. Employment in turn increases the likelihood to enjoy adequate standards of life and reduces the likeliness to struggle in conditions of poverty, which is one of the reasons why people see themselves constrained to adopt the most affordable product, as single-use plastics or Coca-Cola consumption (nourishing the multinational corporation's resources exploitation), or to employ synthetic fertilisers in the desperate tentative to foster intensive farming to yield more food and possibly saleable surpluses. A durably implemented policy acting on job placement facilitation or mitigating poverty, maybe could have a positive effect on HRHE. This would definitely need more space for investigation, to support institutions and the government in their activity of policymaking. An examination of the topics locally related to environment respect would be particularly recommended to verify whether operating in them could indirectly bring positive effects on HRHE consolidation.

Women engagement also emerged to be a pivotal strategy to accelerate the process of building a healthy environment in the examined area: mothers are here the core of the family, carrying on household farming work and raising children; by respectively employing sustainable agricultural methods and by transmitting to their kids the importance of environmental sensitiveness, they can have an immediate concrete impact by on the ground, in literal sense, and a formational one by shaping the minds of tomorrow. For this reason, I think the quote by Ms. Quinter already mentioned "women are ambassadors of change" hits so much and leaves much food for thought. It is appreciable that entities as the World Bank have already grasped the importance of women here, requiring a participation of theirs of at least 50% in all the projects funded by them. Since it emerged that this centrality of women in households (recall "in Kenya, everything is on the mother") is a national cultural feature of family structures, it could be interesting to understand whether women empowerment could be a successful strategy on the whole territory. In addition, another direct link to this characteristic resulted to be a responsibility factor of the mother: it is on her also the task of ensuring food on the table; when this is lacking, in times of drought, non-fulfilment can trigger domestic conflict, ultimately escalating in violence, which is this case results thus gender based. It would be interesting to further explore the connection between gender-equality and an unhealthy environment where to grow up, and try to realise oneself.

The private sector emerged to have an increasingly growing role in relation to the health status of the environment, both in terms of damage and in terms of reparation. In the first sense, the reason stems out from the fast industrialisation and globalisation process of the last century, leading companies to irresponsibly exploit territorial resources and emitting high levels of CO₂ in the air. This is actually one of the major causes of pollution and of climate change, and it is in light of this that they have a great power, to harm, but also to stop harming. If cessation is the first key strategy to build environmental health, then the private sector has a leading role in the process.

However, another phenomenon was detected in this realm: the global increase in sensitiveness to ecology and ecosystems conservation and regeneration, lead the international institutional community to issue regulations on private companies, as the milestone Global Compact of 1999, and the progressive reinforcement of the call for a sustainable development, from the Brundtland Commission 1987 slowly to the SDGs formulation. The new trend of the last decade is that the environmental sensitiveness of the civil society found correspondence in its consumer behaviour, often preferring choosing green products. Companies adapting to international regulations and to those market mechanisms have increasingly to improve their ecological reputation and image, and consequently engage in implementing sustainability policies to reduce their carbon footprint for example within their supply chain of production, performing compensation policy or engaging in local and international cooperation projects to fulfil corporate social responsibility (CSR) and ESG sustainability requirements.

Rooted in this market development lies the origin of the nascent wide amount of resources employed by private companies and banks in support to projects devoted to environmental protection and reparation (most frequently with local NGOs). Given that fundings are extremely important to allow for the effective execution of action (also) to build right, the private sector inevitably gets to significantly contribute to the process of consolidation of HRHE. One example is the local company Simulo Seeds providing CIVS with seeds to be distributed for free among the village, with the business interest to have those people going back to that company to buy more, or the private financial cooperative SACCO, which issues affordable credit to its members to ensure them as long clients. But, to which extent is intention relevant when evaluating the participation to a process of right-construction? The doubt is that money might here be distributed without attention to the type of project, for instance: whether it operates to mitigate or to repair; to yield

immediate effects for image improvement or maybe less visible but long-term durable results: or again whether it is imposed or correctly engaging with the community, etc. The scepticism around this money inflow is further motivated by the empirical failure of institutional “giving pattern” witnessed by respondents; issues of transparency would in this case be more severe due to informality or more controlled due to shorter connections? Has the new pattern of funding a high potential, or does it hide a threat or slowdown to right construction? Many questions raise on the topic, that would need more in-depth investigation.

One other insight to be examined might be determining whether the private actor shall be in the future, or even already today, defined as an independent actor in the process of HRHE construction, in Kisumu County but in this case also worldwide, given the universality of companies and banks development and behaviour in the globalised era. The political scientist Victor Pestoff has indeed developed a triangular model of public service provision that separately and actively involves the three parts of State, market, and society, in engaging in a co-production synergy to provide welfare and social goods (Pestoff, 2012). Being environmental health possible to be considered as a public or social good, an analysis of whether the same model –hiving off the private sector from the actors of the civil society– could be applied to the construction of the human right to a healthy environment, locally but also universally maybe, could be interesting. Overall, it is definitely a new aspect that needs to be deepened for the sake of understanding what could accelerate or hamper the process.

Contributions to the field

Environmental discourse is still very young, intensifying since the last decades, and intensified globally especially after the exacerbation of global warming manifesting around 2015-2016 and accompanied by devastating extreme weather events worldwide. The connection to man that frames a *human right* to a healthy environment, instead, is not as popular yet in social discourses. The present research contributes to the dissemination of information and sensitisation regarding the impellent need for a substantial recognition of such a right in binding pieces of international law, in national constitutions and in social discourse. It contributes to field research mainly in three ways.

First, it enriches the increasing literature on the topic with a human local experience: it shows the consequences of not enjoying a healthy environment by the very personal stories, perceptions and emotions of the people living in this condition (*Chapter III*). Thanks to the ethnographic approach it is able to put the researcher and in turn the reader in the shoes of the respondents for a while serving as echo to their voices, and this is precious to get the human dimension that the environment has.

Secondly, real life witnesses can be useful also to give a more targeted direction to action in the local territory; more specifically, the second set of research (*Chapter IV*) regarding the qualitative study of the processes consolidating the right up to now, analysing which actions do build right and which not, what elements are deemed as necessary to produce durable right, together with individuating the most successful strategies singularly and in the interaction between the actors of this route, can definitely give a direction to policy-makers, civil society to improve their action and accelerate the path towards the realisation of the right to a healthy environment in Kisumu County, as well as a basis to other academic experts to add to this research on intersectional aspects to provide further assistance based on theory and empirical evidence.

Thirdly, while it is true that being a social construct in terms of both origin and of realisation, locality is at the centre of its ontology and consideration, and results are thus not suitable for generalisation when looking for implications and contributions to the field, yet the research can still be useful for comparisons and experience: other local realities with similar characteristics (e.g. rural areas, subject to droughts, with high levels of poverty, and an averagely stable political situation) might use the qualitative study of the consolidation process carried on here to take operational example from the models individuated as successful, or avoid strategies that revealed ineffective. Share of data, local experiences and best practices is a highly used method among countries (especially within the UN system, as I was able to witness in first person) to improve governance and decision-making at country and regional level.

Limitations

One limitation of the study is exactly related to this latter comment: if this kind of research was made more extensively and in geographical areas with different specific features, it would be possible to create a sort of mapping where to pull information from in order to boost more strategically the process of building a human right to a healthy environment.

Time and financial resources constraints are undoubtedly a huge limitation to the implementation of a study that can be useful to its utmost. With more resources, I could have stayed longer on the ground as a researcher, interviewing more people and collecting more data: maybe some new aspects would have emerged as an insight to be deepened. In the study of this kind of right, in fact, the individual dimension is central, as it emerged, and every story could be crucial to understand and learn more about the process. The number and also the feature differentiation of the pool of subjects interviewed represents in facts the major limitation of the study: the intention would have been to reach more people from institutional frameworks, more from village, and while some diversity in age, gender, and social background is already there, increasing it would have definitely improved the research by diminishing bias possibilities by category belongings.

Recommendations

The first recommendation, in light of what just highlighted above, would for sure be to continue doing research in this field: human rights to a healthy environment need to take a defined shape worldwide, and academic investigation is essential to this. Doing this extensively and with a qualitative, in-depth approach would enable actors to use the results to translate more efficiently their intentions into strategies.

The second, is to commit to this consolidation. This study wants to make you, reader, aware of the problem, aware of how it is in Kisumu, and aware that other places would also struggle in their relation with the environment, and would need targeted analysis and policy recommendations. Mine is to hence to take this awareness, if I succeeded in creating some, and own the cause; then, take part to the process. This recommendation is addressed to you, reader from the academia; to you reader from an institution; and you, an ordinary citizen, who might become an *active* citizen tomorrow.

And last, my strongest recommendation is to remember to look for the human aspect of things, to give value to the voices of the people, as it is in the human experience that lies the source, or effect, of whatever we would like to build, especially *human rights*.

“Bring change from inside”

Figure 29. Kolunga Primary School, October 8th, 2024.

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Abbreviations

CBO: Community Based Organisation

ECHAV: Empower vulnerable Communities through Humanitarian Aid Volunteers

ECHR: European Charter on Human Rights

ECtHR: European Court of Human Rights

ESC: European Solidarity Corps

ESG: Environment, Social, Governance

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization

GDP: Gross Domestic Product

HRHE: human right to a healthy environment

IACtHR: Inter-American Court of Human Rights

ICCPR: International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights

ICESCR: International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights

IOs: international organizations

NGO: non-governmental organization

SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals

UDHR: Universal Declaration of Human Rights

UNCHR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

UNCTAD: United Nations Conference for Trade and Development

UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme

UNDP: United Nations Development Programme

yo: years old

WMO: World Meteorological Organization

WTO: World Trade Organisation